

LIABILITY IN TELEMEDICINE IN NIGERIA

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CERTIFICATION

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DEDICATION

To Chibundu, the sister I never met, snatched away as an infant through the cold hands of pneumonia...

To Ms. Mary, my favourite teacher that I will never meet again on this side of the universe because she was a childbirth-martyr...

And to the thousands of families across Nigeria that have lost loved ones because the state of healthcare is not what it is supposed to be...

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ABSTRACT

Telemedicine holds immense potential for improving access to healthcare, particularly in low-resource settings such as Nigeria. By leveraging information and communication technologies (ICT), telemedicine enables healthcare professionals to exchange medical information, offer diagnoses, and provide treatment regardless of geographical distance, ultimately improving patient outcomes. However, the absence of specific legislation on telemedicine in Nigeria has resulted in a fragmented legal framework, exposing patients to potential exploitation and impeding widespread adoption. This long essay takes a patient-centric approach that aims to identify the liabilities that may arise in the practice of telemedicine in Nigeria, with the objective of fostering a safer telemedicine ecosystem and enhancing healthcare delivery in the country.

Employing doctrinal methodology and a content analysis approach, this study critically analyses existing statutory and case laws, legal commentaries, and peer-reviewed articles. It utilises the theoretical framework of remedial liability and argues that while telemedicine does not introduce a new category of liability, it does present novel issues within existing liabilities in the intersection of healthcare and ICT that requires clarification, such as establishing breach of duty and causation, noting that it might make it more difficult for patients to prove negligence in the event of medical errors. Furthermore, with regards to the principle of informed consent, there are gaps to be filled particularly for individuals lacking capacity and establishing liability boundaries. Moreover, new regulations on data protection as well as increasing cybersecurity risks expands the liability of telemedicine providers, medical professionals, and third-party actors. Telemedicine also presents issues in regulation and licensure of medical professionals with the possibility of fraud and implications of cross-border telemedicine. On a positive note, the presence of third-party actors and new statutory developments broadens the scope of potential liability. This development in medical law brought to fore by telemedicine positively influences the outcomes of litigation for aggrieved patients, as it expands the avenues for holding responsible parties accountable.

By elucidating the liabilities associated with telemedicine practice and proposing recommendations to mitigate risks, the findings of this essay contributes to the establishment of a safer telemedicine ecosystem in Nigeria. It provides insights for policymakers, medical practitioners, legal professionals, and the entire telemedicine ecosystem that will be critical to

the widespread adoption of telemedicine to change the face of healthcare delivery in the country.

Key Words: *Telemedicine, Liability, Medical Professional, Patients.*

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

NITDA – National Information Technology Development Agency

NCC – Nigeria Communications Commission

OAU – Organization of African Unity

PBoR – Patients’ Bill of Rights

UHDR – Universal Declaration of Human Rights

UN – United Nations

UN OHCHR – United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights

WHO – World Health Organization

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background Of Study

While the right to life has been recognised as a necessary foundation of human liberties, the enjoyment of that life can only be guaranteed by good health.¹ As such, access to quality healthcare is increasingly prioritised not only in human rights discourses,² but also in promoting sustainable development given the significant interrelationships between health and socio-economic outcomes.³ However, access to quality healthcare has been a critical challenge in developing countries like Nigeria.

Nigeria's healthcare sector can best be described as being in a state of crisis. It experiences severe underfunding, falling below the World Health Organisation (WHO)'s recommended budget allocation of 15% of total budget.⁴ Health workers are poorly motivated due to inadequate remuneration, leading to frustration, strikes, and brain drain. These account for the short supply of health professionals as there are only about 35,000 doctors as against the need of 237,000, according to WHO figures.⁵ As such, the physician-to-patient ratio is 4 doctors to 10,000 patients, resulting in severe delays in care delivery as patients often wait hours to be attended to. Furthermore, health infrastructure and facilities suffer from neglect and lack of maintenance, resulting in obsolete and defective equipment, shortages of drugs, and poor patient care.⁶ Political and bureaucratic corruption also exacerbate the problems, undermining

¹ Good health can be taken to mean " a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity" as defined in the preamble of the WHO Constitution (1946).

² The WHO Constitution (1946) refers to "...the highest attainable standard of health as a fundamental right of every human being." Article 25 of the United Nations' 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights states that "Everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well-being of himself and of his family, including food, clothing, housing and medical care and necessary social services." Thus, there is generally recognised to be a legal obligation on states to ensure access to timely, acceptable, and affordable health care. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/human-rights-and-health> , retrieved 20 May 2023.

³ This can be seen in the targets of the UN Sustainable Development Goals 3.8: Achieve universal health coverage, including financial risk protection, access to quality essential health-care services and access to safe, effective, quality and affordable essential medicines and vaccines for all. <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/health/> , retrieved 20 May 2023.

⁴ Omoleke, I. I., & Taleat, B. A. 2017. Contemporary issues and challenges of the health sector in Nigeria. *Research Journal Health Sciences*, 5(4). <http://dx.doi.org/10.4314/rejhs.v5i4.5> retrieved 19 May 2023.

⁵ International Trade Administration, USA. Oct 2021. *Nigeria Commercial Country Guide: Healthcare*. Retrieved 22 May 2023 from <https://www.trade.gov/country-commercial-guides/nigeria-healthcare>

⁶ Ibid

policy implementation and monitoring.⁷ Additionally, high out-of-pocket payments burden households, with private expenditure on health comprising almost three-quarters of the total healthcare spending.⁸ These issues hinder the country's progress towards Universal Health Coverage, and account for why access to healthcare in the country has been ranked as one of the poorest globally – as Nigeria is positioned 187th of 191 countries.⁹

Telemedicine has been increasingly presented as the necessary intervention in the quest to improve access to healthcare in low-resource settings and countries like Nigeria.¹⁰ With a shortage of healthcare providers and infrastructure challenges, telemedicine offers a promising solution by leveraging information and communication technology (ICT) to bridge the healthcare gap. Through telemedicine, individuals in remote or underserved areas can connect with healthcare professionals, receive medical advice, and access specialized care without the need for physical travel.¹¹ This technology-enabled approach enhances the reach of healthcare services, particularly in regions where healthcare facilities are scarce or distant. By bringing healthcare expertise closer to the patients, telemedicine has the potential to significantly improve healthcare access, promote early intervention, and ultimately contribute to better health outcomes.¹²

Telemedicine has been described as a method of delivering healthcare services by healthcare professionals using information and communication technologies (ICT). It involves the exchange of accurate information to facilitate the diagnosis, prevention, and treatment of diseases and injuries, as well as providing education, training, research, and evaluation to enhance the quality of healthcare providers' services.¹³ In simpler terms, it refers to the "clinician's application of ICT to provide delivery of clinical services."¹⁴ As its name infers,

⁷ Ibid

⁸ Obokoh A. Jan 2019. *Examining Nigeria's healthcare challenges*.

<https://businessday.ng/why-nigeria-is-broke/article/examining-nigerias-healthcare-challenges/>

⁹ Nwachukwu, N. Aug 2022. *Nigeria: A health sector in crisis*. Retrieved 20 May, 2023 from <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/opinion/477854-nigeria-a-health-sector-in-crisis-by-emmanuel-nwachukwu.html>

¹⁰ Nittari G, Khuman R, Baldoni S, Pallotta G, Battineni G, Sirignano A, Amenta F, & Ricci G. 2020. Telemedicine Practice: Review of the Current Ethical and Legal Challenges. *Telemedicine and e-Health*; 26(12), 1427-1437. <https://doi.org/10.1089/tmj.2019.0158> retrieved 18 May 2023.

¹¹ Ibid

¹² Ibid

¹³ Anwar, A. 2016. The Principles Of Liability On Telemedicine Practices, 1(1), 013-037. <http://dx.doi.org/10.47268/palau.v1i1.2016.6> retrieved 18 May 2023.

¹⁴ Cypher, RL. 2020. Telehealth and Telemedicine During a Crisis: Tips to Reduce Liability Risk. *The Journal of Perinatal & Neonatal Nursing*, 34(3), 205-207, <https://doi.org/10.1097/JPN.0000000000000502> retrieved 18 May 2023.

telemedicine transcends geographical barriers, enabling these services to be implemented regardless of distance. Therefore, the American Telemedicine Association regards telemedicine to involve "the utilisation of electronic communications to transmit medical information between different locations, with the primary aim of enhancing a patient's clinical health status."¹⁵ This comprehensive definition thus outlines the primary characteristics of telemedicine as the exchange of health-related information, the electronic medium of communication, and the overarching objective of improving health, rather than delving into intricate technical specifics.¹⁶

Telemedicine offers numerous benefits in healthcare delivery. It enables critical healthcare to reach patients in remote locations, overcoming barriers such as inadequate medical professionals, transportation limitations, and financial constraints.¹⁷ By utilising telecommunication technologies, telemedicine improves access to healthcare services and reduces inefficiencies in the system. It allows for remote group collaboration among healthcare professionals, facilitating knowledge sharing and enhancing the quality of care.¹⁸ Patients benefit from direct access to doctors, even from a distance, enabling second opinions and consultations without the need for travel. This is particularly valuable in rural areas or developing countries with limited healthcare infrastructure. Telemedicine also plays a crucial role in preventive medicine and chronic disease management, offering convenient telemonitoring options and reducing hospitalisation costs.¹⁹ It improves patient safety by minimising errors related to illegible prescriptions and provides opportunities for patient empowerment and education.²⁰ Overall, telemedicine enhances health outcomes, patient satisfaction, and the efficiency of healthcare delivery, making it a valuable tool in modern healthcare practices.

¹⁵ Parimbelli, E., Bottalico, B., Losiouk, E., Tomasi, M., Santosuosso, A., Lanzola, G., Quaglini, S., & Bellazzi, R. 2018. Trusting telemedicine: A discussion on risks, safety, legal implications and liability of involved stakeholders. *International Journal of Medical Informatics*, 112, 90-98. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2018.01.012> retrieved 17 May 2023.

¹⁶ Ibid

¹⁷ Pourmand, A., Ghassemi, M., Sumon, K., Amini, S. B., Hood, C., & Sikka, N. 2021. Lack of telemedicine training in academic medicine: Are we preparing the next generation? *Telemedicine Journal and e-Health*, 27(1), 62-67. <https://doi.org/10.1089/tmj.2019.0287> retrieved 17 May 2023.

¹⁸ Ibid

¹⁹ Raposo V. L. 2016. Telemedicine: The legal framework (or the lack of it) in Europe. *GMS health technology assessment*, 12, Doc03. <https://doi.org/10.3205/hta000126> retrieved 17 May 2023.

²⁰ Ibid

As such, it is not surprising that the adoption of telemedicine is accelerating globally. In 2019, the global telemedicine market reached a size of \$41.63 billion, according to market reports.²¹ However, the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic had an extraordinary impact on the industry, leading to an unprecedented surge in demand worldwide. As a result, telemedicine experienced remarkable growth, expanding by an astounding 91.7% to reach \$79.79 billion in 2020. Furthermore, the market is anticipated to continue its upward trajectory, with a projected compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 25.8% between 2020 and 2027.²² In response to this, numerous telemedicine providers in Nigeria have sprung up, including Tremendoc, CribMD, Reliance HMO, DRO Health, Health Connect 24/7, Doctall, HealthTracka, amongst others. However, a recent study showed that the current telemedicine maturity level of tertiary health institutions funded by the federal government in the country is still lagging at the beginner stage, even though doctors are increasingly using ICT in various capacities.²³ Nevertheless, it is apparent that there is a significant and rapidly increasing importance of telemedicine as a vital component of healthcare delivery, driven by the need for remote healthcare solutions in the face of global health challenges.

1.2. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Despite the potential of telemedicine to revolutionise and transform the current state of healthcare delivery in Nigeria and advance access to quality healthcare for all its citizens, the emergence of telemedicine poses some ethical and legal challenges that concern not only the direct practice of medicine, but the pathways (that is, information and communication technology) through which care is delivered. This integrates traditional duties of medical professionals to patients with legal issues arising from the use of information technology and consumer protection, and as such not only transforms the possible liabilities that exist in healthcare, but also extends the stakeholders beyond healthcare professionals to the intermediary telemedicine providers.

²¹ Adegbite, T. 2021. *Telemedicine – a Panacea for Nigeria’s Healthcare Ills?* Retrieved 18 May 2023 from <https://www.thisdaylive.com/index.php/2021/03/21/telemedicine-a-panacea-for-nigeriashealthcare-ills/>

²² Ibid

²³ Olufunlayo, T. F., Ojo, O. O., Ozoh, O. B., Agabi, O. P., Opara, C. R., Taiwo, F. T., Fasanmade, O. A., & Okubadejo, N. U. 2023. Telemedicine ready or not? A cross-sectional assessment of telemedicine maturity of federally funded tertiary health institutions in Nigeria. *Digital health*, 9, e:20552076221150072. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20552076221150072> retrieved 18 May 2023.

As telemedicine relies on patient-provided data and involves remote communication, there are concerns about potential liabilities and risks that could compromise patient welfare. These issues revolve around the patient-physician relationship, medical malpractice, patient privacy, licensure, informed consent, quality of care, and regulatory challenges. One key question, for instance, is whether doctors should be held to the same standard of care in telemedicine as they would in traditional medicine, considering the departure from customary practices. Establishing the physician-patient relationship in telemedicine poses further challenges. Moreover, the use of digital health platforms for patient examinations instead of in-person visits raises concerns about potential diagnostic errors and inappropriate prescriptions, as the lack of physical examination may hinder accurate assessments. Additionally, third-party intermediaries play a role in telemedicine, and questions arise regarding their responsibilities in data breaches and fraudulent activities. Are they held liable, and do they owe a duty of care to patients? The increased autonomy granted to patients in telemedicine also affects traditional defenses like contributory negligence.

These complex and novel issues highlight the urgent need for well-defined legal guidelines and standards in the field of telemedicine. Addressing these challenges is crucial to ensure patient safety, protect healthcare providers, and establish a framework that promotes accountability, privacy, and quality of care in the evolving landscape of telemedicine.

1.3. AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

The aim of this long essay is to critically analyse and discuss liabilities that may arise in the practice of telemedicine in Nigeria, in order to foster a safer telemedicine ecosystem for patients, physicians, and providers and improve healthcare delivery in the country.

Therefore, the objectives of this essay are:

- a. To examine the legal framework governing telemedicine in Nigeria.
- b. To assess the scope of civil and criminal liability for medical practitioners and non-medical telemedicine providers involved in telemedicine.
- c. To explore the challenges and ethical considerations in telemedicine and their impact on liability.

1.4. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The research questions which are examined in this long essay are:

- a. What are the existing laws and regulations related to telemedicine in Nigeria?
- b. What are the potential civil and criminal liabilities that medical practitioners and non-medical telemedicine providers may face in the practice of telemedicine?
- c. What are the unique challenges and ethical dilemmas that arise in the practice of telemedicine and how do these challenges affect the potential liabilities of medical practitioners and non-medical telemedicine providers?

1.5. JUSTIFICATION OF THE STUDY

There is no gainsaying that Nigeria's healthcare sector is in dire need of urgent intervention, in order to safeguard the constitutionally established rights of its citizens to life and health.²⁴ Telemedicine, the practice of providing healthcare services remotely through telecommunication technologies, has emerged as a critical tool for revitalising healthcare in the country. However, despite its potential benefits, the legal framework governing the implementation of telemedicine in Nigeria remains fragmented and unclear. This lack of clear regulations leaves room for the harmful exploitation of patients, as there is an increased possibility of unscrupulous individuals or entities taking advantage of vulnerable patients through fraudulent practices or substandard care. In a rapidly evolving technology-based healthcare landscape, it becomes crucial to establish liability frameworks to protect patients and deter such exploitative behaviour.

Additionally, the lack of clarity in telemedicine regulations can lead to apprehension among clinicians in utilising these technologies. Healthcare providers may hesitate to embrace telemedicine fully due to concerns about potential legal repercussions or uncertainties surrounding their professional responsibilities and liabilities. This apprehension can hinder the widespread adoption of telemedicine, limiting its reach and impact on patient care.

²⁴ Section 33 (1) of the Nigerian Constitution 1999 (as amended) provides that persons living in Nigeria, shall have a right to life and no one shall be deprived intentionally of his life unless in execution of the sentence of a court of a criminal office of which he has been found guilty. Section 17(3)(c)-(d) provides "The State shall direct its policy towards ensuring that...the health, safety and welfare of all persons in employment are safeguarded and not endangered or abused; ...there are adequate medical and health facilities for all persons:"

Furthermore, the absence of a well-defined legal framework may result in restricted incentives for healthcare technology providers. Without clear guidelines, technology companies may face difficulties in developing and scaling telemedicine solutions, as they may be unsure about liability issues or regulatory compliance requirements. This ambiguity can deter investment and innovation in telemedicine technologies, hindering their potential to transform healthcare delivery. To address these challenges, it is therefore critical to explore liability in telemedicine within the current legal landscape.

Moreover, little academic attention has been given to legal perspectives on telemedicine in Nigeria, and much less to liability in telemedicine. This study seeks to address these gaps both from a practice viewpoint and an academic one.

1.6. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology utilised in this long essay is doctrinal as it would be analysing primary and secondary sources which are relevant to the study. These sources would be evaluated using a combination of analytical and content analysis methods.

Some of the primary sources which would be considered includes the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (CFRN) 1999 as amended, Medical and Dental Practitioners Act 1988, Child Rights Act 2003, National Health Act 2014, Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act 2018, Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, Nigerian Communications Act of 2003, Cybercrimes (Prevention, Prohibition, etc.) Act 2015, Code of Medical Ethics, Patients Bill of Rights, Nigerian Criminal Code, Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948, and the African Charter on Human and Peoples Rights 1981.

Secondary sources would include case reports, textbooks, articles, legal commentaries, and newspapers.

1.7. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This study will analyse existing laws, regulations, and guidelines related to telemedicine in Nigeria. It will explore relevant legislation at the federal and state levels, including healthcare, telecommunication, and data protection laws. Furthermore, it will examine the potential civil and criminal liabilities that medical professionals and telemedicine providers may face when practising telemedicine; or facilitating its practice, in Nigeria. It will analyse the legal

obligations, standards of care, and potential liability risks for healthcare professionals and providers involved in remote healthcare services. Also, the study will delve into the unique challenges and ethical considerations that arise in the telemedicine context. It will explore issues such as patient privacy, data protection, informed consent, remote prescribing, and the duty of care in remote healthcare delivery. The impact of these challenges on liability will further be considered.

1.8. CHAPTERISATION

Chapter 1 of the long essay addresses the background to the study, justification of the study, aims and objectives, research questions, justification of the study, research methodology, and scope and limitations of the study.

Chapter 2 will centre on the literature review and conceptual framework of the study. The literature review will examine academic articles and commentary on liability in telemedicine from various jurisdictions in the last 10 years (2013-2023). The conceptual framework would probe the nature of liability in law, healthcare and ICT; as well as telemedicine itself; and lay out the theoretical foundation of the study.

Chapter 3 will assess the legal framework for the practice of telemedicine in Nigeria, thoroughly appraising the extent to which it regulates issues such as patient privacy, data protection, informed consent, remote prescribing, and the duty of care in remote healthcare delivery in telemedicine and its lacunae.

Chapter 4 focuses on the potential civil and criminal liabilities that medical professionals and telemedicine providers may encounter while practising telemedicine or facilitating its practice within Nigeria. The chapter will examine the legal obligations, standards of care, and the risks of liability that healthcare professionals and providers may face when engaged in remote healthcare services. Additionally, it will explore the distinctive challenges and ethical considerations that arise in the context of telemedicine.

Chapter 5 will then synthesise the analysis presented so far in the paper into a conclusion. Evidence-based recommendations for stakeholders and future researchers will also be proffered.

CHAPTER TWO

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND LITERATURE REVIEW

This conceptual framework serves as a foundation for understanding the subject matter of liability and telemedicine which is being discussed in this long essay. Therefore, the concepts of liability in law, liability in healthcare generally and its intersection with information and communication technologies (ICT), and telemedicine will be critically examined and their interrelationship will be synthesised.

2.1. Liability in Law

The concept of liability is integral to the study and practice of law, as it is the bedrock on which legal actions are founded. By dictionary definitions, liability can be understood as holding someone "legally responsible for something",²⁵ "the quality or state of being liable",²⁶ or "the state of being bound or obliged in law or justice to do, pay, or make good something; legal responsibility."²⁷ The common denominator in these definitions is that liability refers to a legal obligation or duty as law establishes guidelines that outline the rights and responsibilities of individuals. In simpler terms, it dictates what actions are required or prohibited, as well as what individuals are entitled to receive. When these rules are violated, the party responsible for the violation is considered liable. As such, liability represents the legal obligation and responsibility one bears for their actions or omissions. When an individual or entity fails to fulfil this duty, they become vulnerable to a lawsuit seeking compensation for any resulting damages or a court order compelling them to fulfil their obligations, such as in cases of contract breaches or statutory violations.²⁸

²⁵ Cambridge University Press. (n.d.). Liability. In Cambridge English Dictionary. <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/liability> retrieved 26 May 2023

²⁶ Merriam-Webster. (n.d.). Liability. In Merriam-Webster.com dictionary. <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/liability> retrieved 26 May 2023

²⁷ Black's Law Dictionary, 2nd Ed., <https://thelawdictionary.org/liability/> retrieved 26 May 2023

²⁸ Aslam, M.A. 2021. Concept of Liability In The Light of Jurisprudence An Overview. *Legal Service India E-Journal*. <https://www.legalserviceindia.com/legal/article-1931-concept-of-liability-in-the-light-of-jurisprudence-an-overview.html> retrieved 26 May 2023.

On this basis, jurists like Salmond have defined liability in terms of the essential connection or relationship that exists between the wrongdoer and the legal remedy for the wrongdoing.²⁹ According to Markby, the term 'liability' refers to the state of a person who has an obligation to perform a duty, regardless of whether that obligation is primary, secondary, or related to punishment. On the other hand, Austin prefers to use the term 'imputability' instead of 'liability.' He suggests that certain abstentions, actions, or commissions, along with their resulting consequences, can be attributed to the individuals who have refrained from, omitted, or taken those actions.³⁰

Some have sought to distinguish between the concept of liability and responsibility. Professor Nicolae Popa argues that the concept of responsibility is traditionally associated with morality; liability is a social phenomenon that involves organised and institutionalised reactions to reprehensible acts.³¹ To him, it is essential to institutionalise and establish legal boundaries for these reactions, as liability and sanctions should not be driven by a desire for revenge. Instead, they serve as a means of legal recompense and the restoration of order, the repair of violated norms, the reintegration of damaged societal values, and the safeguarding of society.³² As a result, liability connotes that certain actions or inactions should also be addressed within the realm of law through the organised response by state entities (directly or indirectly) to unlawful acts. The purpose is twofold: first, to ensure the reinstatement of the rule of law, and second, to determine whether individuals who have committed illicit acts fulfil the conditions for legal liability.³³ Based on this assessment, appropriate sanctions can then be applied. By this analysis, one can presume that liability serves as the legal determinant of an action that is generally recognised by social mores as wrong. For instance, the tortious claim of negligence could be said to arise from the wrong of a party to fail to rise to the duty which they owe to another party. Nonetheless, as would be observed, liability may also arise in cases where there are legitimate competing interests.³⁴

²⁹ Ibid

³⁰ Ibid

³¹ Marin, A.-G. 2021. Legal Liability from a Threefold Perspective. General Aspects: Array. *Journal of Danubian Studies and Research*, 11(2). <https://dj.univ-danubius.ro/index.php/JDSR/article/view/1496> retrieved 26 May 2023.

³² Ibid

³³ Ibid

³⁴ Ibid

To succeed in a lawsuit, the party initiating the claim (plaintiff) must prove the defendant's legal liability, provided that the plaintiff's allegations are proven to be true. This requires presenting evidence establishing the existence of a duty to act, the failure to fulfil that duty, and a direct causal link (proximate cause) between the failure and any harm or injury suffered by the plaintiff.³⁵ Liability also extends to accusations of criminal acts, wherein the defendant can be held accountable for their actions that constitute a crime, thereby rendering them liable to conviction and punishment. From the foregoing, it is evident that legal liability can broadly be divided into two: criminal and civil liability.³⁶

According to Austin, a civil injury is an offence pursued at the discretion of the injured party or their representatives, while crimes are offences pursued by the sovereign or its subordinates. In addition, all absolute obligations are enforced criminally.³⁷ By this Austin focused on the nature of the infringed right which determined the party that instituted proceedings: the state in criminal cases; which must be pursued in the interest of justice, and the wronged party in civil cases who may or may not institute any proceedings. Salmond, however, argues that the distinction between criminal and civil wrongs lies not in the nature of the infringed right but in the nature of the applied remedy. Four commonly cited points of distinction are: 1) crime is a wrong against society, while civil wrongs are against private individuals; 2) punishment is the remedy for crime, while damages are the remedy for civil wrongs; 3) different proceedings occur in separate sets of courts for criminal and civil cases; 4) criminal liability is based on intention, whereas civil liability is based on the wrongful act.³⁸

To an extent, Salmond's points provide a generally true picture of civil and criminal liability in law. Criminal Responsibility is usually tied to wrongs that are done against public morality, as observed in the Wolfenden's Report in 1975, where Professor Hart defended the committee's recommendation that homosexuality be decriminalised based on Mill and Bentham's utilitarian position that laws should not regulate private affairs so long as it did not diminish the well-being of any other person.³⁹ This position finds its roots in the jurisprudential efforts to distinguish between law and morality and decipher where law should provide sanctions to

³⁵ Hochstatter, J. 2018. Legal Liability. In: Farazmand, A. (eds) *Global Encyclopedia of Public Administration, Public Policy, and Governance*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-20928-9_1071

³⁶ Ibid

³⁷ Aslam, op. cit

³⁸ Ibid

³⁹ Wigwe, C. 2011. *Jurisprudence and Legal Theory*. Read wide Publishers: Accra.

moral wrongs. As such, the second point of distinction that Salmond makes can now come into play as the aim of the law with regard to civil law is not necessarily to punish, but to restore the position of the wronged party before the commission of the wrongful act which is the essence of damages. In that regard, Rebecca Stone argues that civil liability should be seen not in the light of moral wrongs, but the moral permission of the defendant to sue.⁴⁰ She gives an illustrative example in that regard as:

"A very poor person, for example, may be held legally liable for breaching a one-sided contract with a very rich person. When such a contract reflects and reproduces existing injustice, it is hard to view the poor person's breach of such a contract as a genuine wrong against the rich person."⁴¹

As such, unlike criminal liability which has a very strong correlation with morality, civil liability does not.

On the third point of distinction, civil and criminal proceedings indeed have different rules and regulations for the conduct of their proceedings. In Nigeria, there are separate rules for Civil Procedure and Criminal Procedure: for instance, while civil actions are brought to the court through modes as originating summons, writ of summons, originating motions, and petition,⁴² criminal cases are instituted via charge, complaint, and information by the police, Attorney General, or any competent prosecuting authority.⁴³ Moreover, with regards to the right to fair hearing in criminal prosecution, the **1999 Constitution (as amended)** mandates that:

"No person shall be held to be guilty of a criminal offence on account of any act or omission that did not, at the time it took place, constitute such an offence, and no penalty shall be imposed for any criminal offence heavier than the penalty in force at the time the offence was committed".⁴⁴

This principle ensures that individuals cannot be found guilty of a criminal charge unless there was a law in place at the time they committed the offence that specifically defined and prescribed the committed act as a crime. Likewise, penalties imposed on individuals cannot

⁴⁰ Stone, R. (2021). Private liability without wrongdoing. *University of Toronto Law Journal*, e20210062. <https://doi.org/10.3138/utlj.2021-006>

⁴¹ Ibid, p.1

⁴² Aisekhaghe, D. 2021. A Note on the Nature of Civil Litigation in Nigeria. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3922608> retrieved 17 June 2023; Akeredolu, A., & Umeche, C. (2022, April 28). Nigeria: Litigation & Dispute Resolution Guide 2022. *Banwo & Ighodalo*. <https://www.mondaq.com/nigeria/arbitration--dispute-resolution/1187968/litigation--dispute-resolution-guide-2022> retrieved 17 June 2023.

⁴³ Administration of Criminal Justice Act 2015, s.109

⁴⁴ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended), s.36(8)

exceed those established by the law existing at the time the offence was committed. Therefore, an accused person can only face charges and penalties under a legal statute that was in effect at the time the alleged criminal offence took place.⁴⁵ By contrast, remedies for civil liability – including public law remedies or prerogative orders like mandates, certiorari, and prohibition, as well as private law remedies like injunctions and specific performance are often discretionary. In essence, they are determined by the court based on the merits of the case; they are not predetermined. However, the Nigerian legal system departs at this juncture from Salmond's proposition as it is essentially the same courts that try both criminal and civil cases, with the exception of the Federal High Court and National Industrial Court that mostly try civil cases.⁴⁶

In addition, civil liabilities encompass legal obligations that arise from private/tortious wrongs or breaches of contract, distinct from acts prohibited by legislation such as criminal acts or public wrongs. Under civil liability, individuals possess the right to seek remedies or compensation from others. In civil cases, the burden of proof rests on establishing the likelihood of the claim being true, commonly known as "*the balance of probability*."⁴⁷ This standard requires demonstrating that it is more probable than not that the claim is valid. In Nigeria, as in most common law jurisdictions, criminal liability is based on proving fault attributed to the suspect "*beyond reasonable doubt*".⁴⁸ For this to apply, the suspect must have the capacity to comprehend their actions and have control over their actions. As such, children under seven or twelve years old are generally not held criminally responsible, and individuals with mental diseases or defects affecting their capacity are also exempt.⁴⁹

On the fourth point of distinction made by Salmond, however, it is significantly flawed. That is because for many offences, both the *mens rea* (intention) and *actus reus* (physical act) must be present for a suspect to be liable.⁵⁰ The same is also true of civil cases where intention is

⁴⁵ As seen generally in *Ogbomor v. The State* (1985) 1 NWLR (Pt. 2) 233; *Godwin Ikpa v. The State* (1981) 9 SC 7

⁴⁶ Established as superior courts of record in Nigeria's Constitution (CFRN 1999, s.6; see also s.251(1))

⁴⁷ Evidence Act 2011, s.134; also seen in *Iseogbekun v Adelokun*(2013) 2 NWLR P.141(SC); *Amodu v Amodu*(1990) 5 NWLR(Pt.150); *Akande v Adisa*(2012) 15 NWLR(Pt. 1324) P. 538

⁴⁸ Evidence Act, s.135(1); *Otukpo v John*(2012) 7 NWLR. (Pt.1299) P.357; *Garba V. State* [2011] ALL FWLR (Part 584) 14 (CA)

⁴⁹ Nkolo, C. E. 2022. Criminal Liability under the Nigerian Criminal Jurisprudence. *International Journal of Comparative Law and Legal Philosophy*, 4(3), 72.

⁵⁰ Oduniyi, O. O. 2022. Criminal Liability Under the Nigerian Law: An Examination of the Liability of Non-Legal Entities. *Canadian Social Science*, 18(1), 36-41. doi:10.3968/12439

often constructed based on the actions of the party.⁵¹ Moreover, there are instances where an act can be both a crime and an offence, such as with assault and fraudulent misrepresentation.⁵² Liability can further be divided into two categories: remedial liability and penal liability.⁵³ Remedial liability occurs when a legal proceeding results in the defendant being ordered to compensate the affected party, settle a debt, or fulfil a specific obligation. Penal liability, on the other hand, involves the imposition of punishment, such as fines or imprisonment, following a successful legal proceeding. While civil liability is generally considered remedial and criminal liability is typically penal, there can be exceptions, as civil liability may also have penal aspects.⁵⁴

Remedial liability is based on the principle of "*ubi jus ibi remedium*" (where there is a right, there must be a remedy). When the law establishes a duty, corresponding remedies are provided to address breaches, which are enforced by the legal system.⁵⁵ On the other hand, penal liability follows the condition of "*actus non facit reum, nisi mens sit rea*" (the act alone does not constitute guilt unless there is a guilty mind). It requires two elements: the act itself and a guilty mind or mens rea. The act is understood as a movement of the will, either in the form of bodily movement caused by volition or as any event subject to human will, encompassing not only physical actions but also other events within human control. An act comprises its origin (mental or bodily activity or passivity of the doer), circumstances, and consequences.⁵⁶

Nonetheless, it is not at all times that liability is imposed on a person as a result of his own fault (or at least, his own intention). It is in such instances that the no-fault liabilities, such as absolute liability, vicarious liability, and strict liability, can arise. Absolute liability offences or torts only necessitate the prosecution or plaintiff to establish the occurrence of an unlawful act or omission. There is no requirement for the prosecution to prove any form of intent on the part of the defendant. In such cases, the accused is not permitted to rely on defences like due diligence, necessity, or accident.⁵⁷ Strict liability refers to the legal responsibility for damages

⁵¹ As seen in *Edgington v. Fitzmaurice* (1885) 29 Ch D 459

⁵² Op cit, n.24

⁵³ Op cit, n.4

⁵⁴ For instance, penal damages are granted in civil cases to act as a punitive and cautionary measure.

⁵⁵ Khan, M. A., Kundi, K., & Saqib, L. 2019. Liability for Defective Pharmaceutical Products in Pakistani Law. *Pakistan Vision*, 20(2), pp 58-80.

⁵⁶ Aslam, Op Cit.

⁵⁷ Criminal Law Firm of Weisberg Law. (n.d.). Quasi-Criminal Prosecutions: What Is the Difference Between Absolute Liability, Strict Liability, and Full Mens Rea? *CFLaw* <https://cflaw.ca/practice-area/toronto-quasi->

or injuries, even in the absence of fault or negligence on the part of the liable person.⁵⁸ Although they are often used interchangeably, the term "strict liability" is commonly used when liability cannot be defended on the basis of impracticability or lack of reasonable feasibility to avoid the risk.⁵⁹ On the other hand, "absolute liability" is reserved for a smaller set of obligations that impose liability for something that the defendant could not have prevented even with the utmost care and diligence.⁶⁰ In simpler terms, while defences for strict liability could include exercising reasonable care, no such defence exists for absolute liability. Vicarious liability on the other hand is a species of strict liability. It is not a fault based tort or a tort in its own right but a rule of responsibility which renders the defendant liable for the wrongful act or omission committed by another, usually his employee/servant or agent.⁶¹

Sometimes, there are multiple parties who are liable to some degree when a wrong occurs. Joint and several liability is a legal principle that determines how damages are allocated when multiple individuals are responsible for wrongdoing. In cases where joint and several liability applies, any one of the wrongdoers can be held accountable for the entire amount of the damages if the other wrongdoers are not part of the lawsuit (perhaps because they have disappeared and cannot be located) or are unable to pay the judgement. Under several liability, the default assumption is that each wrongdoer is liable for an equal portion of the damages, unless the court decides to distribute the responsibility based on another criterion such as the degree of fault. The inability to pay or the absence of some of the wrongdoers does not change the court's allocation of liability for damages under several liability.⁶² Joint and several liability applies to cases involving conspiracy, concert of action, and concurrent wrongdoers. In criminal cases, conspiracy may give rise to joint or several liability. Conspiracy refers to an offence committed by two or more individuals in accordance with an agreement to harm the

[criminal-prosecutions-lawyer/quasi-criminal-prosecutions-what-is-the-difference-between-absolute-liability-strict-liability-and-full-mens-rea](#) retrieved 18 June 2023

⁵⁸ Global Legal Group. (n.d.). Strict Liability in Tort. *Law Global Hub*. <https://www.lawglobalhub.com/strict-liability/> retrieved 18 June 2023

⁵⁹ Within tort law, strict liability has traditionally been applied in cases involving damages caused by animals. Since animals lack consciousness and possess the potential to cause harm if not properly controlled, those who keep animals are obligated to restrain them. As a general rule, the keepers of animals are held liable for damages resulting from their animals trespassing onto others' property. Also, this is seen in rule in *Rylands v Fletcher*

⁶⁰ Halsbury's Laws Of England / Tort (Volume 97A (2021)) / 2. General Tortious Liabilities / (5) Strict and Absolute Liability / 122. Strict and absolute liability in general.

<https://www.lexisnexis.co.uk/legal/commentary/halsburys-laws-of-england/tort/strict-absolute-liability-in-general-01> retrieved 11 June 2023

⁶¹ <https://www.learnnigerianlaw.com/learn/law-of-torts/vicarious-liability>

⁶² Hylton, K. (2016). Joint and Several Liability, and Vicarious Liability. In *Tort Law: A Modern Perspective* (pp. 180-194). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

plaintiff. If two offenders join forces to physically assault the plaintiff, the court will apply the principle of joint and several liability in the plaintiff's lawsuit for battery against the offenders.⁶³ Finally, liability can also be broadly classified as primary and secondary with regards to the degree in which liability is inputed. Primary liability refers to the direct responsibility of a party for an obligation. In contrast, secondary liability refers to the obligation that falls on another party if the directly responsible party fails to fulfil the obligation.⁶⁴

The diagram below summarises the framework of liability in telemedicine, showing their interrelationships.

Figure 2.1: Legal Liability Framework. Source: Author (2023)

⁶³ Ibid

⁶⁴ Cornell Law School Legal Information Institute. (n.d.). Primary liability. https://www.law.cornell.edu/wex/primary_liability#:~:text=Primary%20liability%20refers%20to%20an,fauls%20to%20satisfy%20the%20obligation. retrieved 17 June 2023

2.2. Liability in Healthcare

References to liability in healthcare or medical practice are usually tortious in nature, although criminal liability may sometimes ensue. Typical claims in the realm of medicine and health include physician liability (medical malpractice and negligence), corporate liability, and products liability.

2.2.1. Physician liability: Malpractice and Negligence

Physician liability arises when the actions or omissions of a doctor has a direct causal link to a patient's harm.⁶⁵ The actions or omissions of the healthcare provider must be considered wrongful, meaning they go against established medical standards or legal provisions. Generally, physician liability is fault-based; although there are circumstances where strict liability rules may be applicable.⁶⁶ According to Nikšić, physician liability has been recognised in law since the earliest civilisations as embodied in the Code of Hammurabi (ca. 2000 B.C.) and law of ancient China (tenth century B.C.).⁶⁷ Furthermore, he situated medical liability within private law (as a civil liability) as its key elements do not only include wrongful acts or omissions by medical professionals, but also damage sustained by patients during medical diagnostic and treatment, or as a consequence of medical advice.⁶⁸

Medical malpractices occur within the context of wrongful actions where a medical practitioner utilises an inappropriate method of care or improperly executes an acceptable method of care (that is, a medical error), or takes any other actions that contravenes the acceptable code of conduct for the profession.⁶⁹ Liability for medical malpractice is generally governed by a negligence framework, which is the primary legal mechanism used to safeguard the quality of healthcare.⁷⁰ Under this framework, physicians are obligated to compensate patients for injuries caused by their own actions. Negligence as a tort occurs as a result of failure to exercise the

⁶⁵ Nikšić, S. 2013. Understanding Medical Liability. In: Beran, R. (eds) *Legal and Forensic Medicine*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-32338-6_53

⁶⁶ Ibid

⁶⁷ Ibid, p.692

⁶⁸ Ibid, p.693

⁶⁹ Adejumo, O. A., & Adejumo, O. A. 2020. Legal perspectives on liability for medical negligence and malpractices in Nigeria. *The Pan African medical journal*, 35, 44. <https://doi.org/10.11604/pamj.2020.35.44.16651>

⁷⁰ Resolution Law Firm. (2020, November 11). Liability and Proof of Medical Negligence in Nigeria. *Mondaq*. Retrieved from <https://www.mondaq.com/nigeria/professional-negligence/1004164/liability-and-proof-of-medical-negligence-in-nigeria#:~:text=In%20circumstances%20where%20the%20medical,procedure%20provided%20by%20the%20Act.>

standard of care that a reasonably prudent person would have exercised in a similar situation.⁷¹ Within the healthcare or medical context, it results when there is a failure to fulfill a legal obligation to care for one's patients, leading to harm or damages that were not intended by the doctor but suffered by the patient. Based on established rules of negligence embodied in the locus classicus of *Donoghue v. Stevenson*⁷², the essential components of negligence as a tort are as follows:

- (a) The existence of a legal duty on the part of individual A towards person B, requiring A to exercise care in their actions within the scope of that duty.
- (b) A breach of that duty by A, indicating a failure to meet the reasonable or expected standard of care.
- (c) As a result of the breach, B suffers consequential damages, which can include physical harm, financial loss, or emotional distress.⁷³

As such, negligence, as defined by the law, refers to conduct that falls below the established standard for protecting others from unreasonable harm.⁷⁴ In legal proceedings, a physician's actions are assessed not against those of an average person but rather against those of a reasonable physician who possesses the same knowledge, skills, and expertise, facing similar circumstances. However, courts do not claim to possess the necessary medical knowledge to make judgments on sound medical practices. Therefore, expert testimony from qualified physicians is required to determine the standard of care or what is considered reasonable to expect from a professional in a specific treatment situation, taking into account the prevailing medical knowledge at that time.⁷⁵

Nonetheless, there is a demarcation between medical negligence and medical errors, such that not all errors qualify as negligence. As observed by Lord Denning in his book, "*The Discipline of Law*", and subsequently affirmed by the Supreme Court in *Ojo V. Gharoro & Ors*⁷⁶, not all

⁷¹Garner; Black Law's Dictionary, p.1056; retrieved from <https://trustedadvisorslaw.com/medical-negligence-in-nigeria-the-legal-remedies/>

⁷² [1932] AC 562. Also seen in *Blyth v. Birmingham Waterworks* (1856) 11 Ex Ch 781; *Hazel v. British Transport Commission* [1958] 1 WLR 169; *First Bank Nigeria Plc. V. Banjo* (2015) 5 NWLR (Pt.1452) 253 C.A.

⁷³ Nikšić, op cit.

⁷⁴ Ibid, n.43

⁷⁵ Ibid; Ogundare, Bisola. 2019. Medical Negligence in Nigeria: A Quick Guide on Liabilities and Remedies. SSRN e-Library. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3476524>

⁷⁶ [2006] 10 (PT 98) SC 173

instances of medical error should give rise to a claim of negligence; but rather where even within his professional circle the action would be regarded as reprehensible. In his words:

"...You must not therefore, find him negligent simply because something happens to go wrong.... you should only find him guilty of negligence when he falls short of the standard of a reasonably skillful medical man, in short, when he is deserving of censure".⁷⁷

As such, establishing medical negligence is often difficult except where the professional regulatory body has successfully conducted disciplinary actions. In Nigeria, the Medical and Dental Council of Nigeria and its establishment Act are the institutional and legal framework governing medical malpractice in the country.⁷⁸ Given this challenge, Adejumo and Adejumo identified three additional approaches through which malpractice could arise asides from negligence: contractual, fiduciary basis, and rights-based approach.⁷⁹ In such cases, alternative legal options are available for patients who have suffered harm without establishing negligence; and they can also lead to disciplinary actions against erring physicians based on breaches of medical ethics.⁸⁰

With regards to contract, in doctor-patient relationships, there is an implied term that the doctor will exercise reasonable skill and care in treatment. Patients can claim damages for breach of the implied or express terms of the contract and any additional costs incurred due to the breach. Unlike negligence cases, the patient only needs to prove the existence of a doctor-patient relationship, breach of the contract's terms, and injury arising from or during treatment. However, as observed by Okorie,⁸¹ doctors hardly ever make guarantees of success in treatments, and the court would not ordinarily imply any such term to that effect.⁸² Thus its application in practice is limited. Related to this is where the fiduciary duty to protect the patients' interest may be imposed on the medical doctor in favour of the patient as was held in

⁷⁷ Ibid

⁷⁸ Medical and Dental Practitioners Act 1988, s.15

⁷⁹ Adejumo and Adejumo, op cit.

⁸⁰ Medical and Dental Practitioners Act 1988, s.16(2)

⁸¹ Okojie Eric, 'Professional Medical Negligence in Nigeria', <http://www.nigerianlawguru.com/articles/torts/PROFESSIONAL%20MEDICAL%20NEGLIGENCE%20IN%20NIGERIA.pdf> retrieved 19 June 2023.

⁸² As seen in *Scott v St Katherine Dock Co* (1865) 159 ER 665.

the Canadian case, *Norbery V. Wynrib*.⁸³ That is because, as the Court of Appeal per Aderemi JCA, observed in *Abatan v. Awudu*⁸⁴;

"the relationship between a Doctor and his patient is one of trust and confidence; a relationship where one has the power and the duty to treat and restore the other to mental and physical well-being."

Liability for medical errors can also be viewed as a breach of a patient's fundamental human rights; usually expressed in terms of the right to health, privacy, and even dignity.⁸⁵ In essence, patients' rights and autonomy must be respected during their treatment. As such, patients have the right to make decisions about their medical care, and failure to provide information on treatment options can be considered a breach of the right to health. The right to privacy includes the right to refuse treatment, even if others may view it as unwise. The existence of suitable systems and standards to protect patients will be relevant in determining liability.⁸⁶

It must be noted that given the nature of medical practice, what will constitute appropriate standards of care evolve over time as medical knowledge and technology advance. Consequently, new technological developments such as telemedicine-related may introduce uncertainties for physicians regarding the current standard of care. Moreover, there are instances where malicious intent is presumed in negligence, such as gross negligence, that may give rise to criminal liability.⁸⁷

2.2.2. Corporate Liability

In jurisprudence and corporate law, the concept of personhood extends beyond human beings to corporate personalities. As such, a group of persons operating as a body can be granted a legal personality separate from the individuals forming the group.⁸⁸ This principle, traceable to the concepts of corporate sole and partnerships, was officially established in the English case

⁸³ [1992] 2 SCR 226

⁸⁴ [2014] 17 N.W.L.R. (Pt. 430)

⁸⁵ CFRN, s.17

⁸⁶ Adejumo & Adejumo, *ibid* n.43

⁸⁷ In *R v Akerele*, where a medical practitioner overdosed on drugs on a number of children which led to their death, he was held to have been criminally negligent and accordingly convicted for manslaughter. Also see **Criminal Code**, C38: Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004; s.303; 343(1)(e); doctor's providing assistance in abortion or euthanasia are also criminally liable (s.228,s.320).

⁸⁸ Akinola, B. (2021). A critical appraisal of the doctrine of corporate personality under the Nigerian company law. NLI Working Paper Series, 002A. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/359510129_A_CRITICAL_APPRAISAL_OF_THE_DOCTRINE_OF_CORPORATE_PERSONALITY_UNDER_THE_NIGERIAN_COMPANY_LAW

of *Salomon v. Salomon*⁸⁹. Incidental to this corporate personality is that incorporated bodies can sue and be sued; thus, they can be liable for wrongful acts in torts, contract, and in some instances, criminal acts.⁹⁰ This position has been affirmed in a plethora of cases including *Lee v Lee's Air Farming Ltd*⁹¹ and *DHN Food Distributors Ltd v Tower Hamlets*.⁹² To explain the concept of corporate liability, jurists have propounded a number of theories including the fictive theory, realist theory, symbolist, concessionary, amongst others.⁹³

In medical and health care, institutional bodies like hospitals are prime holders of corporate personality. The historical role of hospitals was primarily to provide basic necessities, such as food and lodging, to patients through philanthropic donations. As a result, hospitals enjoyed charitable immunity, as imputing them with liability such as compensation was seen as diminishing their assets and hindering their ability to help others.⁹⁴ Nowadays, hospitals offer a wide range of comprehensive healthcare services, including specialised diagnostics and therapies, pre- and postoperative care, and even teleconsultation, telemonitoring, and other applications of telemedicine.⁹⁵ Beyond this, hospitals have adopted modern management practices, organising themselves as business entities with risk management strategies in place to cover economic costs of possible liabilities; eliminating the argument for immunity based on the former charitable structure of their operations. This shift towards providing total and comprehensive services has thus transformed hospitals into institutions that compete and strive for business growth and expansion.⁹⁶

This has also transformed the incidence of corporate liability in healthcare. Previously, hospitals primarily faced medical malpractice lawsuits where they were named as defendants based on *respondeat superior*, specifically in cases of (1) employment/actual agency, (2)

⁸⁹ [1897] AC 22

⁹⁰ *Government of Midwestern State v Mid Motors Nig. Co. Ltd* (1977) 10 S. C. 43

⁹¹ [1960] UKPC 33

⁹² [1976] 1 WLR 852

⁹³ Wigwe, op cit.

⁹⁴ Setiawati, S. and Daulat, P. A. 2023. Hospital Liability as a Corporation in Medical Malpractice. In Kusumaningrum, A. E., et al. (Eds.), ICLEH 2022, ASSEHR 723 (pp. 82–91). Atlantis Press. https://doi.org/10.2991/978-2-38476-024-4_11

⁹⁵ Nittari G, Khuman R, Baldoni S, Pallotta G, Battineni G, Sirignano A, Amenta F, Ricci G. 2020. Telemedicine Practice: Review of the Current Ethical and Legal Challenges. *Telemedicine and e-Health*; 26(12), 1427-1437. <https://doi.org/10.1089/tmj.2019.0158>

⁹⁶ Amarante, E. L. (2016, February 1). Corporate Liability for Hospitals. For the Defense, (February 2016 Issue). Retrieved from <https://www.wiggin.com/publication/corporate-liability-for-hospitals/>

apparent agency/ostensible agency, or (3) non-delegable duty.⁹⁷ These claims of vicarious liability typically do not allege that the hospital, as an institution, directly contributed to the plaintiff's alleged injuries. Rather, they seek to hold the hospital accountable solely based on the actions of individual healthcare providers.⁹⁸

The legal doctrine of *respondeat superior* imposes vicarious liability on employers for the negligent actions of their employees when performed within the scope of their employment.⁹⁹ This doctrine holds employers accountable for the negligent actions of their employees if those actions occurred within the scope of their employment. This means that hospitals, for instance, can be held responsible for the malpractice committed by their employees, including physicians. This is particularly important in medical malpractice cases as it ensures that there is an economically capable party to provide adequate compensation to an injured patient.¹⁰⁰ In *Ibokwe V UCH Board Of Management*, this principle was upheld when Irwin J held that; “*It is now seemed too well settled that a hospital authority is responsible for the acts or omission of the whole of its staffs, whether they were physicians, doctors, nurses or other employees.*”¹⁰¹ This position had also been established in *Cassidy v Ministry of Health*.¹⁰²

However, there are instances where healthcare providers, such as physicians, are considered independent contractors rather than hospital employees. In such cases, the doctrine of *respondeat superior* does not apply, meaning that the hospital cannot be held responsible for the independent contractor's negligence. As Imuekemhe observed,¹⁰³ Nigerian courts often take this position and are less willing to hold hospitals vicariously liable as seen in the case of *University of Ilorin Teaching Hospital v. Mrs. Theresa Akilo*,¹⁰⁴ where the Court of Appeal absolved the appellant hospital on the rationale that the medical doctors, although acting as servants of the hospital, were also considered independent contractors. This classification was

⁹⁷ Ibid, n.69

⁹⁸ Ibid, n.69

⁹⁹ Ibid, n.71

¹⁰⁰ Ibid

¹⁰¹ [1961] WNLR 173

¹⁰² [1951] 2 KB 343

¹⁰³ Imuekemhe, E. J. 2018. An Examination of the Disposition of the Law to Cases of Medical Negligence in Nigeria. Edo State University Law Journal, 1. Retrieved from Edo University Open Educational Resources Repository:

https://www.edouniversity.edu.ng/oorrepository/articles/an_examination_of_the_disposition_of_the_law_to_cases_of_medical_negligence_in_nigeria.pdf

¹⁰⁴ [1951] 1 All ER 573

made because the doctors were not under the direct control or management of the appellant while performing their duties as medical professionals.

In contemporary times, as hospitals are increasingly becoming proper corporate bodies with standard business management and embodying for-profit elements including competition, cost management, and expansion; hospitals are increasingly confronted with claims of direct liability in addition to defending vicarious liability claims as mentioned earlier. Healthcare institutions are thus increasingly seen as companies and healthcare providers and not charity organisations, giving rise to a need for the protection of patient interests so that it would not be sacrificed on the altar of profit-making. As such, courts in foreign jurisdictions such as the United States have established a broad concept of "corporate negligence," wherein hospitals are held to have direct duties towards their patients.¹⁰⁵ Consequently, hospitals can be held liable for breaching these duties, even in cases where the individual medical professional was not negligent. The responsibilities of a hospital encompass various aspects, including but not limited to hiring, staffing, credentialing, maintaining safe equipment and facilities, as well as developing and enforcing policies.¹⁰⁶

2.2.3. Product Liability

Product liability as a concept in law refers to the legal responsibility of a manufacturer or seller for any harm or injuries suffered by a buyer or user due to a defective product.¹⁰⁷ This liability can extend to other parties involved in the distribution chain, such as sellers, importers, distributors, authorised dealers, agents, wholesalers, retailers, and suppliers who can be held legally accountable for any defects, faults, or negligence related to the product; to the end of consumer protection and economic efficiency.¹⁰⁸ While some legal commentators have argued against a separate doctrine of product liability as it could dissuade production and innovation, in addition to adding to the costs of litigation, there are several social advantages to product

¹⁰⁵ Shensky, E. S. (2015, December 10). Corporate Negligence in Medical Malpractice. *The National Law Review*. <https://www.natlawreview.com/article/corporate-negligence-medical-malpractice> retrieved 17 June 2023.

¹⁰⁶ Ibid

¹⁰⁷ Ukwueze, F.O., & Okiche, E.L. (2021) Product liability in Nigeria: a paradigm shift from fault-based to strict liability regime, *Commonwealth Law Bulletin*, 47(3) pp.395-416, <https://doi.org/10.1080/03050718.2020.1788403>

¹⁰⁸ Khan, M. A., Kundi, K., & Saqib, L. 2019. Liability for Defective Pharmaceutical Products in Pakistani Law. *Pakistan Vision*, 20(2), pp.58-80; Gregory, Keating. 2017. Product Liability As Enterprise Liability. *Journal of Tort Law*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.10.1515/jtl-2017-0009>

liability.¹⁰⁹ As Ukwueze and Okiche analysed, the concept of product liability encourages the production of safer products, ensures that prices reflect their true social costs, and compensates injured victims.¹¹⁰ The concept of product liability was established in the English case of *Donoghue v. Stevenson*.¹¹¹

In the healthcare context, product liability promotes product standards of prescription drugs and medical devices and provides a means for seeking compensation, especially where health insurance coverage is limited.¹¹² The rationale for attributing liability to manufacturers which can only be distributed with a healthcare provider's prescription, is because the healthcare providers themselves are intermediary consumers who would not be ordinarily expected to believe that a drug or medical device is defective or has other risks associated with the product if there were no warnings or instructions to that effect.¹¹³ As such, individuals who are harmed by products that are considered "not reasonably safe" due to defects in design, manufacture, or warning are entitled to seek compensation. A product is deemed to have a defective design if the potential risks of harm outweigh its expected therapeutic benefits to the extent that reasonable healthcare providers would not prescribe it to any group of patients.¹¹⁴

Generally, there are three primary legal principles under which a manufacturer or producer of a defective product may be held liable for damages resulting from its use. These principles are Warranty in contract, Negligence in torts, and Strict liability.¹¹⁵ Therefore, there are two main types of product liability regimes: fault-based and strict. Fault-based regimes hold manufacturers or suppliers liable for wrongful conduct, while strict product liability imposes liability regardless of fault, prioritizing public policy and accident prevention. Strict product liability also encourages a safety-conscious mindset among product producers.¹¹⁶ Initially,

¹⁰⁹ Ibid, n.81

¹¹⁰ Ibid, n.81

¹¹¹ [1932] AC 562. Also established in English cases as *Grant v. Australian Knitting Mills Ltd.* [1936] A.C. 85; *Stennett v. Hancock and Peters*, [1939] 2 All E.R. 578; and raised in a number of Nigerian cases including *Nigerian Bottling Co. (Nig.) Ltd. v. Ngonadi*[1985] 1 NWLR (Pt.4) 739; *Ebelemu v. Guinness (Nig.) Ltd* (1993); *Boardman v. Guinness (Nig.) Ltd.* (1980) NCLR 109; *Soremi v. Nigerian Bottling Co. Ltd.* 1977) 12 CCHCJ 2735

¹¹² Ibid, n.81

¹¹³ Ibid, n.82

¹¹⁴ Ateriya, N., Saraf, A., Meshram, V. P., & Setia, P. 2018. Telemedicine and virtual consultation: The Indian perspective. *National Medical Journal of India*, 31, 215–218.

¹¹⁵ Ibid, n.84

¹¹⁶ Akinrinmade, G. 2016. The jurisprudence of product liability in Nigeria: a need to complement the existing fault theory. *Journal of Sustainable Development Law and Policy*, 7(2), 188. DOI: 10.4314/jsdlp.v7i2.9

Nigeria followed the path of its colonial masters with regards to product liability by applying a fault-based regime in which the consumer had a higher burden of proof not only to establish the presence of a defect in the product, but also that the defect had caused or resulted in the injury for which compensation was being sought, as well as a duty of care on the part of the defendant in a claim of negligence.¹¹⁷ Moreover, the courts did not apply the doctrine of *res ipsa loquitur*, which establishes a presumption of negligence against a defendant based on the circumstances, as they did in general negligence cases.¹¹⁸ This was the standard in *Nigerian Bottling Co v Ngonadi*¹¹⁹ and *Ocenosor v Niger Biscuit*.¹²⁰ In another case, *Nigerian Bottling Company Plc v Olanrewaju*,¹²¹ the Court of Appeal established that a higher standard of proof is required in cases involving food poisoning as the claimant must establish a direct connection between the consumed food or drink and the subsequent illness suffered.¹²²

Also, while injured consumers could file a breach of contract claim if they were the direct purchaser of the product, the privity rule in contract law presented a challenge for non-contracting consumers, as they were unable to sue for product defects even if the supplier breached the contract for product supply.¹²³ These presented a significant bottleneck in the protection of consumers. Although there was a statutory enactment supposedly regulating consumer protection, the **Consumer Protection Council Act of 1992** did not effectively alleviate the evidential burden of proof on claimants in product liability cases based on negligence.¹²⁴ The Act's unclear provisions allowed the courts to continue relying on contract and negligence principles rather than shifting the burden of proof. However, as Akinrinmade observed, this led to more injustice and did not take into cognizance the fact that the English jurisdiction which the liability regime was patterned after provided better protection for consumers.¹²⁵

¹¹⁷ Afolayan, M. S., & Arogundade, E. A. 2021. Analysis of the Legal Obligation of Suppliers and Manufacturers to Consumers in Nigeria and the United Kingdom. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)*, V(XI), 1-10.

¹¹⁸ *Ibid*, n.90

¹¹⁹ (1985) LLJR-SC

¹²⁰ (1973) 7 CCHCJ 71

¹²¹ (2006)LCN/2059(CA)

¹²² Also seen in *Okonkwo v. Guinness (Nig) Ltd and Anor* (1980) IP. L.R 581; *Boardman v. Guinness (Nig.) Ltd* 207 (1980) NCLR 109

¹²³ Sodipo, B. A. 2019. Product Liability: Nigeria. In *Product Liability 2019* (pp. 767-784), Lexology:London. <http://www.ajumogobiaokeke.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/edition-767-chapter-18-190809130237968-product-liability-2019-nigeria.pdf> retrieved 17 June 2023

¹²⁴ *Ibid*, n.90

¹²⁵ *Ibid*, n.90

Fortunately, with the introduction of the **Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act, 2018 (FCCPA)** there is now an imposition of liabilities on manufacturers, who supply defective or hazardous products or goods to consumers. In this regard, where a manufacturer of medicines or medical devices produces defective or hazardous products which are used by the consumer, such manufacturer may become liable under the FCCPA.¹²⁶ Under Nigeria's new strict liability regime, manufacturers, suppliers, or vendors can be held liable if it can be proven that the purchased product was defective and caused harm or financial loss to the consumer.¹²⁷ Contractual agreements cannot restrict or exclude this liability, and it applies regardless of whether the consumer directly purchased the goods from the manufacturer or entered into a contract with them. Manufacturers can also be held liable if they provide misleading information that leads to financial loss or health risks for consumers and are not allowed to limit or exclude any form of liability they may be subject to.¹²⁸

In the context of telemedicine, product liability primarily applies to medical devices which are used to provide diagnostic, monitoring, and treatment services over a distance.¹²⁹ In the United States, commentators have noted that over the years, individual plaintiffs who have suffered harm from medical devices have successfully pursued product liability actions against the manufacturers.¹³⁰ Cases such as *Dyer v. Danek Medical, Inc.*¹³¹ and *Miller v. Bristol-Myers Squibb Co.*,¹³² exemplify lawsuits filed against manufacturers for injuries caused by defective medical devices, including a spinal fusion fixation device and breast implants, respectively. The questions courts are now faced with, nevertheless, is whether telemedicine software or even say a mobile phone through which consultations are made can be classified as medical devices for which product liability may be sought.

¹²⁶ Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act, 2018 (FCCPA), s.134-140

¹²⁷ Pharma Boardroom. 2021. Product Liability in Nigeria" <https://pharmaboardroom.com/legal-articles/product-liability-nigeria/> retrieve 18 June 2023.

¹²⁸ Ibid

¹²⁹ Ibid, n.90

¹³⁰ Wiley, L., & Terry, N. (2016). Liability for Mobile Health and Wearable Technologies. *Annals of Health Law*, 25, 63. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781839104909.00015>

¹³¹ 115 F. Supp. 2d 732 (N.D.Tex. 2000)

¹³² 121 F. Supp. 2d 831 (D.Md. 2000)

2.3. Liability in Information and Communication Technologies (ICT)

Given that telemedicine is a blend of telecommunications or ICT and health, ICT related liabilities are also relevant in the discourse. While ICT liability mostly relates to contractual obligations and product liability earlier discussed, there are still certain incidents necessary to highlight with regards to cyberspace, particularly with regards to data protection and cyber torts.¹³³ While these concepts would be discussed extensively later in this work, there is a need to lay foundation in relation to their meanings.

Data protection liability is founded on the fundamental human right to privacy, particularly with regard to *informational privacy*, which is distinct from the privacy in relation to bodily integrity and autonomy observed in the doctor-patient relationship.¹³⁴ In the digital space, there is a significant power disparity between entities responsible for data processing, who determine how data is processed, and individuals whose data is at stake.¹³⁵ This creates a pressing need to protect privacy, as the decisions made through automated data analysis and the inadequate safeguarding of private information can greatly impact people's lives. Unfortunately, many individuals using a particular service are often unaware of the extent of data processing and its potential consequences. Furthermore, once personal data is shared, users have limited control over how it is processed. Simultaneously, with advancements in processing capabilities, such as storage, CPUs, and networking, the intensity of personal data processing has grown. Current trends involve reducing the processing power of sensors, detaching guaranteed locations in cloud computing, widespread mobile and "always on" usage, and extensive use of big data analytics for various purposes. Essentially, ICT support has permeated almost every aspect of life, making the protection of personal data crucial.¹³⁶

Big data also presents significant legal and ethical challenges for patient privacy in terms of confidentiality, as it gives rise to a need to redefine health privacy, prioritize equity, consent, and patient governance in data collection, address discrimination in data usage, and handle data

¹³³ Hildebrandt, M. (2020). Private Law Liability for Faulty ICT. In M. Hildebrandt (Ed.), *Law for Computer Scientists and Other Folk* (pp. 219-234). Oxford University Press.

¹³⁴ Ibid

¹³⁵ Danezis, G., Domingo-Ferrer, J., Hansen, M., Hoepman, J.-H., Le Métayer, D., Tirtea, R., & Schiffner, S. 2014. Privacy and Data Protection by Design – from policy to engineering. *European Union Agency for Network and Information Security*. DOI: 10.2824/38623

¹³⁶ Ibid

breaches effectively.¹³⁷ This requires striking a balance between data accessibility and individual privacy rights. By addressing these challenges, we can leverage the benefits of big data while safeguarding patient privacy.¹³⁸

Moreover, the advent of the cyber age and the existence of cyberspace, encompassing computers, computer networks, the internet, information technology, and virtual reality, have led to a significant portion of individuals' personal and financial activities being conducted on the Internet.¹³⁹ However, these tools have also become avenues through which civil wrongs are perpetrated. Cyber-torts refer to civil wrongs committed on computer systems or networks, such as fraudulent misrepresentation, cyber defamation, and negligent enablement of cyber-crimes.¹⁴⁰ Although Nigeria has enacted a **Cybercrimes (Prevention and Prohibition) Act 2015**, it mainly provides liability for cybercrimes. As such, the realm of cybertorts is still very novel in the country. Given that telemedicine is also now conducted within cyberspace, this would nonetheless constitute an avenue for liability.

2.4. Telemedicine

Telemedicine is the use of medical information exchanged from one site to another via electronic communications to improve a patient's clinical health status.¹⁴¹ According to the European Commission, it can be defined as:

"the provision of healthcare services, through the use of ICT, in situations where the health professional and the patient (or two health professionals) are not in the same location. It involves secure transmission of medical data and information, through text, sound, images or other forms needed for the prevention, diagnosis, treatment and follow-up of patients."¹⁴²

¹³⁷ Price, W.N., Cohen, I.G. 2019. Privacy in the age of medical big data. *Nature Medicine*, 25, 37–43. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-018-0272-7>

¹³⁸ Ibid

¹³⁹ Alasa, A. 2019. A Legal Analysis of Cybercrimes and Cybertorts: Lessons for Nigeria. Available at SSRN: <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3560905> retrieved June 20,2023

¹⁴⁰ Ibid

¹⁴¹ Parimbelli, E., Bottalico, B., Losiuk, E., Tomasi, M., Santosuosso, A., Lanzola, G., Quaglini, S., & Bellazzi, R. 2018. Trusting telemedicine: A discussion on risks, safety, legal implications and liability of involved stakeholders. *International Journal of Medical Informatics*, 112, 90-98. ISSN 1386-5056. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2018.01.012>.

¹⁴² Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on telemedicine for the benefit of patients, healthcare systems and society /COM/2008/0689 final. <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:52008DC0689> retrieved May 20,2023

During the 1970s, the term "telemedicine" was introduced, referring to the concept of providing medical care and information remotely through the use of ICT to enhance patient outcomes and improve access to healthcare.¹⁴³ Subsequently, a report by the World Health Organization (WHO) in 1998 gave a definition for the term as:

"The delivery of health care services, where distance is a critical factor, by all health care professionals using information and communications technologies (ICT) for the exchange of valid information in diagnosis, treatment and prevention of disease and injuries, research and evaluation, and for the continuing education of health care providers..."¹⁴⁴

Often used interchangeably with concepts such as telehealth and e-Health,¹⁴⁵ telemedicine is nonetheless narrower than both. Telemedicine involves healthcare professionals using information and communication technology (ICT) exclusively to deliver clinical services which can include preventive care, as well as the diagnosis and treatment of individuals' health conditions.¹⁴⁶ On the other hand, telehealth encompasses not only clinical applications of ICT, but also with regards to health prevention and promotion and public health in general.¹⁴⁷ E-Health, often used in association with digital health, entails not only telehealth but "*solutions that use the internet and related technologies to deliver and enhance health services and information.*"¹⁴⁸ While undoubtedly a difficult to define term, eHealth can be said to refer to a broader application of ICT to health encompassing various products, services, and processes incorporating organizational transformations within healthcare systems.¹⁴⁹

¹⁴³ Solimini, R., Busardò, F. P., Gibelli, F., Sirignano, A., & Ricci, G. 2021. Ethical and Legal Challenges of Telemedicine in the Era of the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Medicina*, 57, 1314. <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina57121314>

¹⁴⁴ Ibid, p.57

¹⁴⁵ Balestra, M. 2017. Telehealth and Legal Implications for Nurse Practitioners. *The Journal for Nurse Practitioners*, 14(1), pp. 33-39, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nurpra.2017.10.003> . The WHO definition also combined telemedicine and telehealth.

¹⁴⁶ Cypher, Rebecca L. 2020. Telehealth and Telemedicine During a Crisis: Tips to Reduce Liability Risk. *The Journal of Perinatal & Neonatal Nursing*, 34(3), pp.205-207. <https://doi.org/10.1097/JPN.0000000000000502>

¹⁴⁷ Ojonugwa, A. F., Gwom, S. G., & Jolashinm, M. A. 2023.. Telemedicine Practice in Nigeria: Lessons from Indonesia. Redeemer's University Nigeria, *Journal of Jurisprudence & International Law*, 3.

¹⁴⁸ Ebenso B, Allsop MJ, Okusanya B, Akaba G, Tukur J, Okunade K, et al. 2018. Impact of using eHealth tools to extend health services to rural areas of Nigeria: protocol for a mixed-method, non-randomised cluster trial. *BMJ Open*. 8:e022174. Retrieved May 18, 2023 from <https://doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2018-022174/>

¹⁴⁹ Bakx, I. (2021, June). eHealth and Patients' Rights. Erasmus Rotterdam University <https://www.eur.nl/en/eshpm/media/2021-06-iris-bakx-ehealth-and-patients-rights-embargo-versie0> retrieved 17 June 2023.

Telemedicine has been experiencing rapid growth as a method of providing medical care by utilising electronic communications and information technology especially since the COVID-19 pandemic.¹⁵⁰ Telemedicine has proven to be a valuable resource, particularly in underserved communities and remote areas where access to adequate clinical care is limited. Thanks to advancements in technology infrastructure, it has expanded beyond rural care to integrate with various medical specialties, offering reliable and cost-effective solutions. This transformative approach enables licensed healthcare providers to provide their expertise directly to patients in need, eliminating the need for patient transportation.¹⁵¹ The use of telemedicine technologies further facilitates effective communication between patients and healthcare providers. It enables various activities such as scheduling appointments, monitoring chronic conditions, accessing laboratory results, prescribing medication, and seeking clarification on medical advice.¹⁵²

Thus, telemedicine offers numerous benefits such as improved access, quick patient engagement, and reduced costs. It enables remote collaboration among healthcare professionals, improving service quality and facilitating consultations with experienced colleagues or experts. Patients, more aware of their rights and seeking second opinions, benefit from telemedicine's convenience and access to distant doctors through phone, email, or websites. It is particularly useful in areas with limited healthcare infrastructure and access to medical professionals like Nigeria, where long travels for medical care and wait times are burdensome, costly, and hinder efficiency. Telemedicine aids in preventive medicine, offering information and remote monitoring for chronic conditions, reducing hospitalisation costs, and enhancing patient comfort. It also enhances patient safety by eliminating errors due to illegible handwriting through electronic prescriptions. Telemedicine empowers patients, increases health and technical education, and facilitates access to specialist opinions, primary care assessments, preoperative assessments, and postoperative follow ups; especially beneficial for rural areas and rare diseases. Overall, telemedicine improves healthcare delivery and expands

¹⁵⁰ Mills, E. C., Savage, E., Lieder, J., & Chiu, E. S. 2020. Telemedicine and the COVID-19 Pandemic: Are We Ready to Go Live?. *Advances in skin & wound care*, 33(8), 410–417. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.ASW.0000669916.01793.93>

¹⁵¹ Nittari, G., Khuman, R., Baldoni, S., Pallotta, G., Battineni, G., Sirignano, A., Amenta, F., & Ricci, G. 2020. Telemedicine Practice: Review of the Current Ethical and Legal Challenges. *Telemedicine and e-Health*, 26(12), 1427-1437. <https://doi.org/10.1089/tmj.2019.0158>

¹⁵² Kmucha, Steven. 2020. Telemedicine and Physician Liability Issues. *Ear, Nose, and Throat Journal*, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0145561320928207>

services, benefiting both healthcare institutions and patients.¹⁵³ Thus, telemedicine-enabled medical care has shown to have high patient satisfaction and to be as effective as medical care delivered in-person.¹⁵⁴

The primary methods employed in telemedicine are virtual patient-doctor interactions or store-and-forward technology, which aim to replicate the traditional in-person interaction between patients and physicians.¹⁵⁵ Telemedicine applications have been classified into four main areas: teleconsultation, tele-education/tele-expertise, telesurgery, and telemonitoring.¹⁵⁶ Various devices can be employed for remote communication in telemedicine, enabling distance interactions. These devices include video-conferencing units, email platforms, webcams, PDAs (Personal Digital Assistants), and smartphones. The communication channels utilized for remote interaction can also differ, encompassing options such as broadband connections, network infrastructures, and wireless technologies. The wide range of devices and communication channels available provide flexibility and options for individuals to engage in remote communication effectively.¹⁵⁷

However, the emergence of telemedicine has necessitated a closer examination of the legal implications surrounding the delivery of healthcare services through information and communication technology (ICT) by physicians. The reliance on patient-provided data, documents, images, and other information in telemedicine visits opens providers to potential liability if patients suffer harm due to negligent acts or omissions, miscommunication, misdiagnosis, software malfunctions, or other technological risks that jeopardise patient welfare.¹⁵⁸ These issues primarily revolve around the patient-physician relationship,

¹⁵³ Raposo V. L. 2016. Telemedicine: The legal framework (or the lack of it) in Europe. *GMS health technology assessment*, 12, Doc03. <https://doi.org/10.3205/hta000126>; Mazzuca, D., Borselli, M., Gratteri, S., Zampogna, G., Feola, A., Della Corte, M., Guarna, F., Scoria, V., & Giannaccare, G. 2022. Applications and Current Medico-Legal Challenges of Telemedicine in Ophthalmology. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 19(9), 5614. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19095614>; Gioia, G., & Salducci, M. 2019. Medical and legal aspects of telemedicine in ophthalmology. *Romanian journal of ophthalmology*, 63(3), 197–207.

¹⁵⁴ Pourmand, A., Ghassemi, M., Sumon, K., Amini, S. B., Hood, C., & Sikka, N. 2021. Lack of telemedicine training in academic medicine: Are we preparing the next generation? *Telemedicine Journal and e-Health*, 27(1), 62-67. doi: 10.1089/tmj.2019.0287

¹⁵⁵ Kmucha, Op cit.

¹⁵⁶ Bensemmane, S. and Baeten, R. 2019. Cross-border telemedicine: practices and challenges. OSE Working Paper Series, Research Paper No.44 Brussels: European Social Observatory, October, 63p.

¹⁵⁷ Raposo, op cit.

¹⁵⁸ Lowe, L. Sep. 2020. *Uptick in Telehealth Reveals Medical Malpractice Concerns*, Bloomberg Law, retrieved 17 May, 2023 from

malpractice, patient privacy and confidentiality, licensure, informed consent, standards and quality of care, as well as regulatory challenges in cybersecurity and data protection, technological certification standards, device regulation, conflicting cross-border telemedicine, and accountability for the safety of hardware and software.¹⁵⁹ Further exploration can generate the issues of criminal liability for actions that may pose an immediate risk to life or health, as well as civil liability in cases of harm or damage caused.¹⁶⁰

With regards to medical malpractice, which is typically defined as a physician's departure from customary medical practice, a key question that arises is whether doctors are held to the same standard of care in telemedicine as they would be in traditional medicine.¹⁶¹ The practice of telemedicine further raises questions as to obtaining informed consent, practice standards and protocols, and oversight requirements for non-physician providers. Moreover, it is necessary to understand the customary practices that clinicians should follow to ensure continuity of care when utilising digital health solutions. In cases of medical errors in diagnosis or prescription, an important question arises: should the responsibility be attributed to the clinician or the AI-based clinical decision-making system?¹⁶² Another crucial aspect is determining when the physician-patient relationship is established for the purpose of assessing liability in cases of malpractice. Additionally, when a doctor engages in telemedicine across country borders, how does the court determine which standard of care to apply in a malpractice lawsuit?¹⁶³

Furthermore, the use of digital health platforms for patient examinations instead of in-person office visits poses significant challenges for healthcare providers. The lack of physical

<https://news.bloomberglaw.com/health-law-and-business/uptick-in-telehealth-reveals-medical-malpractice-concerns>

¹⁵⁹ Langarizadeh M., Moghbeli F., Aliabadi A. 2017. Application of ethics for providing telemedicine services and information technology. *Medicine Archives (Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina)*, 71(October):351–355. doi: 10.5455/medarh.2017.71.351-355; Szalontay, A. S., Dascalescu, A.-D., Schipor, P.-D., Aghiorgiesei, M. L. Q. B. Q., Macovei, G., & Chirita, R. 2022. Pros and cons approach regarding the use of telemedicine in clinical practice. *Bulletin of Integrative Psychiatry*, 28(4), 71+.

<https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/A737699711/HRCA?u=anon~3b41260c&sid=googleScholar> retrieved 18 May 2023.

¹⁶⁰ Król-Całkowska, J., Walczak, D., & Szymański, W. 2022. Telemedicine in the Past and Now—Polish Regulatory Framework and the Scope of Civil and Criminal Liability of the Medical Staff. *Teka Komisji Prawniczej PAN Oddział w Lublinie*, 15(1), 113-128. <https://doi.org/10.32084/tkp.4459> retrieved 17 May 2023.

¹⁶¹ Wolf, TD. 2020. Telemedicine and Malpractice: Creating Uniformity at the National Level. 61 *Wm. & Maryland Law Review*, 1505, <https://scholarship.law.wm.edu/wmlr/vol61/iss5/7> retrieved 18 May 2023.

¹⁶² Rowland, S.P., Fitzgerald, J.E., Lungren, M. 2022. Digital health technology-specific risks for medical malpractice liability. *npj Digital Medicine*, 5, 157. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-022-00698-3> retrieved 17 May 2023.

¹⁶³ Ibid

examination can lead to the incorrect diagnosis of patients' health conditions or the inappropriate prescription of medications. A recent study conducted by CRICO, a prominent organisation specialising in medical professional liability, found that 66% of claims related to telemedicine filed between 2014 and 2018 in the United States were linked to diagnostic errors.¹⁶⁴

Aside from doctors or clinicians in general, telemedicine also brings into play the third party intermediaries. Where data breaches occur, who would be held responsible (the doctor or telemedicine platform provider)? Does the third-party owe a duty traditionally owed by doctors to their patients? How does the provider protect the public against frauds posing as doctors? Also, given that patients themselves are key stakeholders in telemedicine as it unarguably grants them higher degree of autonomy, how would these impact defences like contributory negligence? These multifaceted and novel issues highlight the urgent need for well-defined legal guidelines and standards in the field of telemedicine.

Overall, the conceptual framework for liability in telemedicine can be summed up in this diagram:

¹⁶⁴ Ibid, n.20

Figure 2.2: A conceptual framework of liability in telemedicine. (Source: Author, 2023)

2.5. Liability in Telemedicine

Literature on liability in telemedicine have majorly focused on identifying potential legal and ethical issues arising in telemedicine, with few studies seeking to analyse liability in telemedicine from a country-specific approach examining the legal framework.

In reviewing the impact of telemedicine on physician liability, Kmucha summarised it as encompassing licensure, establishing the physician-patient relationship, evaluation and treatment, informed consent, medical records, referrals for emergency services, continuity of care, privacy and security of patient records, disclosures and functionality of telemedicine platforms, and prescribing practices based on the model guidelines issued by United State's Federation of State Medical Boards.¹⁶⁵ A similar identification was made by Kaplan in his review article which reiterated the significance of the doctor-patient relationship, along with data confidentiality, security, informed consent, and patient and family satisfaction in telemedicine services.¹⁶⁶ As Kmucha noted, establishing when a patient-physician relationship for instance begins can be challenging in remote settings, affecting trust and liability determinations. As such, informed consent with full disclosure of services being offered via telemedicine and possible risks must be obtained. To this end, Langarizadeh et al. have also highlighted the legal implications of end user licensing agreements (EULAs) and smart contracts.¹⁶⁷ Moreover, strict adherence to prescribing regulations and patient safety considerations is essential despite the unfamiliar terrain of telemedicine.¹⁶⁸ A similar point is made by Anwar and later in Anwar et al.¹⁶⁹ with regards to potential liability in telemedicine, although he also touches on the issue of its impact on appropriate standards of care relevant in determining most malpractice liability.¹⁷⁰

¹⁶⁵ Ibid, n.115; this is nearly identical to the issues highlighted by Solimini et al., op cit.

¹⁶⁶ Kaplan, B. 2020. Revisiting health information technology ethical, legal, and social issues and evaluation: Telehealth/telemedicine and COVID-19. *International Journal of Medical Informatics*, 143, p.104239. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2020.104239>

¹⁶⁷ Langarizadeh, M., Moghbeli, F., & Aliabadi, A. (2017). Application of ethics for providing telemedicine services and information technology. *Medical Archives*, 71, pp.351-355. doi: 10.5455/medarh.2017.71.351-355

¹⁶⁸ Ibid, n.115

¹⁶⁹ Anwar, M.M., Mostafa, E.M.A., Shehata, S.A., Abd ElHafeez, S., & Ali, N.M. (2023). Medicolegal Liability and Telemedicine Practice during COVID-19 Pandemic: Egyptian Physicians' Perspectives. *Zagazig Journal of Forensic Medicine and Toxicology*, 21(1).

¹⁷⁰ Anwar, A. 2016. The Principles Of Liability On Telemedicine Practices. 1(1), pp. 013-037. <http://dx.doi.org/10.47268/palau.v1i1.2016.6>

Regarding the issue of what should form the benchmark of appropriate standard of care in healthcare provision through telemedicine, Rowland et al.¹⁷¹ raises vital issues. According to him, key considerations would include establishing accepted norms for history taking and physical examination during telehealth consultations, documenting these on electronic systems, determining when it is safe to offer digital-first solutions for disease management, ensuring continuity of care, and assigning liability in cases of medical errors involving AI-based clinical decision-making systems – whilst navigating where it is appropriate to even utilise AI in clinical decision-making. In their empirical analysis of the existing literature on telemedicine to identify the ethical and legal challenges associated with its usage, the study by Nittari et al. sought to assess these issues. However, their findings revealed gaps in legislation around the globe as well as limited in-depth literature addressing these issues at both global and regional levels.¹⁷²

According to Parimbelli et al.,¹⁷³ telemedicine has been a topic of legal and ethical debate since before specific telemedicine systems existed. Early applications, such as telephone and email consultations, raised concerns about the doctor-patient relationship and legal jurisdiction in potential lawsuits. Unlike traditional medicine, multiple stakeholders are involved in modern telemedicine, including system designers, developers, physicians, pharmacists, and even patients themselves. Pharmacists may utilise teleconsultation for support, and patients and caregivers become active participants in healthcare delivery. The legal implications and security requirements of medical apps have also sparked debates, as standardised guidelines and regulations are lacking, placing the responsibility on developers to ensure safety and quality and bringing to fore issues such as technological certification standards and device regulation according to Langarizadeh et al.¹⁷⁴ Overall, Parimbelli et al. observed that telemedicine necessitates careful attention to legal issues such as patient care, privacy, and security, involving various stakeholders.

¹⁷¹ Ibid, n.120

¹⁷² Ibid

¹⁷³ Parimbelli, E., Bottalico, B., Losiouk, E., Tomasi, M., Santosuosso, A., Lanzola, G., Quaglini, S., & Bellazzi, R. 2018. Trusting telemedicine: A discussion on risks, safety, legal implications and liability of involved stakeholders. *International Journal of Medical Informatics*, 112, 90-98. ISSN 1386-5056.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2018.01.012.y>

¹⁷⁴ Langarizadeh, op cit.

Raposo¹⁷⁵ in considering the legal framework for telemedicine in Europe highlighted gaps in its regulation of telemedicine. Despite the issuance of working documents and position papers by European institutions, there is still a lack of uniform norms regulating telemedicine in Europe. The absence of European norms concerning medical liability, tort or criminal liability, and the standard of care for healthcare providers further complicates matters. Moreover, defining the appropriate entity to regulate and control telemedicine becomes challenging due to its involvement in multiple countries and domains, such as medicine, IT, privacy, and social security. Moreover, telemedicine has unique characteristics derived from its nature. For instance, the handling of complex technologies, such as remote measurement devices, electronic health records, robotic surgeries, and online prescription of drugs, may require specific qualifications from healthcare professionals that are not required in conventional medicine. Many European countries still lack specific regulations on telemedicine, for which Raposo argued for the need for comprehensive and harmonised norms in this field to enable both patients and doctors to feel more secure in using telemedicine. This is parallel to a study by Król-Całkowska et al. establishing the potential physician criminal and civil liability associated with immediate risks to patients' lives or health in Poland's Laws.¹⁷⁶ While telemedicine has become an integral part of healthcare services, existing laws only partially address this issue as they are fragmentary.¹⁷⁷ Studies examining the legal framework of telemedicine in India, Egypt, and Italy reached the same conclusion.¹⁷⁸

In Nigeria, while there have been several studies conducted on telemedicine generally¹⁷⁹ limited attention has been given to liability in telemedicine. A recent 2023 study by Ojonugwa

¹⁷⁵ Raposo, op cit.

¹⁷⁶ Król-Całkowska, ibid n.134

¹⁷⁷ Ibid, n.134

¹⁷⁸ For India: Ateriya et al., op cit. Nonetheless, India has a Telemedicine Practice Guidelines of 2020 that acts as a regulatory instrument. For Egypt, Anwar et al. Op cit. For Italy, Ferorelli, D., Nardelli, L., Spagnolo, L., Corradi, S., Silvestre, M., Misceo, F., Marrone, M., Zotti, F., Mandarelli, G., Solarino, B., & Dell'Erba, A. (2020). Medical legal aspects of telemedicine in Italy: application fields, professional liability and focus on care services during the COVID-19 health emergency. *Journal of Primary Care & Community Health*, 11. DOI: 10.1177/2150132720985055

¹⁷⁹ Olufunlayo, T. F., Ojo, O. O., Ozoh, O. B., Agabi, O. P., Opara, C. R., Taiwo, F. T., Fasanmade, O. A., & Okubadejo, N. U. (2023). Telemedicine ready or not? A cross-sectional assessment of telemedicine maturity of federally funded tertiary health institutions in Nigeria. *Digital health*, 9, 20552076221150072. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2055207622115007>; Egbewande, O. M., Oladipo, H. J., Olowolagba, S. A., & Iyiola, K. H. (2023). Application of Telemedicine in the Provision of Healthcare in Nigeria: An Insight from COVID-19. *Journal of Health Reporting and Technology*, 9(1), e130916. <https://doi.org/10.5812/jhrt-130916>; Ikumapayi, O. M., Kayode, J. F., Afolalu, S. A., Nnochiri, E. S., Olowe, K. O., & Bodunde, O. P. (2022). Telehealth and Telemedicine – An Overview. In Proceedings of the International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Operations Management, Nsukka, Nigeria, 5 - 7 April 2022. Retrieved from <https://ieomsociety.org/proceedings/2022nigeria/258.pdf>; Allagoa, D. O., Kemelagha, F. A., Ighedose, L. O., &

et al.¹⁸⁰ conducted a comparative analysis of the implementation of telemedicine in Nigeria and Indonesia, in which it examined the legal framework for telemedicine in Nigeria. Like most countries in Europe and India as seen above, there is no *sui generis* legislation and laws governing telemedicine are contained in multiple laws. As such, it was recommended that although some Nigerian teaching hospitals and local software companies have adopted telemedicine practices, the country needs to establish dedicated legislation and comprehensive guidelines for telemedicine.¹⁸¹ These should cover various aspects such as online consultations, diagnoses, prescriptions, dispensing of medicine, and the storage and accessibility of health information. The legislation should also address licensing or accreditation requirements for telemedicine applications and establish a governing body to regulate and enforce telemedicine practices nationwide.

The authors further allowed that successful implementation will require not only the enactment of laws but also strong political commitment.¹⁸² However, the article did not adequately consider the issue of liability as this was not its primary concern, and instead followed the path of foreign literature on the subject to merely identify possible legal challenges. It also did not critically examine the existing legal framework to see if indeed they covered the field with regards to telemedicine so as to avoid a waste of legislative process, especially since the country which was being comparatively analysed, that is, Indonesia, has no *sui generis* legislation on telemedicine either.

Again, Labisi¹⁸³ explored the concept and evolution of telemedicine in Nigeria, evaluated the current regulatory framework, examined relevant medico-legal issues, and also emphasised the necessity of establishing a legal framework as done by Ojonugwa et al. Additionally, potential obstacles to these objectives were discussed, along with the consideration of legal aspects and successful telemedicine integration in some jurisdictions. The findings indicated that due to the

Tella, A. O. (2020). Telemedicine in Nigeria: A medium to the underserved communities. *Yenagoa Medical Journal*, 2(1), 135-144.; Adenuga, K. I. (2020). Telemedicine system: service adoption and implementation issues in Nigeria. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 13(12), 1321-1327.

doi:10.17485/IJST/v13i12.180; Adenuga, K. I., Iahad, N. A., & Miskon, S. (2017). Towards reinforcing telemedicine adoption amongst clinicians in Nigeria. *International journal of medical informatics*, 104, 84–96. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2017.05.008>

¹⁸⁰ Ojonugwa, *ibid* n.120

¹⁸¹ *Ibid*

¹⁸² *Ibid*, p.14

¹⁸³ Labisi, O. E. 2021. The Legal Framework of Telemedicine in Nigeria (LLB Long Essay), Babcock University.

inadequate and fragmented state of the healthcare system in Nigeria, there is a critical need to enhance awareness regarding the advantages of telemedicine. Furthermore, adequate funding and legislation are imperative to effectively govern telemedicine practices. Consequently, the essay recommended that both state and federal governments collaborate to develop an appropriate regulatory framework that seamlessly incorporates telemedicine into the existing healthcare system.¹⁸⁴ While agreeing on the need for legislation, Labisi focused on regulatory measures as the jurisdictions other than Nigeria analysed only had regulatory guidelines with regards to telemedicine. Moreover, the essay also did not adequately examine liability in telemedicine as this was not its primary objective, while its examination of relevant laws were not comprehensive.

Likewise, Ikwu et al.¹⁸⁵ assessing the current status of telemedicine in Nigeria, aimed to identify existing gaps within the legal framework. It thereafter proposed the need for specific policies and legislation to be developed by the government and relevant authorities in order to establish an efficient telemedicine system that aligns with the standards of traditional healthcare practices. Like the previous studies reviewed, it also did not provide a framework for liability in telemedicine in the country.

As such, it is evident that there are still significant gaps in literature with regards to liability in telemedicine within Nigeria's legal framework. This study therefore will fill in these gaps in subsequent chapters.

2.6. Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework underpinning this study is the legal theory of remedial liability, which focuses on enforcing the rights of the individual.¹⁸⁶ Remedial liability aims to address and rectify the harm caused by a violation of rights by compelling the responsible party to comply with their obligations.¹⁸⁷ As such, as a legal theory, it seeks to provide an avenue of

¹⁸⁴ Ibid

¹⁸⁵ Ikwu, A.N., Komolafe, D.T., Ahaneku, G.I., Nwawudu, S.E. 2021. Advancement of telemedicine in Africa and the current laws: A case study of Nigeria. *Medico-Legal Journal*. 89(4):270-275.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/00258172211018341>

¹⁸⁶ Steel, S. 2022. Defensive and Remedial Liability. *Oxford Studies in Private Law Theory*, volume 2,

<http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4042198> retrieved June 30 2023

¹⁸⁷ Ibid

compensation when duties imposed on another in relation to a person whose right is not observed, often leading to harm (although there might not need to be a direct harm as with absolute liability), and in practice is imposed by courts based on the the existing breach of rights. Nonetheless, Steel maintains that the interrelationships between rights and duties for remedial liability should not be seen in the light of the narrower Hohfeldian schemes.¹⁸⁸ That is because a foundational essence of law is to provide remedy for wrongs, as embodied in the *ubi jus, ubi remedium* maxim. As its aim is not necessarily to punish (in terms of criminal justice), remedial liability rests in the realms of private law.¹⁸⁹ This liability primarily exists in both torts and contracts.¹⁹⁰ In tort law, it refers to the legal obligation to provide compensation or remedy for harm or injury caused by a wrongful act or negligence. In contract law, it refers to the duty to fulfill contractual obligations and provide remedies for breach of contract.¹⁹¹

In the traditional sense, a judicial private law remedy (JPLR) refers to a court-ordered action that arises from two distinct situations: either a violation of a legally recognized right or an anticipated violation of such a right.¹⁹² In the case of a rights-violation, it is commonly accepted that the innocent party is entitled to a "secondary" remedial right against the defendant, aiming to restore them to a position as close as possible to what it would have been if the original "primary" right had not been violated.¹⁹³ Conversely, when there is a threat of rights violation, the innocent party may be granted the power to seek a judicial ruling compelling the defendant to fulfill their corresponding "primary" duty. Under this perspective, the primary reason for awarding most judicial JPLRs is to either establish or reinforce the "primary" or "secondary" legal obligations that defendants already owe to claimants.¹⁹⁴

Based on this, there are two main forms of remedies: damages and injunction. Damages refer to the monetary compensation awarded to the claimant, typically to be paid by the defendant. The fundamental principle underlying damages is that of full compensation, which aims to

¹⁸⁸ Ibid; the Hohfeldian theory also prescribes jural relations but it is argued that it focuses on defining the concepts of rights and duties instead of providing remedy.

¹⁸⁹ Jaffey, P. 2022. Remedial consistency in private law. *University of Toronto Law Journal*, 72(2), 216-244. <https://www.muse.jhu.edu/article/849226>

¹⁹⁰ Davies, P. S. (n.d.). Remedies in English Private Law. *Intersentia*. <https://intersentia.com/en/law-of-remedies.html>

¹⁹¹ Ibid

¹⁹² Winterton, D. and Pilkington, T. 2021. Examining the Structure of Remedial Law. *The Modern Law Review*, 84: 1137-1158. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2230.12649>

¹⁹³ Ibid

¹⁹⁴ Ibid

restore the claimant to the position they would have been in if the wrongdoing or tort had not occurred.¹⁹⁵ An injunction, on the other hand, is a court order that compels a person to either perform or cease a specific action. Injunctive relief is granted at the discretion of the court, and failure to comply with an injunction can result in being held in contempt of court. In the realm of law, an injunction can be prohibitory (preventing certain actions) or mandatory (requiring specific actions).¹⁹⁶ Its primary purpose is to maintain the status quo, particularly in situations where further acts or the absence of such acts would cause irreparable harm to one of the parties involved.

In considering liability in telemedicine, the theory of remedial liability is paramount in order to guarantee that the safety and rights of patients are not sacrificed on the altar of technological advancement. Moreover, given the inherent ethical duties in medical practice, having clear liability guidance would enable the ethical medical practitioner who might be previously unwilling to adopt telemedicine to do so. Therefore, its significance lies in its dual impact: protecting patients and promoting the accelerated adoption of telemedicine.

¹⁹⁵ Black's Law Dictionary, 2nd Ed, <https://thelawdictionary.org/damage/> retrieved June 30 2023

¹⁹⁶ Britannica. 2023. *What is an Injunction?* <https://www.britannica.com/story/what-is-an-injunction> retreat June 30 2023.

CHAPTER THREE

LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR TELEMEDICINE IN NIGERIA

3.1. Domestic Legislations

3.1.1. The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (CFRN) 1999 as amended

While Nigeria's Constitution does not explicitly provide for a framework for healthcare or even a right to health, it contains provisions upon which a legal framework guiding the operation of telemedicine in Nigeria can be established. The most direct reference is observed in Chapter II where the Nigerian state is obligated to direct its policy towards ensuring that "*...the health, safety and welfare of all persons in employment are safeguarded and not endangered or abused; ...there are adequate medical and health facilities for all persons.*"¹⁹⁷ The element of obligation on the part of the State connoted by the use of the term "*shall*" in the provision arguably presupposes a correlating right to health.¹⁹⁸ This has led to a general consensus on the interpretation of Chapter II generally as relating to socio-economic rights (so-called second generation rights), the enforcement of which has largely been controversial due to the proviso rendering them non-justiciable.¹⁹⁹ Nonetheless, it provides a veritable framework for the operation of telemedicine as telemedicine ensures that healthcare is increasingly accessible. On the other hand, it would also have a negative application in the sense that the state is obligated to safeguard the health and safety of persons, which would give rise to liability in telemedicine.

Other provisions which can serve as frameworks for telemedicine in Nigeria are seen in Chapter IV of the Constitution, which provides for the fundamental rights. Chief among these is **Section 33 (1)** which states that "*every person shall have a right to life and no one shall be deprived intentionally of his life unless in execution of the sentence of a court of a criminal office of which he has been found guilty.*" Given that health has the potential to reduce lifespan or the

¹⁹⁷ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended), Section 17(3)(c)-(d)

¹⁹⁸ According to the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR), the right to health encompasses entitlements and freedoms that guarantee not necessarily *being healthy* (as this may be impracticable), but the *highest attainable standard of physical and mental health* including the right to healthcare facilities, prevention, treatment and control of diseases; and access to essential medicines. <https://www.ohchr.org/Documents/Publications/Factsheet31.pdf>

¹⁹⁹ CFRN 1999 (as amended), Section 6(6)(c). This was further upheld with regards to the right to education in the same chapter in *Okojie v. Attorney General of Lagos State* (1981) INCLR 218

quality of life, it is regarded as a vital component of the right to life.²⁰⁰ Moreover, medical malpractice, whether carried out in traditional face-to-face healthcare delivery or through telemedicine, may directly or indirectly lead to the deprivation of life of a person. In addition, **Section 34(1)** establishes the right of individuals to dignity, which is further qualified to mean, *inter alia*, that no person is to be "subjected to torture or to inhumane or degrading treatment." According to the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR), this would include the right to be free from non-consensual medical treatment, such as biomedical research or forced sterilisation.²⁰¹ Moreover, it has been argued that if a person is in poor health, their ability to even take normal actions to safeguard their dignity is impaired – meaning that the right to health is central to dignity.²⁰² Finally, **Section 37** establishes the right to privacy, which is key in the physician-patient relationship and even more so in the context of telemedicine where cybersecurity concerns are a significant threat to this right.

With regards to administration, **Item 60(a), Part 1** of the **Second Schedule** to the Constitution grants exclusive powers to the National Assembly (the federal legislative body) to establish and regulate authorities for the purpose of ensuring the observance of the fundamental objectives and directive principles of state policy. This includes encouraging access to quality healthcare. By implication, the Constitution grants the National Assembly with powers to enact laws and establish regulatory bodies for telemedicine, cementing its status as the grundnorm from which other laws that would be examined derive their validity.

3.1.2. National Health Act 2014

Nigeria's National Health Act 2014 (NHA 2014) was signed into law on October 31, 2014 after long debates and controversy within the medical field surrounding the Act. It provides a legal framework for the regulation, development and management of the country's health system and to see standards for the delivery of healthcare services in Nigeria. Divided into seven parts and sixty-five sections, it provides for the establishment of a national health system comprising the

²⁰⁰ See Human Rights Committee, General Comment 6, Article 6 (Sixteenth session, 1982), Compilation of General Comments and General Recommendations Adopted by Human Rights Treaty Bodies, UN Doc. HRI/GEN/1/Rev.1 at 6 (1994), para. 5. Moreover, in the Indian case of *State of Punjab v. M.S. Chawla*, it was held that the right to life ensured under Article 21 incorporates inside its ambit the right to health and clinical consideration.

²⁰¹ Ibid

²⁰² Paulius Čelkis and Eglė Venckienė. 2014. RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE RIGHT TO DIGNITY AND THE RIGHT TO HEALTHCARE. *International Journal of Arts and Commerce*, Vol. 3 No. 5, p. 166. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/278025927_RELATIONSHIP_BETWEEN_THE_RIGHT_TO_DIGNITY_AND_THE_RIGHT_TO_HEALTHCARE

Federal Ministry of Health and state/local government health commissions and committees, private healthcare providers, as well as traditional and alternative healthcare providers.²⁰³ Providers of telemedicine solutions can be invariably referred to as private healthcare providers, even though they do not deliver health services conventionally; meaning that they are covered by the Act. Moreover, this national health system is tasked with defining and setting standards for healthcare delivery.²⁰⁴ The National Health Council, which is the highest health policymaking body in Nigeria, is also established.²⁰⁵ In addition, it provides generally for the rights and responsibilities of patients and healthcare professionals,²⁰⁶ health research,²⁰⁷ management of human resources in the healthcare sector,²⁰⁸ organ donation/transplantation and artificial reproductive methods,²⁰⁹ amongst others.

Health technologies are specifically mentioned in Part II of the Act; where all health institutions are mandated to be in possession of a certificate of standards to render health services.²¹⁰ This is one of the very few references to applications of technology in health in the Act, the second being the provision for confidentiality of electronic health records.²¹¹ The last reference is with regards to health research which was provided in Part III of the Act, where in the definition section health research was said to include "*research on the development of new applications of health technologies.*"²¹² These provisions would be discussed extensively later with regards to licensure, confidentiality, and informed consent; but for now it is necessary to highlight the fact that it is apparent that the drafters of the National Health Act did not adequately consider telemedicine. Aside from the little mention of health technologies, it is only defined as "*machinery or equipment that is used in the provision of health services.*"²¹³ While this seems broad on the surface, it is necessary to state that much of information and communication technology (ICT) on which telemedicine is based utilises software technologies, which do not fall within the regular meaning of equipment and machinery.²¹⁴ Would this then mean that

²⁰³ National Health Act 2014, s.1

²⁰⁴ National Health Act 2014, s.1(1)

²⁰⁵ National Health Act 2014, s.4,5

²⁰⁶ National Health Act, s.20-30

²⁰⁷ National Health Act, s. 31-40

²⁰⁸ National Health Act, s. 41-45

²⁰⁹ National Health Act, s.47-58

²¹⁰ National Health Act, s.13

²¹¹ National Health, s.29(2)(i)

²¹² National Health Act, s.64

²¹³ National Health Act, s.64

²¹⁴ According to the Cambridge Dictionary, machinery is defined as "a group of large machines or the parts of a machine that make it work" <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/machinery> while equipment is

telemedicine providers that utilise mobile application cannot be described as utilising health technologies?²¹⁵ This remains to be settled.

3.1.3. Medical and Dental Practitioners Act 1988

The Medical and Dental Practitioners Act is the primary legislation governing the registration, licensing, and regulation of medical and dental professionals in Nigeria.²¹⁶ It establishes the Medical and Dental Council of Nigeria and grants it responsibility for determining the standards of knowledge and skill expected from its members, and periodically reviewing the code of conduct for medical practitioners.²¹⁷ The Act also empowers the Council to approve courses, qualifications, and institutions for medical and dental training in Nigeria.²¹⁸ With regards to qualifications, for instance, the Act prescribes that full registration as either medical practitioner or dental surgeon is granted upon attending a Council-approved training course at an approved institution and holding a certificate of experience issued under **Section 11** of the Act.²¹⁹ The Council is also charged with maintaining a register of medical practitioners in Nigeria, containing their names, addresses, qualifications, and other relevant information.²²⁰

Apart from its key role in the licensure of medical and dental professionals, the Act also establishes the Medical and Dental Practitioners Disciplinary Tribunal which has disciplinary powers with regards to professional misconduct.²²¹ The Act specifies the circumstances under which the Council can exercise its disciplinary powers, including cases of infamous conduct, convictions by a court or tribunal, or fraudulent registration.²²² Such conduct may range from

defined as "the set of necessary tools, clothing, etc. for a particular purpose"
<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/equipment>

²¹⁵ In the USA, the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) have clarified this by providing requirements for a software to be deemed to be a medical device (software as a medical device) as "a medical device software intended to collect, analyse, or display medical information to diagnose, monitor, or treat medical conditions". They further provide practical instances for when a software can be seen as medical equipment, whether used remotely or not <https://www.fda.gov/medical-devices/software-medical-device-samd/what-are-examples-software-medical-device>. However, given that the NHA does not explicitly refer to this, we cannot be certain that telemedicine was contemplated in the Act.

²¹⁶ Agbator, A. I. (2020, March 17). The legal and regulatory framework governing the health profession in Nigeria and the United Kingdom: A synopsis. The Firma Advisory. Retrieved from <https://thefirmaadvisory.com/blog/the-legal-and-regulatory-framework-governing-the-health-profession-in-nigeria-and-the-united-kingdom-a-synopsis>

²¹⁷ Medical and Dental Practitioners Act, s.1

²¹⁸ Medical and Dental Practitioners, s.1(2)(a), 9, and 10.

²¹⁹ Medical and Dental Practitioners Act, s.8

²²⁰ Medical and Dental Practitioners Act, s.6(2)

²²¹ Medical and Dental Practitioners Act, s.15

²²² Medical and Dental Practitioners Act, s.16(1). The Code of Medical Ethics in Nigeria further elaborates on acts considered infamous conduct (Rule 26 of the Code).

neglecting or disregarding professional duties to patients, abusing professional privileges or skills, engaging in behaviour derogatory to the medical profession (such as drunkenness or drug abuse), adultery with a patient, and engaging in self-promotion, advertising, or canvassing.²²³ Offences stipulated directly under the Act relate to persons or corporate bodies who fraudulently portray themselves to be doctors or dentists in Nigeria without due registration.²²⁴ In addition, the Medical and Dental Practitioners Investigation Panel is authorised to conduct preliminary investigations into allegations of infamous conduct or misconduct.²²⁵

With regards to the extent of the powers of the Disciplinary Tribunal, it extends to civil cases after due investigation by the Panel. With regards to criminal cases, the courts in *Medical & Dental Practitioners Disciplinary Tribunal v. Okonkwo*²²⁶ and *Denloye v. Medical & Dental Practitioners Disciplinary Committee*²²⁷ have held that it has no jurisdiction to try criminal matters. Nonetheless, the Disciplinary Tribunal is still bound to uphold the principles of fair hearing as guaranteed by the Constitution²²⁸ in the conduct of the trials. Upon conviction by the tribunal, the Act prescribes punitive actions ranging from admonishing to suspension or expulsion depending on the gravity of the misconduct.²²⁹

3.1.4. Child Rights Act 2003

The **Child Rights Act 2003** is a product of Nigeria's ratification and domestication of the United Nations' Convention on the Rights of the Child of 1989. It prescribes the rights of a child (a person below the age of eighteen)²³⁰ as provided under the **CFRN 1999 (as amended)**. Nonetheless, it goes beyond the fundamental rights as found in Chapter IV of the Constitution to include socio-economic rights, among which is the right to health in **Section 13**. This notable section provides that "every child is entitled to enjoy the best attainable state of physical, mental, and spiritual health".²³¹ It further imposes the duty of ensuring this right to health not

²²³ Rules 26-70 of the Code of Medical Ethics; seen in *Akintade v. Chairman, Medical and Dental Practitioners Disciplinary Tribunal* (**supra**); *Okonkwo v. Medical and Dental Practitioners Disciplinary Tribunal* (2000) FWLR (Pt. 44) 542.

²²⁴ Medical and Dental Practitioners Act, s.17

²²⁵ Medical and Dental Practitioners Act, s.15(3)

²²⁶ (2001) 7 NWLR (Pt. 711) 206 at 245.

²²⁷ (1968) 1 ANLR 306 at 320.

²²⁸ CFRN 1999 (as amended), s.36

²²⁹ Medical and Dental Practitioners Act, s.15(1)

²³⁰ Child Rights Act, s.277

²³¹ Child Rights Act, s.13(1)

only on the government, but also on the child's parents and guardians, institution, service, agency, organisation or body responsible for the care of a child.²³² This would therefore extend to telemedicine providers and healthcare institutions. Besides from this, the Act mandates the various tiers of government in Nigeria to ensure that the following determinants of child health are safeguarded:

- Reduced infant and mortality rate;
- Provision of necessary medical assistance and health care services to all children; especially the development of primary health care,
- Provision of adequate nutrition and safe drinking water;
- provision of good hygiene and environmental sanitation;
- Appropriate health care for expectant and nursing mothers;
- Immunisation²³³

With regards to telemedicine, the Act further charges governments with the duty to "combat **disease** and **malnutrition** within the framework of **primary health care** through the *application of appropriate technology*".²³⁴ **Section 17(1)** also provides a possible framework for civil liability in telemedicine where it provides that:

A child may bring an action for damages against a person for harm or injury caused to the child wilfully, recklessly, negligently or through neglect before, during or after birth of that child.

Thus, the Act is an important statutory framework for telemedicine in Nigeria. However, it is necessary to note that since child matters are not within the purview of the National Assembly, state houses of Assembly have to ratify the Act to make it effective within their respective states. As of November 2021, only 26 states had ratified and adopted the Act due to controversies as to its conflicts with religious and cultural beliefs especially as pertaining to child marriage and succession laws.²³⁵

3.1.5. Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act 2018

The Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act, 2018 ("FCCPA") is the *sui generis* legislation regulating economic competition and ensuring the protection of consumer interests

²³² Child Rights Act, s.13(2)

²³³ Parents are charged with the duty to ensure that a child under their custody is provided with full immunisation by the age of 2. Failure to do so is an offence for which the penalty is a fine not exceeding N5,000.00 on first offence and one-month imprisonment for subsequent offences. See in Child Rights Act, s.13(4), (5), (6).

²³⁴ Child Rights Act, s.13(3)(e)

²³⁵ National Child Health Policy, 2022

in Nigeria. Among its objectives are "*to protect and promote the interests and welfare of consumers by providing consumers with wider variety of quality products at competitive prices*"²³⁶ The FCCPA established the Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Commission and the Competition and Consumer Protection Tribunal to promote the development of fair, efficient and competitive markets in Nigeria, so as to facilitate citizens' access to safe products and safeguard their rights as consumers.²³⁷ The Commission is required to undertake specific regulatory functions which include actively pursuing methods to remove or eliminate hazardous goods and services from the market.²³⁸ This includes products or devices with emissions, untested aspects, controversial features, emerging technologies, or new technologies. The aim is to compel offenders to replace these goods or services with safer and more suitable alternatives. Moreover, it is granted powers to hold accountable any company, firm, trade, association, or individual found to be at fault and require them to take necessary actions to safeguard, compensate, provide relief, and protect injured consumers or communities from the detrimental impacts of inherently harmful, injurious, violent, or highly hazardous technologies.²³⁹ The Tribunal on the other hand is empowered to resolve disputes arising from the Act.

In relation to providing a legal framework for the operation of telemedicine in Nigeria, the FCCPA makes two key provisions: establishing the rights of consumers²⁴⁰ and imposing duties on manufacturers, importers, distributors and suppliers of goods and services.²⁴¹ Given that telemedicine often involves both the product (with regards to software and hardware technologies and equipment for its delivery) and the healthcare service, the provisions of the Act in this regard are therefore applicable to it. The consumer rights established in the FCCPA include:

- a. Right to information in plain and understandable language that a consumer with average literacy skills and minimal experience as a consumer could be expected to understand,²⁴²

²³⁶ Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act 2018, s.1

²³⁷ Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act 2018, s.3 and

²³⁸ Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act 2018, s.17(m)

²³⁹ Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act 2018, s.17(z)

²⁴⁰ Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act 2018, Part XV. This was a novel introduction as it was not provided for in the repealed Act.

²⁴¹ Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act 2018, Part XVI

²⁴² Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act 2018, s.114

- b. Right to non-misleading labelling and trade description;²⁴³
- c. Right to safe and quality goods; as well as timely delivery/performance²⁴⁴
- d. Right to return goods which are defective, unsafe, or unsuitable by reason of time lapse or non-correspondence with the description for the purpose for which they are bought²⁴⁵
- e. Right to fair dealing in marketing, supply, collection of payments, etc.;²⁴⁶
- f. Right to fair, reasonable, and just contract terms in the supply of goods and services;²⁴⁷
- g. Right against false, misleading or deceptive representations in marketing and otherwise.²⁴⁸

In addition, manufacturers, importers, distributors and suppliers of goods and services are required to withdraw hazardous products from the market. The FCCPA thus imposes liabilities for the supply of defective goods, breaching implied obligations by law and for misrepresentation.²⁴⁹ Another notable feature of the Act is that it grants supremacy to itself as it overrides the provision of any other law (with exception to the Constitution) in all matters relating to consumer protection and competition.²⁵⁰ Thus, where the provisions of any other statute are in conflict with it, it will prevail.

3.1.6. Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023

The Nigerian Data Protection Act 2023, signed into law by President Bola Ahmed Tinubu in June, 14, 2023,²⁵¹ is a laudable and relevant legislation that provides an extensive legal framework for the protection of personal data in Nigeria. It also establishes the Nigeria Data Protection Commission²⁵² for the regulation of the processing of personal information, and for related matters. The primary objective of the Act is to protect the fundamental rights, freedoms, and interests of persons (known as data subjects) to privacy as guaranteed under the Constitution.²⁵³ To achieve this primary objective, it then aims to regulate and govern the ways

²⁴³ Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act 2018, s.116

²⁴⁴ Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act 2018, s.130,131,132

²⁴⁵ Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act 2018, s.122

²⁴⁶ Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act 2018, s.124

²⁴⁷ Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act 2018, s.127

²⁴⁸ Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act 2018, s.125

²⁴⁹ Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act 2018, s.134-140

²⁵⁰ Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act 2018, s.104

²⁵¹ <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/news/more-news/604442-tinubu-signs-data-protection-bill-into-law.html#:~:text=The%20Nigeria%20Data%20Protection%20Act,of%20data%20protection%20in%20Nigeria.&text=President%20Bola%20Tinubu%20has%20signed,Bill%2C%202023%2C%20into%20law.>

²⁵² Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, s.4

²⁵³ Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, s.1

in which personal data is processed; encourage data processing practices that prioritise the security and privacy of individuals' personal data and do so in a manner that is fair, lawful, and accountable; safeguard the rights of data subjects and providing mechanisms for recourse and remedies in case of violations; enforce the responsibilities of data controllers and data processors towards data subjects; and establish an unbiased, independent, and efficient regulatory body to oversee data protection and privacy matters, as well as supervise data controllers and processors. This would ultimately reinforce the legal underpinnings of Nigeria's digital economy, thereby ensuring the country's active participation in regional and global markets.²⁵⁴ As such, given that telemedicine providers and healthcare professionals they work with control or process data, the Act is central in ensuring that telemedicine providers in Nigeria observe a high standard of data privacy and confidentiality.

With regards to the scope of the Act, it applies to the processing of personal data, whether automated or not, in the following cases: (a) Where the data controller/processor resides in Nigeria, (b) where data processing occurs within Nigeria, or (c) where the data controller/processor does not reside in Nigeria but processes personal data of a Nigerian data subject.²⁵⁵ Nonetheless, it allows for some exceptions such as when processing is done for household purposes; when a competent authority processes personal data for the prevention, investigation, detection, prosecution, or adjudication of a criminal offence or the execution of a criminal penalty or establish civil claims in a legal proceeding, in accordance with the law; or a competent authority processes data for prevention/control of a national public health emergency or for national security. It may also allow exceptions for public interest with regards to journalism, or educational, academic, artistic, and literary purposes.²⁵⁶ Personal data itself is defined by the Act as;

any information relating to an individual, who can be identified or is identifiable, directly or indirectly, by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, psychological, cultural, social, or economic identity of that individual.²⁵⁷

²⁵⁴ Ibid

²⁵⁵ Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, s.2

²⁵⁶ Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, s.3

²⁵⁷ Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, s.60

In other words, personal data relates to any information which, directly or indirectly, could identify a natural person. In furtherance of this protection for personal data, the Nigeria Data Protection Commission's responsibilities include implementing measures to enhance personal data protection, promoting the development of data protection technologies based on international standards, and ensuring compliance with both national and international obligations and best practices for personal data protection.²⁵⁸

The Act's provisions on data protection are extensive, covering the principles of data protection and lawful basis for the processing of personal data. It outlines the basis for informed consent, processing of sensitive data, obligations of the data controller and data processor, requirements for data protection impact assessment, amongst others.²⁵⁹ It also provides for the rights of data subjects, such as the right to erasure of personal data from records,²⁶⁰ withdrawal of consent,²⁶¹ the right to object to the processing of personal data,²⁶² and data portability.²⁶³ Furthermore, it lays down a foundation for data security, integrity, and confidentiality with duties imposed on data controllers and processors with regards to data breaches,²⁶⁴ while establishing a legal framework guiding cross-border transfers of personal data.²⁶⁵ It prescribes the registration, licensing, and fees for data controllers and data processors of major importance.²⁶⁶ Moreover, it provides for the enforcement of the rights of a data subject as established in the Act.²⁶⁷

It is necessary to highlight that the **Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023** comes after the **Nigerian Data Protection Regulation 2019** which had previously served as the main data protection legislation in Nigeria. The NDPR was issued by the National Information Technology Development Agency ('NITDA') pursuant to its establishment Act. Similar to the Data Protection Act, it provides for the rights of data subjects, the obligations of data controllers and data processors, transfer of data to a foreign territory amongst others.²⁶⁸ However, although it was considered as groundbreaking as the first all encompassing law on data protection in

²⁵⁸ Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, s.5

²⁵⁹ Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, s.19-28

²⁶⁰ Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, s.29

²⁶¹ Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, s.30

²⁶² Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, s.31

²⁶³ Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, s.33

²⁶⁴ Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, s.34-35

²⁶⁵ Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, s.36-38

²⁶⁶ Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, s.39-40

²⁶⁷ Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, s.41-48

²⁶⁸ Nigeria Data Protection Regulation

Nigeria, the NDPR had its own flaws which the Data Protection Act caters for. For example, the Regulation does not address privacy impact assessment, leaves gaps in its provisions on data retention, and fails to impose specific obligation to report data breach.²⁶⁹

Nonetheless, the NDPR is now subordinate to the Data Protection Act as it provides for its priority in data related matters:

"Where the provisions of any other law or enactment, in so far as they provide or relate directly or indirectly to the processing of personal data, is inconsistent with any of the provisions of this Act, the provisions of this Act shall prevail."²⁷⁰

In addition, both the NDPR and now the Data Protection Act is heavily modelled after the **European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)**, which has been described as the most comprehensive and watertight statute protecting personal data in the world.²⁷¹ Nonetheless, the Data Protection Act is not as comprehensive, and the extent to which this affects liability in telemedicine would be discussed later.

3.1.7. National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) Act of 2007

The NITDA Act established the National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) which had been created earlier in April 2001 to implement the Nigerian Information Technology Policy and coordinate general IT development in the country.²⁷² The Agency's responsibilities include creating a comprehensive framework for the regulation, development, and standardisation of Information Technology (IT) practices in Nigeria. This involves ensuring universal access to IT and system penetration, promoting IT application in public and private sectors, and facilitating electronic governance. The Agency also aims to incentivize the use of IT in all aspects of life, including the establishment of IT parks and systems. Additionally, it introduces regulatory policies and incentives to encourage private sector investment in the IT industry.²⁷³ Overall, the Agency plays a vital role in guiding and promoting IT development and adoption in Nigeria. Given that telemedicine is essentially an IT application in healthcare delivery, it falls under the purview of the NITDA Act.

²⁶⁹ Ademola Adeyoju (2021), "A Quick Guide on the Data Protection Regime in Nigeria" Available from: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3522188

²⁷⁰ Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, s.58

²⁷¹ European Union. 2023. Data Protection Regulation. Retrieved from <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/data-protection/data-protection-regulation/>

²⁷² National Information Technology Development Agency, 'Background' Available from: <https://nitda.gov.ng/background/>

²⁷³ National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) Act of 2007, s.6

With regards to telemedicine governance, the Act specifically empowers NITDA to "*develop guidelines for electronic governance and monitor the use of electronic data interchange and other forms of electronic communication transactions*". It is pursuant to this that NITDA enacted the NDPR 2019. Nonetheless, with the emergence of the Data Protection Act and the Data Protection Commission, NITDA may no longer function in the capacity of data protection. Nonetheless, it would still remain vital in establishing possible regulations for telemedicine governance.

Also, it is necessary to state that although the Agency is granted with lofty objectives, the Act itself does little to impose duties with regards to IT companies and operators, nor does it provide for consumer protection. In fact, the only duties and liabilities prescribed are with regards to tax payments in contributing to the NITDA Fund.²⁷⁴ For this reason, a new NITDA bill of 2021 is still under consideration which provides, *inter alia*, for an expansion of its key objectives to include coordinating and monitoring the adoption of digital products, platforms, and services, promoting the digital economy, ensuring the development and certification of IT systems and practices, protecting consumer rights, and supporting the development of technical standards for emerging technologies.²⁷⁵

The bill also introduces a licensing regime for operators in the industry, granting the National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) the authority to issue regulations and licenses. Operators will need to register with the agency, and any violations of the provisions in the Act will be considered offences with corresponding penalties.²⁷⁶ The licenses to be issued fall into three categories: Product License, Service Provider License, and Platform Provider License. However, the bill does not provide specific details on the criteria or requirements for obtaining these licenses.

Nonetheless, the bill has been subject to much criticism as the new licensing regime may create duplicity in licenses and pose difficulties for IT and Digital Economy companies.²⁷⁷ According to critics, the proposed NITDA Bill 2021 is notoriously "ambiguous, overlapping, and

²⁷⁴ National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) Act of 2007, s.

²⁷⁵ National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) Bill of 2021, s.6

²⁷⁶ National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) Bill of 2021, s.20

²⁷⁷ DETAIL Commercial Solicitors. (2021, September 20). The NITDA Bill and Its Potential Impact on Nigeria's Information Technology Industry and Digital Economy. Retrieved from https://www.detailsolicitors.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/DETAIL_NITDA-Article-20.9.21.pdf

overbearing."²⁷⁸ They argue that it could lead to significant conflicts within the ICT/telecoms industry and grant NITDA excessive powers, encroaching upon the jurisdictions of other regulatory bodies. It remains to be seen the eventual outcome of the debates on the bill, and if it is eventually enacted.

3.1.8. Nigerian Communications Act of 2003

With the objective to, among other things, "*protect the rights and interest of service providers and consumers within Nigeria*";²⁷⁹ the Nigerian Communications Act 2003 establishes the Nigeria Communications Commission (NCC)²⁸⁰ which is empowered to make and enforce "*such regulations as may be necessary under this Act to give full force and effect to the provisions of this Act*".²⁸¹ In accordance with the authority granted to it by **section 70** of the Act, NCC has developed subsidiary instruments. **The Consumer Code of Practice Regulations 2007**, also known as the NCC Code, imposes obligations on telecommunication service providers to ensure the protection and security of customer information. Providers are required to implement reasonable measures to prevent unauthorised or accidental disclosure of customer information and to securely store such data. The NCC Code also places restrictions on the transfer of customer information to third parties, except as permitted or required by other applicable laws or regulations.

Additionally, the NCC has established the **Registration of Telephone Subscribers Regulations of 2011**. **Section 9** of this regulation mandates entities to treat subscribers' personal information with strict confidentiality, taking necessary precautions to maintain the integrity of such information and utilising it only for specified purposes. **Section 10** of the NCC Regulation further prohibits the release of personal information to security agents, licensees, or any other individuals, except in cases where the law permits it. Furthermore, it prohibits the disclosure of subscribers' personal information to third parties and the transfer of such information without the consent of both the subscriber and the NCC.

In summary, both the NCC Code and the NCC Regulation aim to safeguard customer information by requiring telecommunication service providers to uphold strict confidentiality,

²⁷⁸ Adepun, A. (2022, March 17). How proposed NITDA Bill 2021 is unsettling ICT sector. The Guardian. Retrieved from <https://guardian.ng/technology/how-proposed-nitda-bill-2021-is-unsettling-ict-sector/>

²⁷⁹ Nigerian Communications Act 2003, s.1(g)

²⁸⁰ Nigerian Communications Act 2003, s.3

²⁸¹ Nigerian Communications Act 2003, s.4(1)(i)

maintain data integrity, and limit the disclosure and transfer of personal information in accordance with the law and regulatory provisions.

3.1.9. Cybercrimes (Prevention, Prohibition, etc.) Act 2015

The Act aims to create a robust legal and regulatory environment to combat cybercrimes, safeguard critical national information infrastructure, and enhance cybersecurity measures to protect various digital assets and rights.²⁸² It also specifically makes provisions for "*promoting cybersecurity and safeguarding computer systems, networks, electronic communications, data, computer programs, intellectual property, and privacy rights.*"²⁸³ It mandates that service providers must consider individuals' right to privacy and take measures to ensure the confidentiality of data retained, processed, or retrieved for the purpose of law enforcement.²⁸⁴

In addition, it imposes criminal liability on digital service providers who breach confidentiality. Computer-based service providers or vendors who forge or illegally use consumer security codes for fraud or subpar services face a N5,000,000 fine and forfeiture of customers' losses. Corporate bodies and their officers can be prosecuted, leading to winding up and asset forfeiture. Individuals may receive up to 7 years imprisonment, N5,000,000 fine, or both, but proving innocence or preventive measures can be a defence.²⁸⁵

3.1.10 Code of Medical Ethics

According to **Section 1(2)(c)** of the **Medical and Dental Practitioners Act 1988**, one of the statutory functions of the Medical and Dental Council of Nigeria is to periodically review and develop a statement outlining the code of conduct that the Council deems necessary for the ethical practice of the medical and dental professions in Nigeria. Pursuant to this, the Code of Medical Ethics was established in 2008. It is the single statutory instrument in Nigeria that specifically makes provisions for telemedicine. Within this code, medical practitioners are urged to exercise caution and avoid any medico-legal misrepresentations in various aspects of telemedicine, including confidentiality, equipment usage, patient referrals, professional consultations, and the registration status of specialists being consulted. Furthermore, the code mandates practitioners to ensure the security of personal information transmitted through

²⁸² Cybercrimes (Prevention, Prohibition, etc.) Act 2015, s.1

²⁸³ Ibid

²⁸⁴ Cybercrimes (Prevention, Prohibition, etc.) Act 2015, s.38-40

²⁸⁵ Cybercrimes (Prevention, Prohibition, etc.) Act 2015, s.29

emails or other electronic means, as well as during data storage.²⁸⁶ Beyond telemedicine, the Code also makes extensive provisions for the professional practice of medicine and dentistry generally.

However, the code does not comprehensively address several important aspects related to telemedicine. As observed by Labisi, it does not provide detailed guidance on the expected standard of care for telemedicine doctors, the protection of privacy, the requirement for informed consent, the maintenance of confidentiality, or the security of data.²⁸⁷ Additionally, the code does not specifically outline the permissible forms of treatment through telemedicine. Presumably, this was left subject to other laws and regulations in force; but nonetheless might present a challenge for enforcement, thus doing little to resolve the gaps in the practice of telemedicine within Nigeria.

3.1.11. Patients Bill of Rights

The Patients' Bill of Rights (PBoR) is a non-statutory instrument launched by the Federal Government of Nigeria under the auspices of the Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Commission on 1st August 2018.²⁸⁸ It contains an aggregation of rights prescribed in statutes including the Constitution, Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act 2018, National Health Act, Child Rights Act, Freedom of Information Act, among others. The concept of a patient's bill of rights was first adopted by the America hospital in 1973 and revised in October 1992 with the expectation that healthcare institutions would support these rights to improve service delivery at a time when persons are most vulnerable (that is, at the time of ill-health).²⁸⁹

The PBoR prescribes the following twelve rights:²⁹⁰

1. Right to relevant information
2. Right to timely access to medical records

²⁸⁶ Code of Medical Ethics, s.22

²⁸⁷ Labisi, O.E. 2021. "Legal Framework for Telemedicine in Nigeria"; op cit.

²⁸⁸ Hashim, Z. (2019, April 14). Patients' Bill of Rights: Making health a human right in Nigeria. Premium Times. Retrieved from <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/news/headlines/325291-patients-bill-of-rights-making-health-a-human-right-in-nigeria.html?tztc=1>

²⁸⁹ Takai, N. (2019). Patients' Bill of Rights and the Nigerian Nurse: Presented at 2019 Annual Nurses Week Organised by NANNM. Medical World Nigeria. Retrieved from <https://medicalworldnigeria.com/post/patients-bill-of-rights-and-the-nigerian-nurse-presented-by-nrs-nana-takai-rn-rpn-dl-bnsc-llb-bl-at-2019-annual-nurses-week-organised-by-nannm?pid=36238>

²⁹⁰ Patients Bill of Rights, retrieved from <https://articles.nigeriahealthwatch.com/patients-bill-of-rights-game-changer-or-another-policy-paper/?amp=1>

3. Right to transparent billing
4. Right to privacy
5. Right to clean healthcare environment
6. Right to be treated with respect
7. Right to receive urgent care
8. Right to reasonable visitation
9. Right to decline care
10. Right to decline or accept to participate in medical research
11. Right to complain and express dissatisfaction regarding services received
12. Right to quality care.

Nevertheless, given that it is not a statutory instrument, it can only be enforced within the existing legal framework; such as mechanisms prescribed for the fundamental rights to life, dignity of the human person and privacy²⁹¹ via the Fundamental Rights (Enforcement Procedure) Rules 2009 and the Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act 2018.

3.1.12. Nigerian Criminal Code²⁹²

Under the Criminal Code Act, there are limited provisions that address the criminal liability of medical practitioners. Some sections directly address criminal medical negligence, while others can be indirectly interpreted to establish criminal liability for medical negligence. **Section 230** imposes a duty on medical professionals to possess reasonable skill and employ reasonable care when administering medical care. They must exercise due diligence, expertise, and knowledge to avoid causing harm, injury, or death to patients. Nonetheless, **Section 296** limits the liability by providing for protection from criminal liability for individuals who perform surgical operations in good faith and with reasonable care and skill. This provision is intended to apply to emergency situations and includes both medical professionals and non-medical personnel. However, it lacks clarity regarding the scope of liability for any harm resulting from the surgical operation itself or subsequent consequences.²⁹³ Again, **Section 303** of the Act imposes a duty on those performing dangerous acts, including administering medical treatment, to use reasonable care and skill. If a medical professional fails to meet this duty and causes

²⁹¹ under Sections 33, 34 and 37 of the CFRN 1999 (as amended)

²⁹² C38: Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004

²⁹³ Imuekemhe, E. J. 2018. An Examination of the Disposition of the Law to Cases of Medical Negligence in Nigeria. *Edo State University Law Journal*, 1. Retrieved from Edo University Open Educational Resources Repository:

https://www.edouniversity.edu.ng/oerrepository/articles/an_examination_of_the_disposition_of_the_law_to_cases_of_medical_negligence_in_nigeria.pdf

harm to a patient, they can be held criminally liable. However, the section also introduces an exemption for cases of necessity, without defining the term. This exemption undermines the requirement for reasonable care and skill, regardless of the circumstances.

In summary, the existing provisions in the **Criminal Code** provides some basis for criminal liability in medical practice, which extends to telemedicine.²⁹⁴ However, there are ambiguities, gaps, and exemptions that need to be addressed to establish clear standards and legal consequences for malpractice situations involving surgical operations and medical treatment.

3.2. International legislations

3.2.1. Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948

In the 18th and 19th centuries, the concept of rights primarily focused on limiting the state's ability to actively deny citizens their basic civil and economic rights. However, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) introduced a paradigm shift. The UDHR, which was approved by the UN General Assembly on 10 December 1948, emerged from the lessons learned during the Second World War. The initial version of the Declaration was put forth in September 1948, and it underwent collaborative drafting involving more than 50 Member States. During the General Assembly session in Paris, on 10 December 1948, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights was officially adopted by resolution 217 A (III), with no nations dissenting and only eight abstentions.²⁹⁵

The UDHR consists of extensive provisions outlining the most fundamental rights and freedoms of the human person which are not bequeathed by the state but are rather inherent regardless of where the person is, or their race, sex, language, political or religious affiliation, birth or any other persuasion. Upon gaining independence on October 1, 1960, Nigeria was admitted as a member state of the United Nations on 7 October 1960, based on which the

²⁹⁴ The Penal Code Act does not explicitly provide for medical liability. Nonetheless, Section 220 of the Penal Code Act defines culpable homicide and includes provisions for cases where death is caused by a rash or negligent act. If a doctor's negligent conduct during surgery or treatment leads to a patient's death, they may be charged with culpable homicide not punishable by death, equivalent to manslaughter.

²⁹⁵ United Nations. (n.d.). History of the Declaration. Retrieved from <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/udhr/history-of-the-declaration>

UDHR became applicable to the State.²⁹⁶ It must be noted that subsequently, Nigeria's Constitutions have included human rights provisions modelled in part after the UDHR.

Article 25 of the UDHR acknowledges that states have an obligation to take proactive measures to ensure that all individuals have access to an adequate standard of living for the health and wellbeing of themselves and their families. This includes fundamental necessities like food, clothing, housing, healthcare, and social services that are essential for promoting health and well-being. This was further elaborated upon in the **International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (1966)** as the right to the highest attainable standard of physical and mental health.²⁹⁷ Nonetheless, as observed by the UN OHCHR, this right extends beyond healthcare and encompasses the underlying determinants of health. Four interconnected elements define its normative scope and content: availability, accessibility, acceptability, and quality.²⁹⁸

Availability requires sufficient functioning public health facilities, services, goods, and programs for all. Accessibility entails non-discrimination, physical accessibility, affordability, and information accessibility. It involves addressing barriers that hinder healthcare access, particularly for vulnerable populations, through clear norms, policies, and monitoring systems. Acceptability involves providing people-centred and culturally appropriate health services that respect medical ethics and consider gender-specific needs. Quality gives regard to facilities, goods, and services that meet scientific and medical standards. It includes safety, effectiveness, people-centeredness, timeliness, equity, integration, and efficiency.²⁹⁹

Moreover, based on the doctrine of positive obligation in the context of human rights law, two categories of responsibilities are imposed on the State, namely "first instance duties" and "back-up duties."³⁰⁰ "First instance duties" refer to the State's obligation to enact legislative, policy, and other measures aimed at safeguarding the rights enshrined in human rights law. On the

²⁹⁶United Nations Nigeria. n.d. About the UN in Nigeria. Retrieved from <https://nigeria.un.org/en/about/about-the-un#:~:text=The%20Federal%20Republic%20of%20Nigeria,1%20October%20the%20same%20year.>

²⁹⁷ International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (1966), art.12

²⁹⁸Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights. n.d. International standards on the right to physical and mental health. Retrieved from <https://www.ohchr.org/en/special-procedures/sr-health/international-standards-right-physical-and-mental-health>

²⁹⁹ Ibid; World Health Organization. n.d. Human rights and health. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/human-rights-and-health>

³⁰⁰ Hugh Breakey. 2015. Positive Duties and Human Rights: Challenges, Opportunities and Conceptual Necessities' *Political Studies*, 63, p.1198.

other hand, "back-up duties" come into effect when the State fails to fulfil its first instance duties and involve the State's mandate to ensure the provision of efficient remedies for violations of human rights.³⁰¹ As such, this forms a basis for States to enact laws that regulate the healthcare sector, especially with the introduction of information and communication technology as well as other emerging technologies.

Nonetheless, it has been noted that the right to adequate health espoused by the UDHR is difficult to define and apply as it is relative; and that its clarification as "the highest attainable standard" by the ICESCR is not explicit as to whether the assessment should be based on a nation's economic infrastructure alone or within the framework of the global community.³⁰² In some instances, a nation's highest attainable standard of living may not align with the existing consensus on the minimum health-related rights that all individuals should enjoy, such as access to vaccines, physical therapies, or geriatric care. Nevertheless, realising the right to health requires time and resources, states do have immediate obligations, including guaranteeing non-discrimination and taking deliberate steps to achieve the right for all individuals.³⁰³ This forms a foundation for the regulation of telemedicine to ensure that it only promotes, and does not in any way undermine a person's right to health.

Furthermore, the UDHR makes provisions for the protection of privacy (and by extension, that of a patient). In **Article 12**, it makes provisions similar to **Section 37** of Nigeria's Constitution when it states that:

"No one shall be subjected to arbitrary interference with his privacy, family, home or correspondence, nor to attacks upon his honour and reputation. Everyone has the right to the protection of the law against such interference or attacks."

3.2.1. African Charter on Human and Peoples Rights 1981

The increasing recognition and safeguarding of human rights at the global level resulted in a movement towards regional efforts in promoting and protecting these rights. Initially resisted by the UN, regionalisation faced opposition due to concerns about undermining the universality

³⁰¹ Mwanza, R. (2021). Compensation Funds as a Remedial Mechanism for Victims of Corporate Pollution in Kenya: A Feasibility Study. *Journal of Environmental Law*, 33, 557-584. doi: 10.1093/jel/eqab017

³⁰² University of Minnesota Human Rights Library. 2003. The right to health. Retrieved from <http://hrlibrary.umn.edu/edumat/studyguides/righttohealth.html>

³⁰³ Ibid

of human rights. However, States favoured regional systems, trusting mechanisms established by like-minded countries and granting power to regional bodies. Proximity and shared interests further supported regionalism. Importantly, regional efforts sought to uphold the principles of the UDHR and ensure its implementation within the regional context.³⁰⁴ It was based on this that Africa established its own bill of rights.

The African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights had its origins in the African Conference on the Rule of Law held in Lagos in 1961. During this conference, African jurists proposed the adoption of an African Convention of Human Rights to ensure that the conference's conclusions would be upheld through the establishment of an appropriate court with jurisdiction and accessible recourse for individuals under the jurisdiction of signatory states. The African Charter was adopted by the 18th Assembly of Heads of State and Government of the Organization of African Unity (O.A.U.) first in Banjul on January 19, 1981.³⁰⁵ Nigeria signed the Charter on August 31, 1982, ratified it on June 22, 1983, and deposited the instrument of ratification on July 22, 1983. Subsequently, on March 17, 1983, Nigeria enacted the Charter into law through the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act.³⁰⁶

In Nigeria, the relationship between international treaty law and domestic law is governed by **Section 12** of the Constitution. Treaties must be enacted into law by the National Assembly to have legal force domestically. Implementation can occur through statutes that adopt the treaty's exact wording or that reflect the treaty's spirit. Alternatively, treaties can be attached to statutes, giving them superior status, interpreted according to international law principles but remaining subordinate to the Nigerian Constitution.³⁰⁷

³⁰⁴ Ogbu, O. N. nd. THE AFRICAN CHARTER ON HUMAN AND PEOPLES' RIGHT AS COMPATIBLE WITH DESPOTISM: THE NIGERIAN EXPERIENCE. *Nigerian Law Guru*, Retrieved from <https://www.nigerianlawguru.com/articles/human%20rights%20law/THE%20AFRICAN%20CHARTER%20ON%20HUMAN%20AND%20PEOPLES%20RIGHT%20AS%20COMPATIBLE%20WITH%20DESPOTISM,%20THE%20NIGERIAN%20EXPERIENCE.pdf>

³⁰⁵ Ibid

³⁰⁶ Muiyiwa Adigun (2019): The implementation of the African charter on human and peoples' rights and the convention on the rights of the child in Nigeria: the creation of irresponsible parents and dutiful children?, *The Journal of Legal Pluralism and Unofficial Law*, <https://doi.org/10.1080/07329113.2019.1675988>

³⁰⁷ Ibid, Adigun

With the enactment of the **African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act** on March 17, 1983, the Charter was implemented into Nigerian law. **Section 1** of the Act states that the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights shall have the force of law in Nigeria and be applied by all authorities and persons exercising legislative, executive, or judicial powers. The Act, which includes the African Charter as a schedule, is not merely an ordinary Act but one that implements a treaty. Consequently, it has superior status, subject only to the Constitution.

Interestingly, the Charter provides for the right to health. Specifically, **Article 16** provides:

"1. Every individual shall have the right to enjoy the best attainable state of physical and mental health. 2. State Parties to the present Charter shall take the necessary measures to protect the health of their people and to ensure that they receive medical attention when they are sick."

In the celebrated case of *General Sanni Abacha et.al. v. Chief Gani Fawehinmi*,³⁰⁸ the Nigerian Supreme Court made a significant ruling regarding the application of the African Charter on Human Rights (ACHPR) within the country's legal system. The case revolved around the unlawful detention of the legal luminary and activist by the state's security service. The activist argued that his detention violated Articles 4, 5, 6, and 12 of the ACHPR. The Supreme Court concluded that since the ACHPR served as a protective instrument for human rights, its provisions could be invoked in Nigerian courts. To support its stance, the Court directly referenced the articles of the Charter, which stated that individuals whose rights had been violated were entitled to legal remedies to have their rights acknowledged. The Supreme Court further held that the absence of specific remedies in national legislation did not prevent citizens from exercising their rights as established in the Charter.

Based on the foregoing, it can be deduced that the right of citizens to health has been made enforceable by virtue of the ACHPR. Consequently, it establishes a broader health rights framework on which both the accessibility of health (which telemedicine provides), and the protection from abuse in the use of telemedicine can be based.

³⁰⁸ General Sanni Abacha et.al. v. Chief Gani Fawehinmi, Supreme Court, 28 April 2000. Retrieved from <https://ihl-databases.icrc.org/en/national-practice/general-sanni-abacha-et-al-v-chief-gani-fawehinmi-supreme-court-28-april-2000>

3.3. Summary

This chapter has examined the legal framework for the practice of telemedicine in Nigeria, consisting of a range of domestic and international legislations regulating sector-specific issues in telemedicine such as the rights-based approach to health, patient privacy, data protection, informed consent, among others. The table below aptly summarises these statutory instruments as follows:

Issues in Telemedicine	Relevant Laws	Domestic/International
Medical malpractice/negligence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Code of Medical Ethics ● Medical and Dental Practitioners Act 1988 ● National Health Act 2014 ● Nigerian Criminal Code Act 	Domestic
Patient privacy/confidentiality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (CFRN) 1999 as amended ● Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948 ● National Health Act 2014 ● Medical and Dental Practitioners Act 1988 ● Nigerian Communications Act of 2003 ● Code of Medical Ethics 	Domestic & International
Data Protection/Cybersecurity/Digital governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023 ● National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) Act of 2007 ● National Health Act 2014 ● Nigerian Communications Act of 2003 	Domestic

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cybercrimes (Prevention, Prohibition, etc.) Act 2015 	
Right to health/patient-consumer protection/product liability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (CFRN) 1999 as amended ● Child Rights Act 2003 ● Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act 2018 ● Code of Medical Ethics ● Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948 ● African Charter on Human and Peoples Rights 1981 	Domestic & International
Informed consent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (CFRN) 1999 as amended ● National Health Act 2014 ● Code of Medical Ethics 	Domestic
Licensure & Professional Regulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Medical and Dental Practitioners Act 1988 ● Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023 	Domestic
Technological certification standards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● National Health Act 2014 ● National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) Act of 2007 (Under review) 	Domestic
Cross-border telemedicine	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948 (indirectly) ● Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023 (data) 	International & Domestic

Table 3.1: *Legal Framework for the Regulation of Telemedicine in Nigeria* (Source: Author, 2023).

CHAPTER FOUR

CIVIL AND CRIMINAL LIABILITY IN TELEMEDICINE

This chapter will critically evaluate the conventional liabilities that exist in the practice of medicine, and then consider the extent to which innovations and developments brought on by telemedicine may impact these liabilities: from physician/healthcare provider's liabilities as negligence and malpractice, to issues surrounding informed consent, patient privacy and confidentiality, licensure, and determination of who is liable in lieu of vicarious liability and third-party telemedicine corporations.

4.1. Medical Negligence & Malpractice

4.1.1. Conventional Practice & Liability

As one of the indicators of an overburdened and collapsing healthcare system, medical negligence and malpractice has been reported to be on the rise in Nigeria. According to a 2017 survey published in the Archives of Medicine and Health Sciences, negligence was found to be prevalent among 42.8% of the 145 medical practitioners surveyed.³⁰⁹ Disturbingly, reports also indicate that medical errors have become the third leading cause of death in Nigeria, following cancer and cardiovascular disease.³¹⁰ Thankfully, the law is not silent on this as it provides remedies for patients who suffer at the hands of careless medical professionals, the conditions of which will be critically examined in this section.

Medical negligence and medical errors/malpractice are closely related but distinct concepts.³¹¹ Medical malpractice occurs when a healthcare provider chooses an inappropriate method of care or improperly executes an appropriate method of care, regardless of the outcome.³¹² It can

³⁰⁹ Onyekwere, J. (2023, February 21). Menace and consequence of medical negligence in Nigeria. The Guardian. Retrieved from <https://guardian.ng/opinion/menace-and-consequence-of-medical-negligence-in-nigeria/>

³¹⁰ Ibid

³¹¹ Imuekemhe, E. J. 2018. An Examination of the Disposition of the Law to Cases of Medical Negligence in Nigeria. Edo State University Law Journal, 1. Retrieved from Edo University Open Educational Resources Repository: https://www.edouniversity.edu.ng/oerrepository/articles/an_examination_of_the_disposition_of_the_law_to_cases_of_medical_negligence_in_nigeria.pdf

³¹² Enemo, I. P. 2012. Medical Negligence: Liability of Health Care Providers and Hospitals. Nigerian Juridical Review, 10, pp.101-120.

be properly defined as a commission or omission in the care of a patient that would have been judged wrong by skilled and knowledgeable peers at the time it occurred, regardless of whether any negative consequences resulted from it.³¹³ In other words, a medical error can occur even if there were no adverse outcomes for the patient. It is a professional judgment based on the established standards of the medical community, and may include instances of treatment errors³¹⁴ or inaccurate diagnosis as was referred to in *University of Ilorin Teaching Hospital v. Mrs. Theresa Akilo*.³¹⁵

On the other hand, medical negligence refers to a breach of the duty of care owed by a healthcare provider to a patient, resulting in harm or damage.³¹⁶ It can be said to be "the failure of the medical practitioner to exercise a reasonable duty of care in the course of his duty as a professional in that field."³¹⁷ The duty of care, which involves taking proper care to avoid causing injury or to act beneficially towards the patient, is owed by the healthcare provider to the patient they have agreed to treat who relies on the provider's skill and knowledge, a duty of care arises.³¹⁸ As such, it implies a greater burden of proof before it can be argued to have occurred as it is necessary to prove that the healthcare provider's breach of duty directly caused harm or injury to the patient, beyond a mere error in judgment.³¹⁹ While medical malpractice can be considered as acts that could potentially lead to negligence, not all medical errors constitute negligence.

Therefore, the following ingredients are necessary to prove medical negligence.³²⁰

- (a) Duty of care: that the medical professional owed the patient a duty to use reasonable care in treating him or her.

³¹³ Ibid

³¹⁴ *University of Nigeria Teaching Hospital Management Board and Ors v Hope Nnoli* [1994] 8 (NWLR) Pt. 365, 367, at 395-6.

³¹⁵ [2000] 22 WRN 117

³¹⁶ Adejumo, O. A., & Adejumo, O. A. 2020. Legal perspectives on liability for medical negligence and malpractices in Nigeria. *The Pan African medical journal*, 35, 44.

<https://doi.org/10.11604/pamj.2020.35.44.16651>

³¹⁷ Resolution Law Firm. (2020, November 11). Liability and Proof of Medical Negligence in Nigeria. Mondaq. Retrieved from

<https://www.mondaq.com/nigeria/professional-negligence/1004164/liability-and-proof-of-medical-negligence-in-nigeria#:~:text=In%20circumstances%20where%20the%20medical,procedure%20provided%20by%20the%20Act.>

³¹⁸ Ogundare, Bisola. 2019. Medical Negligence in Nigeria: A Quick Guide on Liabilities and Remedies. SSRN e-Library. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3476524>

³¹⁹ Ibid

³²⁰ These ingredients flow from the standard ingredients of negligence in the law of torts. Ogbuinya, J.C.A. in *University of Ilorin Teaching Hospital v Dr. Dele Abegunde* [2013] LPELR-21375(CA) gave a foundation for this by referring to the standard definition of negligence.

- (b) Breach of duty: That the medical professional failed to exercise reasonable care.
- (c) Damages: That the patient suffered damage(s) as a result of the breach.

A number of cases would be instructive in this light. In the case of *Mrs. Deborah Agere & Anor v Dr. S Ojobo*,³²¹ the claimants sought damages of one million naira, alleging negligence on the part of the defendant. They claimed compensation for the loss of their first male child, physical pain, emotional distress, and psychological depression resulting from the defendant's grossly reckless and negligent delivery of the first plaintiff's pregnancy. The first plaintiff had been referred to the defendant by her doctor for delivery. The defendant recommended a cesarean section after determining that a normal delivery would not be possible due to the plaintiff's pelvis. On the day of the delivery, the baby was found to be in distress, leading to a cesarean operation. The defendant also suggested a blood transfusion, which the plaintiff declined based on her religious beliefs. The baby unfortunately passed away three days after birth. The defendant denied all allegations, claiming they were untrue. He argued that the baby's distress was due to the plaintiff coming to the hospital eight days after the expected delivery date, potentially in an attempt to have a vaginal delivery. The court acknowledged that the defendant owed a duty of care to the plaintiff, but the plaintiffs failed to provide evidence establishing a breach of that duty. Some of the plaintiff's witnesses even testified to the defendant's reasonable care and efforts to preserve the plaintiff's life. As a result, the court dismissed the plaintiff's claims.

This decision can be said to draw from Lord Denning's dictum in *Hatcher v. Black*³²²

"A medical man, for instance, should not be found guilty of negligence unless he has done something of which his colleagues would say: "He really did make a mistake there. He ought not to have done it'...You must not therefore, find him negligent simply because something happens to go wrong.... you should only find him guilty of negligence when he falls short of the standard of a reasonably skillful medical man, in short, when he is deserving of censure."

That case was a notable one involving a plaintiff who was a singer and had a diseased thyroid. The plaintiff underwent a thyroidectomy based on the assurance that there was no risk to her voice. However, during the operation, a nerve was severely injured, resulting in damage to the

³²¹ Unreported suit No B/595/94.; accessed from Imuekemhe, op cit.

³²² 1958 Times, 2 July.

plaintiff's voice. It was later revealed that the doctor was aware of the slight risk to the plaintiff's voice but deliberately misled her to prevent her from rejecting the treatment.³²³

Another case which will be discussed before examining the ingredients of medical negligence separately will be that of *Miss Felicia Osagiede Ojo v Dr. Gharoro & UBTH Management Board*.³²⁴ The plaintiff in this case filed a claim against the defendants following a surgical procedure to address a specific medical condition. During the operation, one of the surgical needles broke and could not be retrieved, remaining inside the plaintiff's body. The plaintiff experienced severe abdominal and vaginal pain after the procedure and reported it to the first defendant, who attributed the pain to the stitches. However, when the pain persisted, X-ray examinations conducted four days later revealed the presence of the broken needle in the plaintiff's stomach, which was not there prior to the operation.

The plaintiff alleged that the defendants did not immediately perform another operation to remove the needle, citing fresh wounds from the initial surgery as the reason. She also claimed that the defendants failed to disclose that something had been left behind in her stomach. Additionally, she presented testimony from another gynecologist who stated that, due to the surgical procedure, the plaintiff would be unable to conceive a child. The defendants admitted to the presence of the broken needle but asserted that they informed the plaintiff after the initial operation. They also admitted to using sub-standard needles that could easily break during procedures. However, they denied the plaintiff's claim that the broken needle would affect her ability to have children, arguing that its location in the anterior abdominal wall had no impact on pregnancy. Thus, they implied that the plaintiff did not suffer any long-term injuries.

One legal question raised in the case was whether the plaintiff could rely on the doctrine of *res ipsa loquitur*. The court examined relevant precedents and held that the doctrine could be pleaded in the alternative. Ultimately, the judge ruled that while the defendants owed the plaintiff a duty of care in managing her medical condition, they were not negligent in their handling of the case, including leaving the broken needle in her abdomen as they apparently were not liable for the defect in the product. This decision, while being controversial in certain aspects as in a similar English case a surgeon had been found to be negligent for leaving behind

³²³ Ibid

³²⁴ (2006) LLJR-SC

cotton swabs in a woman's abdomen after an operation,³²⁵ nonetheless establishes that medical professionals would not bear product liability if it contributes to medical error.³²⁶

Duty of Care

A medical practitioner does not owe a duty of care to all the sick people in the world, but once he undertakes to treat a patient, whether or not there is an agreement, a duty of care can arise.³²⁷ This rationale is borne from the fact that when a patient seeks medical care from a healthcare professional, a contractual relationship is formed between them. However, even in cases where there is no explicit contract between a medical practitioner and a patient, the law still imposes a legal duty of care based on the principles of tort law.³²⁸ Hence, both contractual and tortious duties are in play which is why the existence of a formal agreement between the patient and medical practitioner will not be a hindrance to liability in negligence. The more important consideration therefore is whether or not the healthcare professional with specific skills and knowledge undertakes to provide care to a patient who relies on their expertise.³²⁹ In *Hedley Byrne & Co Ltd v Heller & Partners Ltd*,³³⁰ Lord Morris noted that if someone with special skill undertakes to apply that skill for the assistance of another person who relies upon it, a duty of care arises. Similarly, in *R v Bateman*,³³¹ the court explained that a person holding themselves out as possessing special skill and knowledge owes a duty of care to the patient or client. By this, even quacks or unlicensed persons posing as medical professionals can be held to have a duty of care.³³²

Breach of Duty

To establish a breach of duty, it must be shown that a medical practitioner's actions fell below an appropriate professional standard.³³³ The determination of this standard is a question of facts

³²⁵ *Mahone v. Osborne* [1939] 1 All ER 535

³²⁶ In the US case of *Silverhart v. Mt. Zion Hospital* 98 Cal. Rptr. 187 (Ct. App. 1971), a similar event occurred wherein a defective broken needle was left in the defendant's pelvis. The court reasoned that the liability of the hospital would depend on whether it was negligent in its use establishing that the general rule for equipment failure is that the provider or hospital may be liable for negligence in the care, maintenance, or use of the equipment, but will not be liable for latent defects which cause harm to a patient.

³²⁷ C. O. Okonkwo, "Medical Negligence and the Legal Implications" cited in *Enemo*, op cit.

³²⁸ Imuekemhe, Op cit.

³²⁹ Kodilinye Gilbert and Oluwole Aluko, *The Nigerian Law of Torts* (1st Ed, Spectrum Books Ltd, 1996), p.143

³³⁰ [1964] AC 465

³³¹ (1927) 19 Cr App R 8.

³³² Halsbury's Laws of England, cited in Kodilinye, *ibid*, p.83

³³³ Kodilinye, op cit.

and not of law, that is, it is not fixed and varies depending on the circumstances.³³⁴ In *Bolam v. Friern Hospital Management Committee*,³³⁵ McNair, J. opined that the standard for assessing a person's skill in a particular field is based on the ordinary skill level of a competent professional in that field. It is not necessary for someone to possess the highest level of expertise, but rather to demonstrate the ordinary skill of a proficient individual practicing in that specific field.³³⁶ Again, the court held a similar position in *Frost v. Mayo Clinic*³³⁷ that the expected standard of skill and knowledge for a medical professional is based on what is typically possessed and utilised by reputable doctors in similar practices within comparable communities, facing similar circumstances. It is in applying that skill and knowledge that the medical professional is required to exercise reasonable care. As such, what may be unacceptable practice for a doctor in more advanced countries like the United States may be standard practice here in Nigeria.³³⁸ Furthermore, consultants, being specialists, may be held to a higher standard due to their advanced knowledge and experience.³³⁹

Damage

In addition, the claimant must show that harm occurred to him and that but for the breach, the harm would not have arisen.³⁴⁰ That is, there must be the presence of injury as well as a direct causal link between the defendant's negligent acts or omissions and the plaintiff's injury. This causation is based on facts, as Lord Denning established in *M v. London Borough of Newham*.³⁴¹ Thus, in *Barnett v Chelsea & Kensington Hospital Management Committee*³⁴², three night-watchmen visited the hospital, complaining of vomiting since drinking tea and sought medical attention. The casualty officer advised them to go home, resulting in one of them, Mr. Barnett, dying from arsenic poisoning. Mrs. Barnett sued the hospital for negligence. The judge ruled that the hospital was not responsible for Mr. Barnett's death as even if he had been admitted, there was no known antidote that could have been administered. While the hospital failed in its duty of care, it was not deemed a direct cause of Mr. Barnett's demise as

³³⁴ Ibid

³³⁵ [1957] 1 WLR 582

³³⁶ Ibid

³³⁷ 304 F. Supp. 285, 1969

³³⁸ *Warnock v Kraft* (1938) 85 p. 2nd 505

³³⁹ *R v. Akerele* (1942) 8 WAKA 56. Consequently, in *Shakoor v. Situ*, the court held that an alternative medical practitioner could not be judged by the standard of an orthodox medical practitioner, as the alternative practitioner does not hold himself out as practicing orthodox medicine.

³⁴⁰ *Bolam v. Friern Hospital Management Committee*, Supra

³⁴¹ [1964] AC 465

³⁴² [1968] 2 WLR 42

the court's application of the "but for" test revealed. This test was similarly applied in *Ajaegbu v. Etuk*³⁴³, the plaintiff was unable to establish that the damage suffered was a result of the medical practitioner's breach of duty. In addition, determining damage also depends on the foreseeability principle and assessing the remoteness of the damage.³⁴⁴

Ordinarily, the burden of proving that negligence has occurred rests on the plaintiff who is claiming such, which they have to prove based on a balance of probabilities.³⁴⁵ Nonetheless, there are situations in which the evidence of the negligent act or omission is so clear on the surface that this burden of proof will shift to the defendant, as the court would apply the doctrine of *res ipsa loquitur*.³⁴⁶ *Mahone v. Osborne*³⁴⁷ and *Fish v Kapur*³⁴⁸ are examples where the doctrine applied when surgical swabs were left in a patient's body and a dental extraction resulted in a jaw fracture, respectively. In Nigeria, it was also invoked successfully in *Igbokwe & Ors v. University College Board of Management*,³⁴⁹ where the court found the hospital negligent on the after a woman suffering from post-maternal psychosis fell from the fourth floor of the hospital building despite specific instructions given to a nurse to keep an eye on her. However, there have been cases in Nigeria where this doctrine has been unsuccessfully invoked where the court determined that there was no breach of duty despite the medical error.³⁵⁰

While medical errors may not always successfully give rise to a claim in medical negligence, they can still have consequences as it can lead to disciplinary action against the healthcare provider by professional bodies such as the Medical and Dental Practitioners' Disciplinary Committee. This disciplinary action is typically based on a breach of medical ethics or professional standards.³⁵¹

³⁴³ (1962) 6 ENLR. 196.

³⁴⁴ Ibitoye, T. 2018. "Applicability of the Doctrine of Res Ipsa Loquitur in Medical Negligence in Nigeria". NAUJILJ, 9 (1). To determine remoteness, the *novus intervenes* principle also comes into play in determining if the causal chain was broken at any point.

³⁴⁵ Ibid

³⁴⁶ Literally meaning, "the thing speaks for itself".

³⁴⁷ Supra

³⁴⁸ All England Law. Reports, 1948 (2)

³⁴⁹ (1961) WNLR 173

³⁵⁰ *Miss Felicia Osagiede Ojo v Dr. Gharoro & UBTH Management Board*, Supra. Also seen in *O'Malley-Williams V. Board of Governors of National Hospital for Nervous Diseases* where the plea of *res ipsa loquitur* failed because the injury being complained of was a well-recognised consequence of the procedure that was carried out.

³⁵¹ These includes duties set out in the Code of Medical Ethics including neglecting urgent cases, incompetence in assessment and diagnosis, providing incorrect advice, failure to obtain proper consent, and making treatment mistakes.

Criminal Liability

Section 230 of the Criminal Code Act³⁵² establishes a duty for individuals who administer surgical or medical treatment to possess a reasonable skill set and exercise reasonable care in their actions. Where reckless or negligent behavior occurs during medical treatment, which is more reprehensible than the standard required for civil action, endangers human life or causes harm in relation to the treatment, the dispensing of medicine, or the handling of dangerous substances, a misdemeanor offense of one-year imprisonment would suffice.³⁵³ Furthermore, Section 303 of the Criminal Code pertains to situations where a person's grossly negligent behavior results in someone's death, thereby constituting the offense of manslaughter.³⁵⁴

4.1.2. Impact of Telemedicine on the Liability for Negligence

Duty of Care

With regards to the duty of care, it is apparent that the duty of care owed by a medical professional to a patient in telemedicine remains unchanged, as also approved by Nigeria's Code of Ethics for medical professionals.³⁵⁵ That is because the general principles for legal liability for medical malpractice remains consistent for telemedicine as they are in themselves sufficiently abstract to be applicable to remote care without requiring redefinition.³⁵⁶ The practical effect nevertheless is a different issue altogether because this is what determines the extent to which a patient can be remedied if they suffer harm. For instance, telemedicine raises significant issues such as whether the patient-doctor relationship can be established without physical interaction. To this end, can phone consultations, emails, or live Internet connections establish a patient-doctor relationship?³⁵⁷ Based on current case law as seen in *R v Bateman* and *Hedley Byrne & Co Ltd v Heller & Partners Ltd* (supra), the answer should be a resounding yes if it can be shown that the medical professional held himself out to be one, leading the patient to rely on his judgment. It does not matter what medium is used as long as this occurs. Nevertheless, it must be shown that there was actual or implied consent to enter into such a

³⁵² Criminal Code Act, Cap. C38, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004

³⁵³ Criminal Code Act, s.343

³⁵⁴ *R v. Akerele*, Supra. See also *R V. Lawanta* and *R V. Ozegbe*

³⁵⁵ Section 22

³⁵⁶ Holčapek, T., Šolc, M., & Šustek, P. 2023. Telemedicine and the standard of care: a call for a new approach?. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 11, 1184971. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2023.1184971>

³⁵⁷ Kramer GM, Kinn JT, Mishkind MC. 2015. Legal, regulatory, and risk management issues in the use of technology to deliver mental health care. *Cognitive Behaviour Practice*, 3(258), p.68.

relationship both from the medical professional and the patient; and as such the patient must have acted on the advice given by the medical practitioner.³⁵⁸ Nonetheless, the American Medical Association has mandated that in utilising telemedicine, a medical practitioner must establish a bona fide relationship with the patient, typically through an in-person examination, before prescribing treatment.³⁵⁹ While this may avoid any unnecessary legal defense seeking to dispute the existence of a patient-doctor relationship, it may not be practical in Nigeria where among the very reasons telemedicine is being advocated for is the high doctor-to-patient ratio.

The lack of physical interaction also impacts diagnosis and subsequently the prescription of treatment as the medical professional may solely have to rely on the verbal conjectures of the patient, leading to higher chances of medical error.³⁶⁰ Nonetheless, considering the case of *Burne v. A*³⁶¹ where a doctor made a wrong diagnosis of a child's condition due to the misleading description of symptoms by the child's mother over telephone, the court is likely to absolve the medical professional of liability even if he neglected to ask all necessary common-sensical questions.

Breach of Duty

Given that new knowledge and technology constantly emerges in the medical field, changing the standard of practice, determining what is the appropriate standard of duty in particular cases can be a thorny issue. Telemedicine brings this to fore as it represents yet another evolution for the medical profession. Consider the following hypothetical scenarios: where a doctor relies solely on the blurry images sent by a patient for the diagnosis of a skin condition, can he be said to have been negligent if he, as a result, makes a wrong diagnosis? Or where the family of a patient in a rural area distant from the hospital who has suffered an emergency condition e.g. stroke repeatedly calls their family doctor on the phone during work hours to provide them

³⁵⁸ In *Miller v. Sullivan* 625 N.Y.S.2d 102, 103 (App. Div. 1995), a prospective patient was suffering from the symptoms of a heart attack when he called a physician, who advised the prospective patient to come to the hospital but the latter did not and eventually died. It was held that there was no relationship established as the prospective patient failed to act on the advice.

³⁵⁹ The Code of Medical Ethics has recently highlighted the enduring ethical responsibilities of physicians during teleconsultations, extending beyond specific guidelines for telemedicine. New obligations have been emphasized, such as ensuring the accuracy of information, implementing protocols to prevent unauthorized access, safeguarding patient information's security and integrity, and verifying the patient's identity. Physicians are also advised to be aware of the limitations of technology, including their own limitations when relying on it. "Ethical Practice in Telemedicine", <https://code-medical-ethics.ama-assn.org/ethics-opinions/ethical-practice-telemedicine>

³⁶⁰ Kahn EN, La Marca F, Mazzola CA. 2016. Neurosurgery and telemedicine in the United States: assessment of the risks and opportunities. *World Neurosurgery*, 9(133), p.8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wneu.2016.01.075>

³⁶¹ [2006] EWCA Civ 24

with instructions for first aid and he fails to pick the call, would the doctor be liable for negligence if the patient is grievously affected? Or perhaps, where telesurgery is being performed by a junior doctor with the virtual supervision of a consultant on a patient and a technical glitch occurs due to the junior doctor's negligence which affects the success of the surgery and adversely affects the health of a patient, would the junior doctor be held to have breached his duty? And to which standard of care; his own, or the consultant's? Can the consultant also be liable?³⁶² In the instance of omission to use telemedicine, for instance during the Covid-19 pandemic where virtual consultations were the norm, if a doctor insisted on physical consultation and the patient became infected with Covid-19 as a result of exposure at the hospital, can the doctor be deemed negligent?

In the case of *Roe v Minister of Health*,³⁶³ the plaintiffs were injected with contaminated anesthetic by the anesthetist, causing them to become paralysed. The court ruled that the anesthetist was not considered negligent as the risk of contamination leading to such consequences was not commonly recognised or appreciated by competent anesthetists during that period. Later in *Bolam v. Friern Hospital Management Committee*³⁶⁴ this was crystallised as the Bolam test that the standard of care is measured by conventional practice. With regards to telemedicine therefore, applying this decision may mean that where a medical practitioner makes an error that might not have been foreseen by his fellow experts due to the use of a particular technology, they will not be liable despite the gravity of the error on the patient. However, this might be a serious hindrance to patient safety and right to health and ensuring that they obtain remedy for the harm suffered. The additional imposition of the burden of proving that there was such a breach of duty on the injured claimant also makes the process even more arduous for the victim who has suffered harm. Moreover, most commentators agree that litigation for medical negligence is already biased on the side of the defendants as the court heavily relies on expert witnesses (who are part of the medical profession) who are often

³⁶² In *Clarke v. Hoek* 219 Cal. Rptr. 845 (Ct. App. 1985). In a case involving a physician acting as a proctor for a surgeon seeking credentials, the court determined that the proctor did not have a physician-patient relationship with the patient and therefore had no duty to prevent malpractice. Factors considered included whether the consultant and patient had met, if the patient was examined, if records were viewed, if the patient's name was known, and if the consultation was paid or gratuitous. The proctor in this case reviewed X-rays and discussed the surgery plans but did not participate in the procedure, receive payment, or meet the patient. The court concluded that the proctor's duty was solely to observe and screen the surgeon on behalf of the hospital.

³⁶³ [1954] 2 QB 66

³⁶⁴ *Supra*

reluctant to speak against their fellow professional.³⁶⁵ It might therefore be impossible for patients to hold medical professionals accountable.

Nevertheless, not all judicial authorities fully subscribe to the rationale in *Bolam* or *Roe*. In *Hucks v. Cole*³⁶⁶ a doctor was found to have been negligent by the Court of Appeal after failing to administer penicillin to a patient with septic places on her skin, despite being aware that the organisms present could potentially cause puerperal fever. Several reputable doctors provided testimony stating that they would also not have administered penicillin under the given circumstances. Giving his reasons for not taking into account the testimony of the expert witnesses summoned by the defendant, Sachs L.J. said, at p. 397:

"When the evidence shows that a lacuna in professional practice exists by which risks of grave danger are knowingly taken, then, however small the risk, the court must anxiously examine that lacuna--particularly if the risk can be easily and inexpensively avoided. *If the court finds, on an analysis of the reasons given for not taking those precautions that, in the light of current professional knowledge, there is no proper basis for the lacuna, and that it is definitely not reasonable that those risks should have been taken*, its function is to state that fact and where necessary to state that it constitutes negligence...*The court must be vigilant to see whether the reasons given for putting a patient at risk are valid in the light of any well-known advance in medical knowledge, or whether they stem from a residual adherence to out-of-date ideas.*" (Emphasis mine).

Lord Browne-Wilkinson in *Bolitho v City and Hackney Health Authority*³⁶⁷ considered this case where he agreed to the notion that the court is not bound to hold that a defendant doctor escapes liability for negligent treatment or diagnosis just because he leads evidence from a number of medical experts who are genuinely of opinion that the defendant's treatment or diagnosis followed sound medical practice; and he established a proviso to the Bolam test that the accepted practice among professionals must be logically and defensibly grounded. The facts of the *Bolitho* case can be summarised as follows: Two-year-old Patrick Bolitho was admitted to St Bartholomew's Hospital for croup, under the care of Dr Horn and Dr Rodger. Due to concerns, Dr Rodger arranged for Patrick to have dedicated nursing by a special nurse. Patrick experienced two respiratory episodes where his breathing became noisy and he turned pale. Dr

³⁶⁵ Imuekemhe, op cit.

³⁶⁶ (a case from 1968 reported in [1993] 4 Med. L.R. 393); cited by Lord Browne-Wilkinson in *Bolitho v City and Hackney Health Authority* [1998] AC 232;

<https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/ld199798/ldjudgmt/jd971113/boli01.htm> retrieved June 30 2023.

³⁶⁷ *Supra*, n.34

Horn was notified but did not attend to him. Despite appearing well after each episode, Patrick suffered a respiratory and cardiac arrest half an hour after the second episode. Although he was revived, he sustained severe brain damage and eventually passed away. Patrick's mother, acting as the administratrix of his estate, sued the local health authority for negligence. She claimed that Patrick would have survived if he had been intubated. The health authority acknowledged that Dr Horn had breached her duty of care by not attending to Patrick. However, Dr Horn argued that even if she had seen Patrick, she would not have intubated him, and this decision would have been in line with a respected professional opinion. The House of Lords ruled that a defendant cannot evade liability by arguing that the harm would have occurred anyway due to another breach of duty. Therefore, it was necessary to determine if the hypothetical decision not to intubate Patrick would have been a breach of duty. Nonetheless, the court still did not hold the doctor liable as three out of eight expert witnesses summoned, including that of a consultant pediatrician, did not consider the failure to intubate as unreasonable given that it was an invasive procedure. Moreover, Lord Browne-Wilkinson opined that courts should be cautious in finding the body of professional opinion unreasonable and should only be left to "exceptional cases."³⁶⁸

As such, the current state of judicial precedent in dealing with the matter of standard of care in the ever-evolving medical practice leans towards the common opinion of a reputable body of professionals, even in the face of the most grievous medical errors. By implication, jurists have tended to leave it in the hands of the medical professionals to determine what is the appropriate standard of care in specific scenarios so long as it is in line with overarching legal and ethical principles that give it a logical foundation.³⁶⁹ To safeguard patients' safety in the age of telemedicine, it is therefore imperative that Nigeria's professional regulatory body for medical professionals draws up guidelines to determine the appropriate standard of care with telemedicine like has been done in some jurisdictions.³⁷⁰

³⁶⁸ Moreover, the where there are divided opinions between a body of medical professionals, the court is not permitted to choose one above the other so long as they are both competent as seen in *Maynard v. West Midlands Regional Health Authority* [1985] 1 All ER 635

³⁶⁹ The Legal principles will include patient's rights to life, health, dignity and privacy as discussed earlier. Some relevant ethical principles will include beneficence, non-maleficence, and justice.

³⁷⁰ Desai, C., Modgil, V. and Pearce, I. 2022. Avoiding litigation in the age of telemedicine. *Trends Urology & Men Health*, 13: 2-5. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tre.852>

Damages

Given that telemedicine occurs through a technology-based intermediary, it would have implications on the chain of causation and foreseeability. For instance, in the hypothetical scenarios discussed earlier, it might be determined as follows:

- where a doctor relies solely on the blurry images sent by a patient: In this instance, the "but for" test would imply that but for the doctor's use of blurry images, the wrong diagnosis causing harm may not have occurred. If the use of patient's images are standard practice, it is the patient themselves that may be said to have been responsible for or at least contributed to the error, mitigating liability.
- where a family doctor fails to pick emergency call: It could be considered that the stroke would have still occurred regardless even if there was a duty to attend to emergency calls in work hours³⁷¹ as the patient's family were not professionals;
- Technical glitch in telesurgery: If this occurred as a result of a defect in the equipment utilised or even availability of internet network connection which is not directly a fault of either surgeon, causation will not be established.

This shows that causation, which is already difficult to prove in negligence, might be even more difficult to prove in the use of telemedicine. In lower-income countries like Nigeria suffering a host of challenges from poor internet connectivity to woeful power supply, these scenarios may be more fact than fiction. To safeguard patients' rights, therefore, it is critical that they are well aware of the potential risks in telemedicine.

4.2. Patient Privacy and Confidentiality; Data Protection & Cybersecurity

4.2.1. Conventional Practice & Liability

Privacy and confidentiality have been essential principles in medical ethics throughout history, although they were not always explicitly referred to as such.³⁷² The concept of "privacy" can be traced back to the Latin words "*privatus*" and "*privo*," meaning to be separate from others, personal, not public, and secret.³⁷³ The concept has evolved over time, from the notion of

³⁷¹ The National Health Act establishes a duty for emergency admissions, not the scenario provided. Moreover, in *Bolitho*, no claim was established against Dr. Rodger who did not receive any notifications to attend to Patrick from Dr Horn due to her flat batteries.

³⁷² Agbasi, M. N. 2015. "Examination of The Principle of Confidentiality of Patients under Medical Law" *International Journal of Health and Medical Information*, 4(1).

³⁷³ Ildigwe, N. M., & Nwakoby, C. S. 2021. "Confidentiality in health care - Reflecting on the rights of COVID-19 patients." *Nigerian Journal of Law and Jurisprudence*, pp. 40-64.

<https://www.nigerianjournalonline.com/index.php/DJLJ/article/download/1631/1594>

personal secrets in ancient times to the idea of one's home as a sanctuary during the early modern period. The right to privacy was acknowledged by Sir Edward Coke in 1604 when he proclaimed, "*The house of every one is to him as his castle and fortress.*"³⁷⁴ In 1890, Warren and Brandeis defined privacy as "*the right to be let alone,*" a definition still referenced in modern works. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights, adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in 1948, recognized privacy as a fundamental human right, protecting individuals from arbitrary interference with their privacy, family, home, or correspondence.

The term "privacy" encompasses four distinct forms: physical privacy, informational privacy, proprietary privacy, and decisional privacy.³⁷⁵ Physical privacy refers to the desire for limited contact and the freedom to enjoy seclusion and solitude. Informational privacy entails protecting personal information and maintaining confidentiality. Proprietary privacy concerns the ownership and control of personal attributes, such as DNA. Decisional privacy encompasses the autonomous right to make personal choices and be free from unwanted interferences. In healthcare, decisional privacy relates to making important medical decisions and allocating scarce resources.³⁷⁶ Within the scope of this discourse, as with most modern connotations in the context of healthcare, the focus is on informational privacy. In today's digital age, privacy is often understood as the right to maintain control over personal information, including possessions, communications, and other private affairs.³⁷⁷ As a fundamental right, privacy is owed to a person by all persons who come in contact with them, including in healthcare. In other words, privacy does not need the existence of a relationship with another to exist.³⁷⁸

Legal framework protecting informational privacy of patients begins with the 1999 Constitution which guarantees the privacy of citizens, including the confidentiality of their medical information.³⁷⁹ The correspondence between a medical practitioner and their patient, concerning the patient's medical information, is protected under this constitutional provision. The Nigerian Data Protection Act of 2023 and Regulations of 2019 further recognises medical

³⁷⁴ Kayaalp M. 2018. Patient Privacy in the Era of Big Data. *Balkan Medical Journal*;35, pp.8-17
DOI:10.4274/balkanmedj.2017.0966

³⁷⁵ Op cit., Ilodigwe & Nwakoby

³⁷⁶ Ibid

³⁷⁷ Op cit., Kayaalp

³⁷⁸ Herring, J. 2018. *Medical Law and Ethics* 7th edition. Oxford University Press: London

³⁷⁹ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, s.37; *Digital Rights Lawyers Initiative (DRLI) v. National Identity Management Commission (NIMC)* (2021) LPELR-55623(CA)

information as personal data, imposing a duty of care on individuals entrusted with such information.³⁸⁰ The Child Rights Act 2003,³⁸¹ Freedom of Information Act 2011,³⁸² National Communications Commission Act,³⁸³ among others, also protects the rights of patients to privacy.

Confidentiality, on the other hand, more strictly applies to the medical professional/healthcare provider as it arises in certain fiduciary relationships like the doctor-patient relationship.³⁸⁴ Confidentiality is a crucial aspect of the patient-physician relationship, designed to ensure that patients feel comfortable disclosing their health information for adequate treatment.³⁸⁵ This duty, enshrined in the Hippocratic Oath and supported by legal frameworks, generally prohibits medical practitioners from disclosing patient information to third parties.³⁸⁶ The National Health Act 2014 mandates that all information about a person's health status, treatment, or stay in a health establishment is to remain confidential.³⁸⁷ The Code of Medical Ethics for Medical Practitioners reinforces the duty of confidentiality, stating that any information obtained by a practitioner during the patient-doctor relationship is considered privileged and must not be divulged to a third party.³⁸⁸ Breach of confidentiality can occur when sensitive information is not adequately protected by the recipient or when there is intentional disclosure and it is actionable under the law, with administrative and criminal penalty and liability in negligence/malpractice issuable if proven.³⁸⁹

Confidentiality is related to privacy as it encompasses a set of rules and obligations that restrict access to information of a private nature that is shared between a patient and their doctor. As stated by Lord Goff in the case of *Attorney General v. Guardian Newspaper (No. 2)*,³⁹⁰ a duty of confidence arises when a person becomes aware of confidential information and has either agreed or is deemed to have agreed to keep it confidential. In such circumstances, it is justifiable to prevent the disclosure of this information to others. While privacy and

³⁸⁰ NDPA 2023, section 34-35

³⁸¹ CRA 2003, section 8

³⁸² FOI 2011, section 14

³⁸³ NCCA, section 9-10

³⁸⁴ *Campbell v. MGN Ltd*

³⁸⁵ Ilodigwe, op cit.

³⁸⁶ Ilodigwe, op cit.

³⁸⁷ National Health Act 2014, s.26

³⁸⁸ Rule 8B and 9F

³⁸⁹ Liability for wrongful disclosure attracts a fine not less than ₦20,000 or imprisonment for a term of two years or both- NHA s.38(2).

³⁹⁰ [1990] 1 AC 109

confidentiality are related concepts, they differ as privacy empowers individuals with self-autonomy over their health information which is enforceable against the whole world, while confidentiality refers to the responsibility of those entrusted with private health information to keep it confidential and is enforceable only against the party with that obligation in an established relationship.

However, confidentiality is not absolute, and certain circumstances permit the disclosure of patient information. The National Health Act allows disclosure with the user's consent, court order, or in cases involving minors or individuals unable to give consent, at the request of a parent or guardian.³⁹¹ Additionally, disclosure may be warranted when non-disclosure poses a threat to public health.³⁹²

4.3.2. Impact of Telemedicine on Privacy and Confidentiality: Data Protection & Cybersecurity

The integration of ICT with health has significantly expanded the liability within conventional medical confidentiality even as the demand for patient data in the healthcare industry is growing rapidly. While technology companies on one hand seek access to electronic health records (EHR) to fuel advancements in medical artificial intelligence (AI) and health-focused products,³⁹³ malicious attackers target sensitive health data for criminal purposes.³⁹⁴ Hence, as commentators have noted, the challenges of maintaining confidentiality will only get worse, as new improvements in technology continue to affect medicine.³⁹⁵ Thus, data protection and cybersecurity measures play a crucial role in safeguarding the privacy of information and communication within the healthcare system.³⁹⁶ Fortunately, data protection in Nigeria can be asserted to be a well-regulated area of law with the enactment of the Data Protection Act 2023

³⁹¹ National Health Act 2014, s.26(2), see *Tarasoff v Regent of the University of California*, 551 P.2D 334 [1976]

³⁹² Ibid

³⁹³ Kaplan, B. (2020). Revisiting health information technology ethical, legal, and social issues and evaluation: Telehealth/telemedicine and COVID-19. *International Journal of Medical Informatics*, 143, 104239. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2020.104239>; Cohen, I. G., & Mello, M. M. (2019). Big Data, Big Tech, and Protecting Patient Privacy. *JAMA*. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2019.11365>

³⁹⁴ Jalali, S.M, Landmark, A., Gordon, W.J. 2021. "Telemedicine, privacy, and information security in the age of COVID-19". *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*, 28(3), pp.671–672, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jamia/ocaa310>

³⁹⁵ Agbasi, M. N. 2015. "Examination of The Principle of Confidentiality of Patients under Medical Law" *International Journal of Health and Medical Information*, 4(1).

³⁹⁶ Loi, M., Christen, M., Kleine, N. and Weber, K. (2019), "Cybersecurity in health – disentangling value tensions", *Journal of Information, Communication and Ethics in Society*, Vol. 17 No. 2, pp. 229-245. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JICES-12-2018-0095>

in addition to other sector-specific legislations that provide for strict duties and additional liability on doctors and healthcare organisations, reducing the patient's burden of proof in enforcing their privacy rights where a medical professional's negligence results in the leakage of confidential health information.

Confidentiality & Physician Liability

Essentially, the MDCN's Code of Ethics mandates medical practitioners to avoid medico-legal pitfalls in telemedicine, including in confidentiality.³⁹⁷ This means that in using telemedicine applications, the physician is still bound to the duty of protecting the patient's information. Furthermore, medical practitioners will come under the ambit of data processors within the Nigerian Data Protection Act as they collect patient data, implying that they are also bound by the extensive responsibilities and principles provided under the Act which significantly expands their liability.³⁹⁸ However, the medical professional may face challenges in ensuring state-of-the-art security for patient data as this is ordinarily not within their expected scope of knowledge, making them at increased risk of liability.³⁹⁹ Hence, even though medical practitioners often rely on the larger healthcare provider-organization or service provider for cybersecurity, they remain responsible for specifying and confirming requirements in an information security management system and following standard cybersecurity/digital safety protocols.⁴⁰⁰

Compliance with Data Protection Regulations

Telemedicine relies on various communication modes like video links, voice calls, and text messages, often facilitated by third-party clinical service applications.⁴⁰¹ At all these stages, patient data is collected and often stored on the Internet "cloud" or other computer storage devices to ensure continuity of care, giving rise to what are known as "electronic health

³⁹⁷ Code of Ethics, s.22

³⁹⁸ Nigerian Data Protection Act 2023, s.35(2) mandates data processors for instance to report data breaches when they occur. Moreover, they are bound by the principles and lawful basis of data processing provided in ss. 23-24.

³⁹⁹ Koeppel, D. (2020). Towards Guidelines for Medical Professionals to Ensure Cybersecurity in Digital Health Care. In M. Christen et al. (Eds.), *The Ethics of Cybersecurity* (pp. 331). The International Library of Ethics, Law and Technology 21. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-29053-5_17

⁴⁰⁰ Ibid

⁴⁰¹ Iqbal, Y., Tahir, S., Tahir, H., Khan, F., Saeed, S., Almuhaideb, A. M., & Syed, A. M. (2022). A novel homomorphic approach for preserving privacy of patient data in telemedicine. *Sensors*, 22(12), 4432. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22124432>

records". This automatically brings telemedicine under the statutory watch of the National Health Act 2014 and the Data Protection Act 2023. These will be examined below.

The National Health Act 2014 provides that the person in charge of a health establishment in possession of a user's health records is to set up control measures to prevent unauthorised access to those records or the computer system by which they are kept.⁴⁰² Failure to do this, as well as failure to create or change a record when required to do so, falsifying health records, or generally using a patient's health records inappropriately is a criminal offence for which a conviction of two-years imprisonment or fine of N250,000 or both.⁴⁰³ However, the Act fails to define a standard for the control measures for patient data protection, nor does it establish who is "the person in charge of a health establishment" especially where it is incorporated – although it may apply to the directors. Nonetheless, it is doubtful if this provision can indict healthcare providers, although it will definitely render cyberattackers criminally liable.

The Data Protection Act provides that where data is processed (and especially sensitive data), it must be based on established principles and lawful basis as set out in the Act.⁴⁰⁴ As such, novel obligations are imposed by the Act with regards to data protection assessments,⁴⁰⁵ implementing appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure the security, integrity, and confidentiality of personal data in its possession or under its control such as encryption, de-identification, periodic risk assessments, etc.,⁴⁰⁶ and appointment of data protection officers and registration with the Data Protection Commission if they are of major importance although this is not defined in the Act.⁴⁰⁷ Moreover, it outlines strict regulation of data transferred across borders, which protects health data in the event of cross-border telemedicine.⁴⁰⁸ Where any of these obligations are violated, the Act provides for administrative remedies through which a person with interests in such violations can be

⁴⁰² National Health Act, s.29(1)

⁴⁰³ Ibid, s.29(2)

⁴⁰⁴ Nigerian Data Protection Act, ss.19-28

⁴⁰⁵ Ibid, s.23

⁴⁰⁶ Ibid, s.34. A number of factors have to be considered, including (a) the amount and sensitivity of the personal data; (b) the nature, degree and likelihood of harm to a data subject that could result from the loss, disclosure, or other misuse of the personal data; (c) the extent of the processing; (d) the period of data retention; and (e) the availability and cost of any technologies, tools, or other measures to be implemented relative to the size of the data controller or data processor. This means that healthcare institutions will be placed on a higher standard due to the sensitivity of the data involved.

⁴⁰⁷ Ibid, s.27 & 39 respectively

⁴⁰⁸ Ibid, s.36

redressed.⁴⁰⁹ While the Act allows for the right of an aggrieved person to institute civil proceedings,⁴¹⁰ the provision regarding administrative remedies makes it possible for a protected person to obtain redress only because they are aggrieved by the decision, action, or inaction of a data controller or data processor in violation of the Act. This means that a patient does not have to prove that the violation caused them to suffer injury or loss; they only need to show that the violation occurred and that they have sufficient interests in the matter to be able to obtain an enforcement order which could include remedial action by the telemedicine provider, compensation if they have suffered harm, or remedial fee or penalty.⁴¹¹ By this, it extends the data protection of the patient using a telemedicine platform even before an actual data breach occurs.

Cyberattacks

Reports of cyberattacks of health data worldwide have been profound and on the rise, with an estimated 150 million patient health records breached between 2009 and 2014.⁴¹² In the United States, data breaches of healthcare records increased by 40.63% in February 2021.⁴¹³ The pertinent concern surrounding cyberattacks in healthcare extends beyond the sheer quantity of reported incidents. What makes these attacks even more alarming is the nature of the stolen property involved. Health data, being highly personal and irreplaceable, holds immense value.⁴¹⁴ Any breach or loss of such data not only results in financial harm but also inflicts significant damage to an individual's dignity, and unlike instances involving stolen credit cards or lost identification, the loss of one's health identity cannot be easily rectified or "reset."⁴¹⁵ Moreover, healthcare organisations possess large volumes of sensitive data, including payment information, patient histories, and private details, making them attractive targets.⁴¹⁶

⁴⁰⁹ Ibid, s.41(1)

⁴¹⁰ Ibid, s.46

⁴¹¹ Ibid, s.43. This penalty/fee ranges from a maximum of NGN 10 to 2 million depending on the size of the data controller or processor.

⁴¹² Bhuyan, S.S., Kabir, U., Escareno, J.M. et al. 2020. Transforming Healthcare Cybersecurity from Reactive to Proactive: Current Status and Future Recommendations. *Journal of Medical Systems*, 44, 98
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10916-019-1507-y>

⁴¹³ Cranford, L.. February 2021. Healthcare Data Breach Report. Retrieved from
<https://www.hipaajournal.com/february-2021-healthcare-data-breach-report/>

⁴¹⁴ Luh, F., & Yen, Y. (2020). Cybersecurity in Science and Medicine: Threats and Challenges. *Trends in Biotechnology*, 38(8), 825-828. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tibtech.2020.02.010>

⁴¹⁵ Ibid

⁴¹⁶ K. Abu Ali and S. Alyounis. 2021. CyberSecurity in Healthcare Industry. *International Conference on Information Technology (ICIT)*, Amman, Jordan, 2021, pp. 695-701,doi:10.1109/ICIT52682.2021.9491669.

Cybersecurity threats extend beyond privacy, endangering patient safety, such as vulnerabilities in wireless medical devices.⁴¹⁷

Healthcare organisations are vulnerable to various types of cyberattacks with severe consequences for patient privacy and safety.⁴¹⁸ Denial-of-Service (DoS) attacks overwhelm networks, hindering user access, as seen in the 2014 attack on Boston Children's Hospital.⁴¹⁹ Privilege escalation attacks exploit vulnerabilities to gain higher-level access and manipulate systems, posing a risk to patient safety⁴²⁰. Man-in-the-Middle (MITM) attacks compromise data integrity by intercepting communication between parties. Cryptographic attacks aim to decrypt encrypted information, while SQL injection attacks exploit website vulnerabilities to alter or extract database information.⁴²¹ Malicious software (malware) spreads through external drives or phishing emails, and phishing deceives individuals or organizations into revealing sensitive information. Spear-phishing specifically targets healthcare providers.⁴²²

With regards to cyberattacks of all forms, two liabilities can arise under Nigeria's legal framework. First, the primary and criminal liability rests on the cyberattackers, as provided by the Cybercrimes (Prevention and Prohibition) Act of 2015.⁴²³ This stringent criminalisation is necessary as the American Hospital Association emphasised that these attacks are not merely financial crimes but instead directly jeopardize a hospital's capacity to provide vital medical services.⁴²⁴ When hospitals detect cyberattacks on their systems, they often face the challenging decision of taking their entire network offline to mitigate further damage. This disruption disrupts regular workflow and necessitates a shift to paper-based systems for patient care, leading to extensive computer system and diagnostic device shutdowns and they may be compelled to delay surgeries and divert emergency department patients elsewhere.⁴²⁵ Consequently, hospitals' real-life incidents demonstrate the severe consequences of

⁴¹⁷ For example, over 750,000 patients world-wide use pacemakers that are at risk for sabotage, requiring Abbott Laboratories to issue a software patch for these devices in 2018. Swede, M. J., Scovetta, V., & Eugene-Colin, M. (2019). Protecting patient data is the new scope of practice: A recommended cybersecurity curricula for healthcare students to prepare for this challenge. *Journal of Allied Health*, 48(2), 148-156

⁴¹⁸ Luh & Yen, op cit.

⁴¹⁹ Bhuyan et al., op cit.

⁴²⁰ Ibid

⁴²¹ Ibid

⁴²² Ibid

⁴²³ Cybercrimes (Prevention and Prohibition) Act of 2015, s.29

⁴²⁴ Dameff, C., Pfeffer, M. A., & Longhurst, C. A. (2019). Cybersecurity implications for hospital quality. *Health Services Research*, 54(5), 969. <https://doi.org/10.1111%2F1475-6773.13202>

⁴²⁵ Ibid

cyberattacks on healthcare facilities. Tragically, in Germany, a woman lost her life when a hospital under a ransomware attack failed to provide critical care.⁴²⁶ This incident serves as a stark reminder of the significant impact cyberattacks can have on patient care and overall healthcare system functionality, and thus it is imperative to utilise all vital efforts to protect patients from these threats.

In addition, employee error and negligence and non-compliance with relevant regulations plays a substantial role in information security breaches.⁴²⁷ In the event where data breaches occur, healthcare providers including telemedicine platforms who control patient data are mandated to report the same to the Nigeria Data Protection Commission within three days with all relevant facts leading to the breach.⁴²⁸ They are also required to inform all who may be affected of the occurrence of the breach. The Commission can then in its discretion conduct an investigation to determine the extent to which the controllers and processors may be liable and issue administrative sanction if they are indeed found liable.⁴²⁹

4.3. Informed Consent

4.3.1. Conventional Liability

The Black's Law Dictionary defines informed consent in terms of an individual's agreement to a recommended medical procedure, having been fully informed about the associated risks and alternatives.⁴³⁰ Informed consent is a medico-legal doctrine based on respecting a patient's autonomy and their right to make decisions regarding their own body.⁴³¹ The acknowledgment of a patient's right to provide consent to medical treatment is of utmost importance globally within the medical profession and serves as the authority for any form of treatment or procedure

⁴²⁶ Ibid; Iqbal, op cit.

⁴²⁷ Swede, M. J., Scovetta, V., & Eugene-Colin, M. (2019). Protecting patient data is the new scope of practice: A recommended cybersecurity curricula for healthcare students to prepare for this challenge. *Journal of Allied Health*, 48(2), 148-156

⁴²⁸ Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, s.35

⁴²⁹ Ibid, s.41(2); 42-43

⁴³⁰ Black Law's Dictionary, 2nd Ed.

⁴³¹ Okeke, H. (2023). Critical Review Of Nigerian Health Laws: Making A Case For Legal Framework On Patient Safety In Nigeria. *Cavendish University Law Journal* 2.

to be administered.⁴³² The National Health Act 2014 and Code of Medical Ethics provide a statutory basis for informed consent in Nigeria.⁴³³

The significance of informed consent in the United Kingdom was highlighted in the influential Bolam case in 1957, which shifted medical practice away from paternalism towards embracing the concept of informed consent.⁴³⁴ In Nigeria, the Supreme Court recognised the importance of consent in the case of *Medical and Dental Practitioners Disciplinary Tribunal v Okonkwo*⁴³⁵ as follows:

"The patient's consent is paramount...the patient's relationship with a doctor is based on consensus,... the choice of an adult patient with a sound mind to refuse informed consent to medical treatment, barring state intervention through judicial process, leaves the practitioner helpless to impose a treatment on the patient."

In that case, Mrs. Okorie was a patient under the care of the respondent at a hospital. During her time there, she explicitly refused to receive a blood transfusion or any other form of bloody material into her body. She even signed a document stating her firm decision that under no circumstances should blood be transfused to her. It's important to note that she had already expressed the same wishes at a previous hospital before being transferred to the respondent's care. Respecting Mrs. Okorie's wishes, the respondent honored her undertaking and did not administer a blood transfusion. Tragically, Mrs. Okorie passed away subsequently. Following her death, the deceased's mother and uncle filed a complaint against the respondent with the Medical and Dental Practitioners' Tribunal. The tribunal found the respondent guilty of negligence for not providing adequate treatment. However, the apex court recognized the fundamental right of an individual to refuse medical treatment in the specific case being considered. As a result, the court acquitted Mr. Okonkwo of charges of professional misconduct and negligence brought against him by the Medical and Dental Practitioners' Disciplinary Tribunal.

⁴³² ARINZE-UMOBI & OKEKE. 2020. A Review Of Socio-Cultural Factors Affecting Patients' Right To Informed Consent And Autonomy In Medical Practice In Nigeria. *AJLHR* 4 (1), p.125..

⁴³³ Section 23 of NHA

⁴³⁴ Okeke, op cit.

⁴³⁵ (2001) 3 SC 76

In medical cases, the standard of consent required is particularly high, comparable to the consent required by international human rights instruments concerning indigenous rights.⁴³⁶ There are three key elements for informed consent to be established: it must be free, prior, and informed.⁴³⁷ The element of freedom implies that consent is invalid if obtained through manipulation or coercion. Involuntary consent obtained under duress or coercion may lead to legal action for battery. Moreover, the consent must be willingly given by a legally competent patient. The aspect of prior consent necessitates seeking consent well in advance of any authorization by medical or hospital authorities or the commencement of activities that may impact the patient's health. Furthermore, informed consent entails the provision of comprehensive and accurate information about the proposed medical procedure. This disclosure must be accessible and understandable to the patient, encompassing details such as the nature, scope, duration, potential risks, and foreseeable implications of the procedure.⁴³⁸ The physician is responsible for furnishing all necessary information regarding the treatment, its benefits, associated risks, complications, and consequences to be expected.⁴³⁹

Failure to obtain informed consent can result in liability for assault or negligence. In the case of *Okekearu v. Tanko*,⁴⁴⁰ a medical doctor performed an amputation on the left center finger of a 14-year-old boy without obtaining his consent. The boy subsequently filed a lawsuit seeking damages for battery, claiming that the doctor had acted without his permission. In his defense, the doctor argued that he had obtained consent from the plaintiff's aunt, who was the closest relative present at the time of the procedure. However, the trial court ruled in favor of the plaintiff, finding the doctor liable for battery, negligence, and permanent incapacity resulting from the finger amputation. As a result, the court awarded the plaintiff the sum of N100,000 as general damages.

As observed in the above case, challenges may arise when dealing with temporarily unconscious or mentally incapacitated patients, as well as children, requiring the consent of

⁴³⁶ Gbobo, P. I., & Oke-Chinda, M. (2018). An Analysis of the Doctrine of Informed Consent in Nigeria's Health Care Services. *Journal of Law, Policy and Globalization*, 69.

⁴³⁷ Ibid

⁴³⁸ National Health Act, s.23. In the case of *Sidaway v. Board of Governors Bethlehem Royal Hospital*, a patient successfully brought an action against her doctor claiming that he failed to warn her about some inherent hazards in a form of treatment which the doctor proposed and applied to her. The same was also invoked in *Chester v Afshar* [2004] UKHL 41

⁴³⁹ Ibid. Thus, Herring, op.cit., p.129 posited that the Bolam test does not apply in cases requiring informed consent.

⁴⁴⁰ (2002) LPELR-SC 73/1998

their next of kin, guardians, or parents to make decisions on their behalf. That is because competence and cognitive capacity plays a crucial role in informed consent as it is hinged on a person's ability to apply rational thinking and make critical decisions.⁴⁴¹

In situations where patients are unconscious, the Doctrine of Necessity comes into play.⁴⁴² The Doctrine of Necessity provides legitimacy to necessary acts performed to preserve human life, protecting physicians from criminal liability for non-consensual treatment.⁴⁴³ However, it is crucial for physicians to avoid taking advantage of an unconscious patient by performing procedures beyond what is immediately necessary to save their life. Canadian cases have established a distinction between procedures justified by necessity and those performed for mere convenience. In the case of *Marshall v Curry*,⁴⁴⁴ the surgeon successfully defended against a battery claim for removing a testicle during a hernia operation. The court deemed the action necessary at that point. On the other hand, in *Murray v Mc Murdy*,⁴⁴⁵ the surgeon sterilised a female patient without her consent during a caesarian section. The court ruled in favour of battery since sterilisation was not crucial for the patient's immediate survival. Therefore, obtaining valid consent is essential for invasive procedures or treatments to avoid civil and criminal liability as battery has both criminal and civil connotations, in addition to being a violation of a patient's right to dignity.

When it comes to children, parents are generally considered capable of making informed decisions for their children, as they bear the long-term consequences of such choices.⁴⁴⁶ It is important to consider the best interests of the child when making medical decisions. Factors such as improving the child's condition, preventing further deterioration, weighing the benefits against the risks, and exploring less invasive treatments should be taken into account.⁴⁴⁷ While parents generally make decisions for their children's well-being, this authority is not absolute and can be challenged in specific cases.⁴⁴⁸ However, the ability to give consent is not solely

⁴⁴¹ Arinze-Umobi, CN. 2021. The Legal Basis for Determining Patients' Decision-Making Capacity in Medical Practice in Nigeria. *UNIZIK Journal of Public and Private Law*, 11, p.142.

⁴⁴² Gbogbo & Oke-Chinda, op cit, p.73.

⁴⁴³ Ibid

⁴⁴⁴ (1933) 3 D.L.R. 260

⁴⁴⁵ (1949) 2 D.L.R. 442

⁴⁴⁶ Arinze-Umobi, op cit., p.144

⁴⁴⁷ Ibid

⁴⁴⁸ *Re Gillick* [1986]. The test proposed by Lord Scarman posits that a minor will be able to consent to treatment if they demonstrate "sufficient understanding and intelligence to understand fully what is proposed" ([1986] AC 112, 187[D]).

based on the statutory age of majority as legal children can provide valid consent if they are fully informed and understand the implications of the treatment or procedure, known as mature minors.⁴⁴⁹ This principle was established in *Re Ernestine Gregory*. In this case, a 17-year-old Jehovah's Witness with leukemia refused a blood transfusion, and the court recognized his capacity to make that decision, upholding his right to self-determination.

Mentally incapacitated individuals may be unable to give informed consent due to mental illness or impairment, including dementia resulting from age-related degenerative processes. In such cases, the individual's capacity to understand and consent to treatment is compromised. Currently, the newly passed National Mental Health Act 2021 makes provisions for consent of patients with mental health conditions. Generally, treatment requires prior written consent given voluntarily after receiving relevant information about their health and treatment options.⁴⁵⁰ The information must be provided in a language they understand, considering their literacy level, and supported decision-making should be provided at no cost if needed. However, admission may be secured involuntarily if there is a risk of imminent harm or severe deterioration in their condition that can only be addressed through facility admission, and on the application of specific persons such as spouses, parents, medical doctors, and legal authorities.⁴⁵¹

4.3.2. Implications of Telemedicine on Liability in Informed Consent

Generally, the standard for informed consent in telemedicine is generally the same as the conventional practice, only that telemedicine presents a unique context.⁴⁵² This raises issues such as whether liability can arise where a patient refuses to make use of telemedicine platforms even where this is necessary, whether the consent of children or mentally incapacitated persons operating telemedicine applications under the anonymity of the Internet is valid, and the issue of language barriers in communicating risks associated with telemedicine. These are discussed below:

Refusal to Accept Treatment via Telemedicine Where this is Critical

⁴⁴⁹ *Re Gillick, Supra.*

⁴⁵⁰ National Mental Health Act 2021, s.26

⁴⁵¹ *Ibid*, s.28

⁴⁵² Kamara et al., op cit.

Telemedicine has been proposed as an intervention in rural areas where the access to healthcare may be a significant hurdle. In instances where it is critical to use a telemedicine platform to receive healthcare and the patient refuses to use such, what would be the legal implication? Will the telemedicine provider or perhaps a medical professional who had previously established a relationship with the patient be compellable to act in some way? The following cases are instructive in that light.

The general rule was established *Randolph v. City of New York*⁴⁵³ where it was held that "*a patient has a right to determine his own medical treatment and that right is superior to the physician's duty to provide necessary care*". In the case of *Airedale NHS Trust v Bland*,⁴⁵⁴ the court made a significant ruling regarding a patient's right to refuse treatment, even if it is life-saving. The court stated that if a patient is capable of making a decision about whether to undergo treatment and chooses to refuse it, their decision must be respected, even if it goes against their best interests. Another notable case, *Schloendorff v New York Hospital*,⁴⁵⁵ involved a woman who allowed her physician to administer anesthesia to determine if a diagnosed fibroid tumor was malignant. However, without her consent, the physician proceeded to remove the tumor while she was under the influence of the anesthesia. The court, led by Cardozo J, held that every adult of sound mind has the right to determine what happens to their own body. Performing an operation without the patient's consent is considered assault and can result in liability for damages. In telemedicine, this can extend to telesurgery.

On the other hand, the right to self-determination may be set aside in cases of overriding public interest. In *Esabunor v Faweya*,⁴⁵⁶ for instance, the appellant withheld consent to transfuse her child with blood based on religious grounds (being a Jehovah's Witness). The Commissioner of Police obtained a court order to transfuse the child with blood, arguing that the child's right to life outweighed the appellant's right to determine the fate of the child. While this ruling may raise concerns about violating the appellant's rights as a guardian and freedom of religion and association, it can be argued that the paramount interest is to protect the child's right to life.

⁴⁵³ 501 NYS 2d 837, 841 (App. Div. 1986)

⁴⁵⁴ [1993] AC 789

⁴⁵⁵ 92 NY 1914

⁴⁵⁶ (2019) LPELR-46961 (SC)

Similarly, in *Re S (Adult Refusal of Medical Treatment)*,⁴⁵⁷ the state's overriding interest in preserving lives takes precedence, regardless of an individual's religious beliefs or doctrines. In this case, a pregnant Nigerian woman in England was in labor, but due to complications with the baby's position, a cesarean section was necessary to save both the baby's and the mother's lives. However, the defendant and her husband, claiming to be "Born Again Christians," refused to give their consent. The hospital sought a court order from the president of the Family Court Division to proceed with the cesarean section, and the court granted the order, considering the best interest of the unborn child and the public as a whole.

In summary, these cases highlight the complex balance between an individual's right to autonomy and the state's obligation to protect and preserve life. While the right to refuse treatment is generally respected, there are instances where public interest and the welfare of others, particularly vulnerable individuals, may supersede individual preferences and religious beliefs. However, it is doubtful that these exceptions are applicable in telemedicine due to the distance between the healthcare provider and the patient.

Consent of Children/Mentally Incapacitated Adults

Under the cover of a mobile screen, it is possible for underage children to register on telemedicine platforms as has occurred with other applications such as social media. The question therefore would be: will their consent be valid? It is most likely that the existing principles regarding the matured minor will be applicable. With regards to consent to the use of their personal data and health information, nonetheless, the provisions of the Nigerian Data Protection Act 2023 will come into play. **Section 26(1)** provides that Data controllers must obtain consent from a parent or legal guardian when processing personal data of a child or someone lacking legal capacity to consent, nonetheless, where it is necessary for the vital interests or social care, consent given by a child aged 13 or older for electronic information and services will be valid. This means that for the purpose of data protection in telemedicine, the consent of children over 13 is permitted. The Act further requires data controllers to use appropriate mechanisms to verify age of data subjects, such as government-approved identification documents.⁴⁵⁸

⁴⁵⁷ (1992) All. ER

⁴⁵⁸ Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, s.26(2)&(3)

Language barriers

Empirical evidence suggests that language barriers have a direct impact on healthcare delivery.⁴⁵⁹ This issue becomes even more pronounced in the context of telemedicine, where patients who do not understand the language used by doctors may face challenges in comprehending medical advice and instructions. As a result, patients who cannot communicate effectively with their telemedicine providers are more likely to experience difficulties in adhering to prescribed medications and may be more prone to missing appointments compared to those who can communicate fluently in the same language.⁴⁶⁰ Taking into account the fact that law does not compel the impossible, medical professionals may be absolved of liability if they are unable to fully provide necessary information due to language barriers so long as they take reasonable measures.

4.4. Licensure and Professional Regulation

4.4.1. Conventional Practice & Liability

The Medical and Dental Council of Nigeria (MDCN) is the authorised government agency responsible for regulating and overseeing the practice of medicine and dentistry in Nigeria.⁴⁶¹ Operating under the authority of the Medical and Dental Practitioners Act, the MDCN plays a crucial role in ensuring the quality and integrity of healthcare services in the country. One of the primary responsibilities of the MDCN is to establish and periodically review the standards of knowledge and skill required for individuals aspiring to become members of the medical or dental profession.⁴⁶² By setting these standards, the MDCN ensures that healthcare practitioners possess the necessary qualifications and competencies to provide safe and effective care to patients. In addition to setting standards, the MDCN also maintains a register of qualified practitioners who are entitled to practice medicine or dentistry. This register serves as a comprehensive database of licensed professionals and is regularly updated to reflect any changes or additions.⁴⁶³ By publishing updated lists of registered professionals, the MDCN

⁴⁵⁹ Jack, C., Hlombe, Y., & Mars, M. (2014). Language, cultural brokerage and informed consent - Will technological terms impede telemedicine use? *South African Journal of Bioethics and Law*, 7(1), 14-18.

⁴⁶⁰ Odhiambo, R., & Mars, M. (2018). Patients' understanding of telemedicine terms required for informed consent when translated into Kiswahili. *BMC Public Health*, 18, 588. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-018-5499-1>

⁴⁶¹ Established under the Medical and Dental Practitioners Act 1988

⁴⁶² Medical and Dental Practitioners Act, s.1

⁴⁶³ *Ibid*, s.6

enables patients and the public to verify the credentials of healthcare practitioners and make informed decisions about their healthcare providers.

The MDCN further plays a vital role in formulating a code of conduct for medical and dental professionals in Nigeria.⁴⁶⁴ This code of conduct outlines the expected ethical and professional behavior for practitioners and serves as a guiding framework for their interactions with colleagues, patients, allied professionals, and the public. It covers various aspects of professional practice, including confidentiality, patient care, communication, and integrity. The code of conduct is periodically reviewed and revised to ensure its relevance and alignment with evolving healthcare practices.⁴⁶⁵

To enforce the code of conduct, the MDCN has established bodies such as the Medical and Dental Practitioners Investigating Panel and the Medical and Dental Practitioners Disciplinary Tribunal.⁴⁶⁶ These bodies are responsible for investigating complaints of medical negligence or malpractice and taking appropriate disciplinary actions when necessary. If a practitioner is found guilty, the MDCN can issue reprimands, suspend their license to practice, or even revoke their license, depending on the severity of the misconduct.⁴⁶⁷ Complaints regarding medical negligence or malpractice are required to be reported to the MDCN, which serves as a central point for addressing professional misconduct within the medical and dental fields. This centralised reporting system ensures that complaints are properly documented, investigated, and resolved in a fair and transparent manner.⁴⁶⁸

Recognising the significance of the code of conduct, the MDCN emphasises its importance by providing every newly qualified medical and dental professional with a copy of the code during their swearing-in ceremony. This symbolic gesture reinforces the commitment of healthcare practitioners to uphold the principles and values mandated by the MDCN, thereby fostering professionalism and ethical practice throughout the medical and dental professions in Nigeria.⁴⁶⁹

⁴⁶⁴ Ibid, s.1

⁴⁶⁵ Ibid

⁴⁶⁶ Ibid, s.15

⁴⁶⁷ Ibid, s.15-16

⁴⁶⁸ Ibid, s.16

⁴⁶⁹ Oreh, A. 2017. Medical Regulation in Nigeria - Current situation and Recommendations. Technical Report. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/345985327>

What then are the existing requirements for licensure as a medical professional in Nigeria? The **Medical and Dental Practitioners Act 1998** provides for two stages: first, provisional registration and full licensure.⁴⁷⁰ To be fully registered, a person must possess a qualification approved by the Medical and Dental Council and hold a certificate of experience issued under **Section 11** of the Act. This certificate is granted to doctors after completing one year of compulsory housemanship or a specified period as determined by the Council. The Act also stipulates that the Council will only recognize qualifications from institutions that are appropriately established and equipped for medical training. Before obtaining full registration, individuals with recognized medical or dental degrees from universities may be granted provisional registration, allowing them to practice while undergoing the mandatory housemanship training.

Under **Section 13 of the Act**, the Council has the discretion to grant limited registration to foreign-trained individuals employed in approved hospitals or institutions in Nigeria as doctors, provided they intend to be in the country for a limited period. Limited registration may also be granted to doctors who have obtained qualifications outside Nigeria, as long as they pass the Council's assessment examination. Limited registration terminates either at the time specified by the Council or when the doctor's employment ceases. The Council has the final authority to determine whether the termination of employment should result in the withdrawal of limited registration, and its decision is final. They are generally not permitted to manage public hospitals except it is part of their employment agreement. Limited registered doctors remain liable for their actions and omissions during their employment as doctors, although they do not enjoy the full privileges and status of fully registered doctors, such as being Council members.

4.4.2. Impact of Telemedicine on Regulation and Licensure Liabilities

Fraudulent Representation/Cyber torts

With regards to the impact of telemedicine on regulation and licensure of physicians, a difficulty that might arise is the issue of fraudulent representation by ill-meaning persons as medical practitioners, especially where the service is being delivered through a virtual application or platform which hosts several private doctors as a result of the anonymity of telemedicine provides. These fraudsters might even take advantage of this to write and

⁴⁷⁰ Medical and Dental Practitioners Act 1998, s.1(2)(a),8,9,10,

distribute fake prescriptions which can be dangerous and cause serious harm to patients, particularly if they are being used to treat serious health conditions.⁴⁷¹ They may also use the opportunity to obtain patients' information, and further bill them fraudulently.⁴⁷² Apart from these persons, doctors with partial license or provisional registration may also be tempted to render services on such platforms where financial incentives are promised, away from the watchful eyes of the professional regulatory body, although in Nigeria they are barred from private practice. Even fully registered medical practitioners may also face the temptation of engaging in varying species of fraud given that they are shielded from the watchful eyes of professional regulatory bodies on such platforms.

An illustration can be highlighted from the United States. On Wednesday, May 26, 2021, the United States' Department of Justice (DOJ) announced that it had taken legal action against 14 individuals, including telehealth executives and physicians, in relation to healthcare fraud schemes that exploited the COVID-19 pandemic. These schemes are alleged to have resulted in over \$143 million in false billings from orchestrated schemes with the purpose of defrauding beneficiaries and exploiting federal healthcare programs. One of the specific allegations was that multiple defendants had offered COVID-19 tests to Medicare beneficiaries in various locations. The objective behind this was to entice the beneficiaries to provide their personal identifying information along with saliva or blood samples. It was further alleged that the defendants had misused the obtained information and samples to submit claims to Medicare for laboratory tests that were unrelated, medically unnecessary, and significantly more expensive. According to the DOJ, there were instances where the COVID-19 test results were either not delivered to the beneficiaries in a timely manner or were unreliable, posing a risk of further disease transmission.⁴⁷³

How then might these impact liability? Already, **Section 17(1)** of the **Medical and Dental Practitioners Act** provides that:

Subject to subsections (6) and (7) of this section, if any person who is not a registered medical practitioner –
(a) for or in expectation of reward, practices or holds himself out to practice as a

⁴⁷¹ Singh, A. (2023, May 10). Telemedicine and the Digital Era – A Potent Mixture for Medical Fraud? KnowLaw. Retrieved from <https://knowlaw.in/index.php/2023/05/10/telemedicine-and-the-digital-era-potent-mixture-for-medical-fraud/>

⁴⁷² Ibid

⁴⁷³ <https://www.justice.gov/opa/pr/doj-announces-coordinated-law-enforcement-action-combat-health-care-fraud-related-covid-19>

medical practitioner; or
(b) takes or uses the title of physician, surgeon, doctor or licentiate of medicine, medical practitioner or apothecary; or
(d) without reasonable excuse takes or uses any name, title addition or description implying that he is authorized by law to practice as a medical practitioner.
He shall be guilty of an offence.

However, an individual found guilty of an offense under this provision may only face a maximum fine of N5,000.00 upon summary conviction, or a maximum fine of N10,000.00, imprisonment for up to five years, or both upon conviction or indictment. This appears to be grossly an inadequate liability to deter offenders in the modern era as the value of the naira has fallen significantly. It is therefore necessary that this section is reevaluated to safeguard patients in the light of advancements in technology. Apart from the individual who may fraudulently pose himself as a licensed medical practitioner, MDCN's guidelines reveal that employers who hire unlicensed doctors can be held criminally liable in pursuance of **Section 17** of the **MDCN Act**. It is the responsibility of employers to ensure that the doctors they employ are registered and licensed by the Council, regardless of nationality or place of employment within Nigeria.⁴⁷⁴ The wordings of this suggest strict liability therefore on a telemedicine provider (whether a hospital or not) that hire unlicensed persons, whether they are at fault or not. However, a telemedicine provider may claim that a contract of employment does not exist but that these physicians are merely independent contractors. Such claims would be examined in detail in this chapter under vicarious liability.

Cross-border Telemedicine

In existing practice, medical professionals trained, registered, and licensed in Nigeria are allowed to render services anywhere in the country.⁴⁷⁵ However, Nigerians increasingly frequent healthcare in foreign countries such as India, UK, and US as the country's own healthcare system deteriorates, resulting in the loss of billions of naira annually.⁴⁷⁶ With the advent of telemedicine, advocates including Nigeria's former ICT Minister, Isa Pantami, have stated that telemedicine would eliminate the need for travels as people will be able *"to book appointments, receive medical advice or recommendation and consult with physicians and other healthcare practitioners from the comfort of their homes, offices schools and*

⁴⁷⁴ <https://www.mdcnigeria.org/information-desk/licencing/>

⁴⁷⁵ Medical and Dental Practitioners Act, s.14

⁴⁷⁶ Makinde O. A. (2016). Physicians as medical tourism facilitators in Nigeria: ethical issues of the practice. Croatian medical journal, 57(6), 601–604. <https://doi.org/10.3325/cmj.2016.57.601>

localities".⁴⁷⁷ Therefore, telemedicine might soon become the new face of medical tourism, with patients in Nigeria being able to consult with medical professionals outside the country.

While this may be good news, there are important legal issues which may need to be considered. Medical tourism is recognised as a right under the **National Health Act 2014**,⁴⁷⁸ where it provides that "*without prejudice to the rights of any Nigerian to seek medical check-up, investigation or treatment anywhere within and outside Nigeria, no public officer of the government of the federation or any part thereof shall be sponsored for medical check-up*" (Emphasis mine). This was further given judicial attention in *Shehu V Afere*,⁴⁷⁹ where the court recognised the rights of Nigerian citizens to seek medical treatment anywhere in the world if they can afford it. Nonetheless, in the case of telemedicine practice, unlike in standard medical practice where patients will be traveling the country to a different jurisdiction, these patients instead may receive medical services from foreign professionals who are not registered or licensed to practice in Nigeria. The question that will then be raised is: will foreign medical professionals who establish a patient-doctor relationship with clients in Nigeria, as well as the telemedicine providers who hire their services, be liable for non-licensing?

On the surface, it appears that they might be, although it is evident that the emergence of telemedicine was not considered at the time the **Medical and Dental Practitioners Act** was enacted. However, the **Code of Medical Ethics** in **Section 22** highlights that:

"It is of ethical significance for registered practitioners to continuously assess and avoid medico-legal pitfalls in areas such as confidentiality, professional competence, *legal and registration status of the specialist being consulted*." (Emphasis Mine).

This, therefore, means that the standard of liability with regards to registration of medical professionals remains unchanged in telemedicine in Nigeria. On one hand, this ensures that patients' safety is held in highest regard, while on the other, it may present an obstacle as the requirement for "limited" registration of foreign-trained professionals is a rigorous process. It is suggested that the MDCN looks to ease the process using the discretionary powers granted them under the MDPA in order to facilitate speedy registration of certified foreign medical professionals who telemedicine providers might wish to hire.

⁴⁷⁷ <https://guardian.ng/technology/fg-unveils-nigcomsat-virtual-hospital-to-reduce-medical-tourism/>

⁴⁷⁸ National Health Act, s.46

⁴⁷⁹ (1998) 7 NWLR PT 556

4.5. Determination of Who is Liable in Telemedicine

4.5.1. Vicarious Liability of Hospitals/Telemedicine Providers

The legal principle of vicarious liability imposes a form of indirect liability on employers for the negligent actions of their employees when those actions occur within the scope of their employment.⁴⁸⁰ This doctrine holds employers accountable for the negligent acts committed by their employees, ensuring that there is a financially capable party to provide appropriate compensation to an injured individual. In *Jones v. Manchester Corporation*⁴⁸¹ Lord Denning established that when a master employs a servant to act on their behalf, they are responsible for the servant's conduct as if it were their own. If the servant commits a tort while acting within the scope of their employment, both the servant and the master are considered tortfeasors. This was affirmed by the Supreme Court case of *Iyere v. B.F. & F.M. Ltd.*⁴⁸² Within healthcare, the principle was notably applied in *Cassidy v. Ministry of Health*⁴⁸³ as well as the majority of Nigerian medical law cases.

To establish vicarious liability, the claimant must demonstrate that the employee committed a wrongful act or omission, the existence of an employer/employee relationship, indicating that the employee was working under the authority and control of the employer, and that the employee acted within the course of employment when committing the wrongful act or omission, meaning the actions were performed within the boundaries of their job responsibilities and the employer's interests.⁴⁸⁴

Section 22 of the National Health Act 2014 has provided for a limited vicarious liability of health establishments when it provides that:

“Subject to not being found negligent, a health care provider or other officers or employees of a health care establishment shall be indemnified out of the assets of the health care establishment against any liability incurred by him in defending any proceeding, whether civil or criminal in which judgement is given in his favour or is acquitted, if any such proceeding is brought against him in his capacity as a health care provider, an officer or employee of a health care establishment.” (Emphasis mine).

⁴⁸⁰ Adejumo & Adejumo (2020) op cit.

⁴⁸¹ (1952) 2 QB 852 at 870

⁴⁸² [2001]7 NWLR (pt.711)76. Similarly, in *Sharon Paint & Chemical Co. Ltd v Ezenwa* [2001] FWLR (pt.43) 290 at 312 the court held that vicarious liability is an indirect legal responsibility, such as the liability of an employer for the act of an employee, or a principal for torts of an agent.; *Nduka v Ezenwaku* (2006) 6 NWLR (pt.809) 494

⁴⁸³ Supra

⁴⁸⁴ *Ifeanyichukwu v Soleh Boneh Ltd*

This means that the Act has significantly protected hospitals or telemedicine providers from being liable for the negligent actions of their employees. Nonetheless, it is not clear if this will entirely disregard tortious rules, even though statutory law generally prevails over English law.⁴⁸⁵ Another issue raised within the context of telemedicine, especially where the telemedicine providers are not directly in liaison with hospitals and allow private practitioners to provide care, is whether or not they can be regarded as employees of the telemedicine provider. To determine this, recourse would have to be made to the tests which have been applied in tort cases, namely, the control test, which questions how much control the employer has over the manner in which the work was done,⁴⁸⁶ the organisation test, which takes into consideration the nature of the employment and if it is such that is critical to the operation of the organisation,⁴⁸⁷ and the multiple test which differentiates between contract of service and contract for service.⁴⁸⁸ Nonetheless, the current English approach is an expansive one that focuses less on whether or not an employment relationship exists but whether the contract is akin enough to employment that it will be just and reasonable to impose vicarious liability on the employer.⁴⁸⁹ However, the conclusive proof for the existence of employment in Nigeria remains the employment contract as observed in *Iyere v. B.F. & F.M. Ltd.*⁴⁹⁰ Therefore, each telemedicine provider will need to negotiate with medical professionals whether they wish to undertake an employment or independent contractor contract.

4.5.2. Third-party Intermediary Liability

Telemedicine brings into fore the possibility for liability of persons who may not technically be part of the healthcare ecosystem, such as the complex range of corporate bodies and highly skilled personnel involved in the development and service of the ICT infrastructure used for telemedicine, telecommunications providers, as well as external cybersecurity providers. These parties may be liable under data protection and product defects.

Data Protection Liability

⁴⁸⁵ Interpretation Act, s.48

⁴⁸⁶ *Union Bank Nig. Ltd v Ajagu* (1990)1 NWLR 328 at 343. However, this has been noted to be inapplicable where skill is required as the medical profession.

⁴⁸⁷ *Carmichael vs. National Power* (2001); *Stevenson, Jordan and Harrison Ltd v MacDonald and Evans* (1952)1 TLR 101, Lord Denning L.J

⁴⁸⁸ *Performing Right Society Ltd v Mitchell & Broker* (1924)1 KB 762 at 767, per McCredie J

⁴⁸⁹ *Cox v Ministry of Justice* [2016]UKSC10

⁴⁹⁰ *Supra*

Section 48 of the Nigerian Data Protection Act 2023 provides that where a body corporate or firm commits an offence under the Act, both the body corporate or firm itself and its principal officers are considered culpable, unless the principal officers can prove that they did not consent to or connive in the commission of the offense, and that they took reasonable measures to prevent the commission of the offence. Failure to prove this would render its principal officers who include the directors and secretaries⁴⁹¹ jointly liable. In addition, a data controller and data processor are held vicariously liable for the actions or failures of their agents or employees in relation to their business activities. As such, skilled personnel deployed by these persons may be primarily liable even though liability would pass to their employer/principal.

Product liability

Where a defect in the platform infrastructure leads to a medical error or perhaps security breach, the "manufacturer", in this case the persons involved in the manufacture, would be strictly liable as provided under the FCCPA 2018.⁴⁹² Moreover, the medical doctor or telemedicine provider may sue them for negligence if it applies. Where both the defect in the product and negligence of the medical practitioner or telemedicine provider results in an injury to the patient, they may be severally liable or both jointly and severally liable depending on the roles they played in the incident. On the positive side, this expands the scope of liability, meaning that there might be an increased chance of patients to successfully obtain remedy given that a wider scope of actors are involved that are capable of being sued and providing adequate compensation.

⁴⁹¹ Companies and Allied Matters Act (CAMA) 2020, s.868

⁴⁹² FCCPA 2018, s.134-140

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Conclusion

Access to quality healthcare is crucial for ensuring a good quality of life and promoting sustainable development. While the right to life has long been acknowledged as a fundamental human right, realizing this right requires good health, making access to quality healthcare increasingly relevant in both human rights discussions and the pursuit of sustainable development. However, in developing countries like Nigeria, access to quality healthcare remains a significant challenge.

Telemedicine has emerged as a promising intervention in improving healthcare access, particularly in low-resource settings like Nigeria. Telemedicine involves the delivery of healthcare services using information and communication technologies (ICT), allowing healthcare professionals to exchange accurate medical information and provide diagnosis, prevention, and treatment of diseases and injuries. It surpasses geographical barriers, enabling the provision of healthcare services regardless of distance. By utilising telecommunication technologies, telemedicine enhances access to healthcare, reduces inefficiencies in the healthcare system, and improves the quality of care. It promotes collaboration among healthcare professionals, facilitates knowledge sharing, and enhances patient outcomes. Patients can directly access doctors, even from remote locations, enabling second opinions and consultations without the need for travel. This is especially valuable in rural areas and countries with limited healthcare infrastructure. Telemedicine also plays a vital role in preventive medicine and chronic disease management by offering convenient telemonitoring options and reducing hospitalization costs. Moreover, it improves patient safety by reducing errors related to illegible prescriptions and provides opportunities for patient empowerment and education. Overall, telemedicine significantly contributes to improving health outcomes, patient satisfaction, and the efficiency of healthcare delivery, making it a valuable tool in modern healthcare practices.

The emergence of telemedicine in Nigeria has the potential to revolutionize healthcare delivery and improve access to quality healthcare. However, along with its benefits, telemedicine also

presents ethical and legal challenges that need to be addressed. The integration of technology and healthcare expands the stakeholders involved in telemedicine to include intermediary telemedicine providers, necessitating an examination of the legal implications surrounding telemedicine in Nigeria. One of the key concerns is the potential liability arising from the use of information technology and the delivery of healthcare services through telemedicine. Providers may face liability if patients suffer harm due to negligence, miscommunication, misdiagnosis, software malfunctions, or other technological risks. This encompasses various aspects, such as the patient-physician relationship, medical malpractice, patient privacy and confidentiality, licensure, informed consent, standards and quality of care, cybersecurity, data protection, technological certification standards, device regulation, cross-border telemedicine, and accountability for the safety of hardware and software. Additionally, questions arise regarding criminal and civil liability in cases where actions pose risks to life or health or result in harm or damage.

Despite the importance of addressing these ethical and legal challenges, Nigeria lacks specific legislation on telemedicine, and the existing legal framework is fragmented. Relevant laws span sector-specific domains, including health, communication technologies, and legal processes, making the determination of liability complex. This lack of clarity exposes patients to potential exploitation and undermines the widespread adoption of telemedicine by healthcare providers. Additionally, the absence of a well-defined legal framework hinders the incentives for healthcare technology providers to develop and scale telemedicine solutions. Furthermore, the academic attention given to legal perspectives on telemedicine in Nigeria, particularly regarding liability, has been limited. This long essay thus sought to address these gaps by providing a comprehensive analysis of the legal landscape surrounding telemedicine and its implications for liability.

This essay has therefore critically analysed the liabilities that may arise in the practice of telemedicine in Nigeria, with the aim of fostering a safer telemedicine ecosystem and improving healthcare delivery in the country. The objectives of the essay were to examine the legal framework governing telemedicine, assess the scope of civil and criminal liability for medical practitioners and non-medical telemedicine providers, and explore the novel considerations brought on by telemedicine that could impact the conventional incidence of telemedicine.

Based on this background, the essay established a conceptual and theoretical framework for telemedicine in Nigeria in the second chapter. It noted that the concept of liability holds significant importance in the study and practice of law, as it serves as the foundation upon which legal actions are built. Liability can be defined as the legal responsibility assigned to an individual or entity for a particular action or omission. It encompasses both civil and criminal wrongs, wherein liability is imposed based on different principles and remedies. Liability can be further categorized into two primary forms: remedial liability and penal liability. Remedial liability focuses on providing compensation or redress to the injured party, while penal liability aims to hold individuals accountable through punishment. However, it is worth noting that liability is not always imposed solely on the basis of fault or intention. In some cases, liability can arise under the concept of no-fault liabilities, such as absolute liability, vicarious liability, and strict liability.

In the context of healthcare, references to liability primarily pertain to tort claims, although criminal liability may also come into play. Common types of claims in the realm of medicine and health were classified into physician liability, corporate liability, and product liability. When considering telemedicine, liability further encompasses the combination of telecommunications or information and communication technologies (ICT) and healthcare. Therefore, it becomes crucial to address ICT-related liabilities, notably incidents related to data protection and cyber torts due to its reliance on cyberspace. With regards to their interrelationships, it was diagrammatically explained that product liability and corporate liability occurs both in main healthcare liabilities and ICT liabilities, establishing third-party intermediaries as key players.

The theoretical framework on which the study was based is the theory of remedial liability, positing that since a primary function of law is to provide remedies when persons suffer wrong due to the actions of another, the liability imposed on the wrongdoer must be clear and adequate, taking into account novel developments that may create new species of wrongs. However, existing literature on liability in telemedicine predominantly focuses on identifying potential legal and ethical issues, with limited studies analysing liability from a country-specific approach and examining the applicable legal frameworks.

In the third chapter, the domestic and international framework for telemedicine in Nigeria was exhaustively discussed, including the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (CFRN)

1999 as amended, Medical and Dental Practitioners Act 1988, Child Rights Act 2003, National Health Act 2014, Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act 2018, Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, Nigerian Communications Act of 2003, Cybercrimes (Prevention, Prohibition, etc.) Act 2015, Code of Medical Ethics, Patients' Bill of Rights, Nigerian Criminal Code, Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948, and the African Charter on Human and Peoples Rights 1981. It was established that fragmentary as the laws were, they covered key aspects of liability in telemedicine including medical malpractice/negligence, patient privacy/confidentiality, data protection and cyber security, right to health/patient-consumer protection/product liability, informed consent, licensure and professional regulation, technological certification standards, and cross-border telemedicine.

Next, chapter four critically analysed the existing liabilities in the practice of medicine and explored the potential impact of telemedicine innovations and developments on these liabilities. It considered various aspects such as negligence, malpractice, informed consent, patient privacy and confidentiality, licensure, and the determination of liability in relation to vicarious liability and third-party telemedicine corporations. The rapid emergence of new knowledge and technology in the medical field constantly challenges the establishment of appropriate standards of duty in specific cases. Telemedicine introduces yet another evolution to the medical profession, raising questions about where the duty of care arises and how to determine liability. This is particularly complex when telemedicine platforms are utilised, as establishing causation becomes more challenging. It was further noted that due to the bias towards medical professionals and intervening factors brought into play by telemedicine, proving telemedicine-related negligence in Nigeria based on current case law might be even more arduous than conventional negligence.

Furthermore, the increased adoption of cloud computing in the telehealth sector poses significant security and privacy challenges. Balancing the need to protect patients' privacy and to ensure the security of information systems and patient data becomes crucial. As such, liability can be extended to include criminal liability of hackers, for instance, and strict liability might apply to telemedicine platforms or healthcare providers who fail to attain specific security standards leading to breach. It is noted that the legal framework in Nigeria significantly protects patients with regards to data privacy and cyber security.

In the context of telemedicine, the principle of informed consent, which is based on patient autonomy and the right to control decisions about one's body, also warrants examination. Evidence suggests that virtual consultations, such as video conferences, can be clinically comparable to in-person consultations in many specialties. However, determining liability becomes complex when a person without capacity, such as a child or someone mentally incapacitated, gives consent through the anonymity provided by the internet. The validity of such consent and the potential liability of medical professionals acting on such consent will need clarification. Also, the standard of informing patients of care delivered through telemedicine platforms may need to be lowered where language barriers exist as many African languages do not integrate complex terms relating to telemedicine technology.

Moreover, the standard of liability concerning the registration of medical professionals remains unchanged in telemedicine in Nigeria, despite novel issues of cyber torts (fraudulent representation) and cross-border telemedicine. While prioritising patient safety, the requirement for "limited" registration of foreign-trained professionals presents an obstacle due to its rigorous process. To address this, it is recommended that the Medical and Dental Council of Nigeria (MDCN) consider easing the registration process by utilizing the discretionary powers granted to them under the Medical and Dental Practitioners Act (MDPA). This would facilitate the speedy registration of certified foreign medical professionals sought after by telemedicine providers. Additionally, the presence of telemedicine intermediaries and the concept of vicarious liability broaden the scope of potential liability and enhance the chances of a plaintiff-patient obtaining appropriate redress. This development in telemedicine positively influences the outcome of litigation for wronged patients, as it expands the possibilities for holding liable parties accountable.

In conclusion, the introduction of telemedicine brings forth various legal and ethical considerations. It significantly impacts existing liabilities in medicine, necessitating a critical evaluation of physician and healthcare provider liabilities, informed consent, patient privacy and confidentiality, licensure, and the determination of liability. These issues highlight the need for robust legal frameworks that address the unique challenges posed by telemedicine while ensuring patient safety and access to justice.

5.2. Recommendations

5.2.1. Recommendations for Patients

For patients making use of telemedicine platforms, the following recommendations are proffered:

- Awareness: Patients should be aware of their rights and responsibilities as outlined in the Patient's Bill of Rights.
- Verifying the healthcare provider's credentials: Patients should ensure that the healthcare provider delivering the telemedicine service is licensed and qualified to practice medicine in Nigeria.
- Maintain privacy and security: Patients should protect their personal health information by ensuring that they use secure and encrypted telemedicine platforms as much as practicable.
- Prompt reports of any complications, adverse reactions, or concerns about the telemedicine services received to the healthcare provider or the telemedicine platform.
- Reviewing consent forms: There is a tendency where the use of the internet is concerned for persons to not apply the same diligence in reading agreements as they will normally do. Patients or users of these platforms should do well to read consent forms and other agreements as they outline the terms and conditions of the telemedicine services, including potential risks and liabilities.
- Seeking legal advice where necessary: Although this is not common practice in Nigeria, patients should consider seeking legal advice from qualified lawyers who are knowledgeable about telemedicine regulations and practices in Nigeria where they might have suffered from malpractice or have any pressing concerns.

5.2.2. Recommendations for Medical Professionals and Telemedicine Providers

The following recommendations are suggested for medical professionals and telemedicine providers:⁴⁹³

- Promoting telemedicine literacy: Telemedicine platforms can include educational content for patients to enhance their understanding of their condition, treatment options,

⁴⁹³ Some of these recommendations are adapted from policy statement and this article: Khairat, S., Chourasia, P., Muellers, K. A., Andreadis, K., Lin, J. J., & Ancker, J. S. (2023). Patient and Provider Recommendations for Improved Telemedicine User Experience in Primary Care: A Multi-Center Qualitative Study. *Telemedicine reports*, 4(1), 21–29. <https://doi.org/10.1089/tmr.2023.0002>

self-care practices, data privacy and cyber security, their general rights as patients, amongst others. This can help patients become more informed and actively participate in their healthcare.

- **In-Home Testing and Evaluation:** Generally, and especially for patients with limited mobility or disabilities, integrating in-home testing and nursing evaluation into the telemedicine visit can greatly improve the overall experience. This may involve sending healthcare professionals to patients' homes to perform necessary tests, evaluate vital signs, or provide specialised care, all within the telemedicine framework. One telemedicine platform that already adopts this model in Nigeria is Healthtracka.⁴⁹⁴ It is recommended that other telemedicine platforms model after this as international bodies have also maintained that telemedicine should be used in combination with, and not as a substitute for, conventional care delivery in order to improve patient outcomes.
- **Standard Cyber security Provision:** Providers should ensure that adequate cyber security measures are taken and that possible breaches are reported early to appropriate authorities.
- **Adequate methods for user and especially professional registration on such platforms:** Providers should work with the professional regulatory bodies to ensure that medical professionals who are registered to provide care are fully licensed and registered. This should integrate standard measures such as multi-factor authentication. Users should also be properly authenticated to avoid on-boarding malicious persons.
- **Access to Provider Notes and After-Visit Summaries:** Patients should have the ability to access their provider's notes and after-visit summaries from telemedicine consultations. This allows patients to review important information discussed during the appointment, understand the treatment plan, and have a record of their healthcare interactions, which can aid in continuity of care.
- **Technical Assistance for Patients:** To reduce the burden on physicians and improve the telemedicine experience, ancillary staff or care assistants can be trained to provide technical assistance to patients with limited digital literacy. They can help patients with setting up the necessary technology, troubleshooting issues, and ensuring a smooth telemedicine encounter. They can also call patients before their telemedicine visit to review medications and gather necessary information, which can alleviate the burden on physicians and allow them to focus on critical aspects of patient care.

⁴⁹⁴ <https://healthtracka.com/>

- Provision for users to log complaints and reports in real-time: This would help to keep medical professionals in check and also keep track with any challenges a patient might be facing on the platform.
- Establishing alternative dispute resolution mechanisms: Where a patient logs a complaint which might impact liability, providers may provide information about ADR mechanisms through which they can obtain some remedy. They can also inform the patient of the process involved in making complaints to the professional regulatory body.

5.2.3. Recommendations for Professional Regulatory Bodies

The following recommendations are proffered for professional regulatory bodies, particularly the Medical and Dental Council of Nigeria (MDCN);

- Development of clear guidelines establishing appropriate standards of care and obtaining consent: Following the example set by the American Medical Association in 2021, Nigeria should develop clear guidelines that outline the standards of care expected from healthcare professionals practicing telemedicine. These guidelines should cover various aspects such as patient assessment, diagnosis, treatment, and follow-up care. By establishing these standards, Nigeria can ensure that telemedicine services meet a certain level of quality and patient safety.
- Adequate monitoring and regulation of medical professionals using telemedicine platforms: MDCN should establish mechanisms to assess the qualifications, credentials, and competence of healthcare providers offering virtual consultations. Regular audits and evaluations can be conducted to ensure compliance with the established standards of care.
- Ease of registration requirements for licensed foreign medical professionals: Facilitating cross-border telemedicine can greatly benefit patients in remote areas or those requiring specialised care. To enable this, MDCN should ease the registration requirements for licensed foreign medical professionals seeking to provide telemedicine services within the country. By simplifying the registration process, Nigeria can expand access to quality healthcare services and leverage the expertise of foreign medical professionals in areas where local resources may be limited.
- Providing training for medical professionals on best practices in telemedicine both in current curriculums and for continuing professional development.

5.2.4. Recommendations for Policy/Law makers

With regards to policy and law makers, the following recommendations are hereby made:

- **Clear institutional guidelines:** The fragmented nature of the legal framework in Nigeria poses significant challenges in the regulation of telemedicine. With various regulatory bodies having overlapping functions, such as the National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA), Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC), Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Commission (FCCP), and Data Protection Council, there is a pressing need for clear institutional guidelines to avoid double jeopardy and over-regulation that may discourage telemedicine providers.
- **Reform of the National Health Act 2014:** This is necessary to reflect current developments and legislative gaps in telemedicine. The Act should be updated to include specific provisions and guidelines pertaining to telemedicine, ensuring that it is appropriately regulated and aligned with the advancements in healthcare technology. Areas that require attention include informed consent, third-party liability, certification standards, and revision of administrative penalties to make them more stringent. Informed consent is of utmost importance in telemedicine, as patients must fully understand the nature of the virtual healthcare services they are receiving and provide their consent accordingly. The National Health Act should establish clear guidelines on how informed consent should be obtained in telemedicine scenarios to protect both patients and healthcare providers. Furthermore, the administrative penalties associated with non-compliance in telemedicine should be revised and made more stringent. Stricter penalties would serve as a deterrent for healthcare providers who may otherwise engage in fraudulent activities or neglect patient safety. The revised penalties should be proportionate to the severity of the violations and aim to maintain the integrity and quality of telemedicine services.
- **Promote awareness of patient rights and issues in telemedicine:** Education campaigns can be conducted to inform the public about their rights, the potential benefits of telemedicine, and the safeguards in place to protect their privacy and confidentiality. By increasing patient awareness, trust in telemedicine can be enhanced, and concerns about its practice can be addressed.

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